

**SEVERE WEATHER ANALYSIS OF TORNADO (SWAT): SYNOPTIC AND
CONVECTIVE SETTING OF EF1 MANILA TORNADO
(14 AUGUST 2016) OVER PHILIPPINES**

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Major in Meteorological Sciences

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Approval Sheet

This thesis entitled “**Severe Weather Analysis of Tornado (SWAT): Synoptic and Convective Setting of EF1 Manila Tornado (14 August 2016) over Philippines**”, prepared and submitted by **CAPULI, GENERICH H.** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Bachelor of Science in Astronomy Major in Meteorological Sciences**, has been examined and is hereby recommended for Oral Examination.

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Abstract

This is the first case study conducted and related to a tornadic event in the Philippines. An extensive ground-relative, mesoscale, synoptic, and dynamic analyses was constructed to understand the cause of Manila Tornado development, which occurred at 14th of August 2016 and rated in Enhanced Fujita (EF) Scale as an EF1. Prior to the tornado occurrence, the tropospheric environment over Luzon resembles to an efficient convection process; a surface inverted trough along with the common monsoonal flow induced convergence and instability along the western Luzon and divergence aloft caused by an upper-level ridge. Along a typical tropic set up over the aforementioned area, the surface was moist and the warm buoyant air parcels managed to tap along the prime environment, especially at the peak of convective heating. A tornadic mini-supercell TSTM developed in the area of potentially unstable atmosphere with undiluted Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE) $\geq 1750 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and low-level CAPE $\geq 200 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ in both 00 and 12 UTC Tanay soundings. Without capping, this instigated a stout updraft that can withstand environmental entrainment and realize the available buoyancy by 70 to 80%. The updraft column also gained rotation because of the kinematics in place with ample and near-pure streamwise vorticity close to the ground accompanied in the substantial Storm-Relative Helicity (SRH) indices. This caused a tornado to occur from 0830 to 09 UTC 14 August 2016. When compared to the established U.S. baseline climatology, the Manila Tornado's cumulative vertical profile is within the distribution norms associated with tornadic supercell environmental setups. This study showed

that tornadic event in Manila was caused by a combination of; (a) Potential vorticity (PV) anomaly and possible ducted waves, which increased vorticity over the Metropolis, (b) Kinematic support due to the curved hodographs and wind profile, and (c) Thermodynamic instability that triggered the severe TSTM and tilted the vortex into vertical.

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CHAPTER I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

The chapter I is known as the problem and its background, which include the following parts: the introduction, research problems/research objectives, the theories and conceptual framework, scope and limitations of the study, significance of the study and the definition of terms.

Introduction

Estimated at 40,000 cases are reported around the world, a convective storm system like a thunderstorm (TSTM), or a cumulonimbus (cb), requires three (3) essential ingredients to form: low-level moisture, conditional instability over a layer of sufficient depth, and lift (Johns & Doswell, 1992; Doswell et al., 1996). The combination of low-level moisture and conditional instability allows warm air parcel to be more buoyant during its ascent. Then, the parcel is able to accelerate freely upward from the Level of Free Convection (LFC) where it first becomes positively buoyant. The third ingredient; lift, is vital to ensure that the parcel ascends to LFC, either through mechanically, orographically, or by gradients. Then, cold air sinks at ease for Deep Convection Initiation (DCI). This starts by forming cumulus clouds (cu) that continues to develop, visually seen as a tower-like structure where little to no rain but increasing lightning activity is experienced. In the mature stage, the updrafts and downdrafts within the cloud become more intense where the downward-moving air caused by falling precipitation results in the outflow (AMS, 2012j). Lastly, during the dissipating stage, the thunderstorm begins to weaken and the rain tapers off as the

Figure 1

Idealized Representations (Left) and Photographs of (Right) Convection.

Note: Courtesy of Bluestein (2013) and Hobbs and Rangno (1985)(b) Empirical Model and Features of a Small Cb Cloud.

remaining downdrafts push the storm's energy outwards (Houze, 2014). This is illustrated through a simple idealized model of dry convection by Bluestein (2013) in Figure 1.

Figure 2

Empirical Model and Features of a Small Cb Cloud.

Note: Courtesy of Hobbs and Rangno (1985)

Morphologically, TSTMs are divided into three classifications as in Chisholm and Renick (1972); single-cell, multi-cell, and supercell. Single-cells are known as the ‘Localized TSTM’ wherein it develops just one main precipitation shower with relatively small impact and follows the general life cycle as discussed above. Most of these are small, lasting only about an hour. The TSTM’s features were highlighted as in Figure 2. from Hobbs and Rangno (1985). However, single-cell TSTM takes on more relevance when it serves as a building block of a larger multi-cell.

Multi-cellular systems are like a garden-variety of TSTMs to one another with each cell having different life stages, a lifetime exceeds that of an individual (1 hr), and may produce hazardous convective weather conditions (HCW). The pattern of

cells within the storm mode is changing such as the downdraft air spread out in the boundary layer to trigger new TSTM cells (Houze, 2014).

Lastly, supercells, which are less common but receives much attention due to its strength and associated violent weather. Generating a supercell requires a deep, persistent mesocyclone a region of vertical vorticity with a characteristic width of 3-8 km as a result of tilting and stretching of horizontal vorticity along a mean bulk wind difference (Davies-Jones, 1984; Markowski & Richardson, 2009). They are frequently long-lived (1-4 hr life cycle are common) that occur in wind sheared environment and sufficient thermodynamic profile.

Distinctively, they are sub-classified into two (2) types that represents extremes (Bluestein, 2013) and between the extremes figuratively sketched in Figure 3; a Low Precipitation (LP) mode that occur in dry environmental conditions and High Precipitation (HP) form with its downdraft spreads out over the ground from the area of precipitation. Both forms can exhibit strong cyclonic (or anticyclonic) rotation in supercells which sometimes produce violent tornadoes, but with 'sometimes' implying only a fraction of supercells produce tornadoes (Trapp et al., 2005).

Tornadoes are also HCWs produced from severe weather phenomenon involving a violently rotating column of air that extends commonly, but not always, from a cb (in rare cases, a cu base) to the surface of the Earth. Typically, a tornado forms as a visible condensation funnel, whose narrow end touches the ground cloaked by a cloud of debris and can reach maximum wind speeds up to 135 m s^{-1} (486 km h^{-1} ; Alexander, 2010). Spawned from a severe TSTM along wind sheared environment

Figure 3

Schematic Diagram and Annotated Features of (a) High Precipitation and (b) Low Precipitation Supercell TSTM.

Note: Courtesy of Bluestein and Parks (1983)

and ample storm-relative inflow (Markowski & Richardson, 2014; Coffey et al., 2022; Peters et al., 2023b), it can be destructive to man-made structures and can lead to loss of life, especially in urban areas with high population, building density, and variable quality. Thus, making it difficult to describe a regional signature.

Tornado and Tornadogenesis research is mainly practiced in and focused on the western Great Plains of United States, known as the Tornado Alley (Gagan et al., 2010), due to their ideal topographic environment with at least a thousand tornadoes identified each year in the continental U.S. But tornadoes occur all over the world and cause damage and casualties. In particular, the east Asian countries such as Japan has an annual occurrence of 20–25 tornadoes, a casualty rate of 0.58, and injury rate of 29.7 on average as conducted by the Japan Meteorological Agency and previous studies (JMA; Niino et al., 1997; Matsui et al., 2009), while Fan and Yu (2015) reported an annual average frequency of 60 tornadoes in China during 2004–13. Both statistics are roughly 90% and 75% less frequent than the 250 tornado cases per year in Europe back in 2006–2010 of which came from the 9000 severe TSTMs reported annually (Groenemeijer & Kühne, 2014; Antonescu et al., 2017). Nonetheless, Markowski and Richardson (2010) asserts that these tornado statistics were significant to the aforementioned region requiring knowledge of the environment of the storms, which can be obtained through rawinsonde observations (RAOB) and/or numerical weather prediction (NWP) models.

In the Philippines, tornado reports were mostly based on the news outlets as captured and reported by common folks but no active research regarding tornado and/or tornadogenesis being conducted on the country. Therefore, a review of synoptic- and mesoscale conditions of tornadoes are required as it is still a challenge to predict based on the environment whether a tornado will develop or not requiring sufficient to extensive analysis (Tochimoto, 2022).

On the afternoon of 14th of August 2016 at 08 UTC (4:00 PM PhST), a severe thunderstorm is currently under its way and about to plow over the Metropolis moving east monitored through a radar. By 0835 UTC (4:35 PM PhST), a funnel cloud was spotted dropping a wedge-structure vortex signaling a tornadic activity in Quezon Blvd. to Sampaloc area. The tornado inflicted around 200 homes in Baseco, Manila (hereafter the Manila Tornado) which remained on the ground for 15 to 20 minutes and was rated as EF1 in the Enhanced Fujita (EF) Scale. This paper documents and aims to shed light to the severe weather event that happened on Metro Manila during the mentioned date by providing a case description and the meteorological conditions; both synoptic- and mesoscale, of the previously-said event which created a favorable unstable environment and preceded the tornadogenesis.

Theoretical Framework

Spatio-Temporal Atmospheric Scales and Processes

The atmosphere is an undulating structure with dynamic interactions between scales that drive the energy flow, including transfers between potential and kinetic energy. Specifically, meteorological features and processes occur across a broad range of spatial and temporal scales from micro to synoptic scale depicted in Figure 4. Local weather is driven by large synoptic and meso-scale features. Therefore, diagnosis of large-scale fields such as those of synoptic-scale indices allows to identify regions which have the greatest thermodynamic instability and favorable wind profile and hence should be considered to monitor and stitch meso-scale processes that are related to DCI.

Figure 4

Atmospheric Motion and Interaction. The Amount of Energy at each scale is indicated by the Energy Spectrum (solid black line). The light dashed and dotted lines indicate the Slopes of the Different Portions of the Spectrum. The Size of Typical Domains and Grid Cell Spacing for modeling at that scale are also included as a depiction of the Type of Motion represented by each scale.

Note: Courtesy of Haupt et al. (2017)

Previous studies from decades ago (e.g. Doswell, 1984; Rockwood & Maddox, 1988, and references therein) have studied cases involving synoptic- and mesoscale interactions, and hypothesized that these are critical in storm initiation, both prior and during the TSTM event. This reinforces the notion that the intensity and time of weather occurrence depend largely on the prevailing synoptic pattern. Recent studies such as from Choo et al. (2018), Meng et al. (2018), and Mathias et al. (2021) (and other references) include an overview to cover and linked both atmospheric scales.

Conservation of Energy: 1st Law of Thermodynamics

Figure 5

The Evolution and Spreading of Thermodynamics during the Past Two Centuries.

Note: Courtesy of Bejan (2016)

As noted by the mathematician and physicist Joseph Fourier in 1822 (Fourier, 1822),

Heat, like gravity, penetrates and occupy all parts of space.

It has been 3 centuries since the establishment of the foundation of thermodynamics and the branch of science itself shown in the progress of Figure 5, from Sir Isaac Newton's *Scala Graduum Caloris* or known as Newton's Law of Cooling (Newton, 1701) providing the first proof of heat transfer, to the contributions by the mathematician and physicist Daniel Bernoulli who laid the foundation for the Kinetic Molecular Theory of Gases and Hydrodynamics through his book *Hydrodynamica* (Bernoulli, 1738) which the latter eventually disentangled the caloric theory by Lavoisier and Dalton.

By the 19th century, Fourier (1822) provided and built his Theory of Heat Conduction in his book *Théorie analytique de la chaleur* (The Analytical Theory of Heat) or known as heat flow between two adjacent particles being proportional to the change of temperature based on Newton's work. 2 years later, the Father of Thermodynamics, Sadi Carnot published his book *Reflections on the Motive Power of Fire* (Carnot, 1824) which coined the term 'work' as an exchanged energy to or from an object or mechanism and has a unit of Joule (J), contributed by physicist James Joule in 1850 (Joule, 1850) as mechanical equivalent of heat; the cornerstone of the initial first law. By the 1850's, physicist Rudolf Clausius, who supported Bernoulli's conceptual idea, added the state function Entropy (S) term to the thermodynamic laws indicative of the heat lost, while Lord Kelvin introduced the term thermo-dynamics and Kelvin Scale. The 3rd and final zeroeth law were then derived by Walther Nernst in 1906 and by James Clerk Maxwell back in 1871 following his dynamical theory of heat and summarized as "*all heat is of the same kind*" (Maxwell, 1872; Bailyn, 1994).

Overall, the thermodynamic branch of science deals with the transformations of the energy in a system and between the system and its environment. An important part of the first law is the idea that heat and work are energy/heat transfers. That is, when a certain quantity of energy enters the system in the form of heat, the same quantity leaves the surroundings. When the surroundings perform work on the system, the increase in the energy of the system is equal in magnitude to the decrease in the energy of the surroundings. Thus, the total energy remains constant over time.

Figure 6

Conceptual Framework of Interconnection between the Heat or Energy Transfers in the Earth's Atmosphere and Surface involving Radiation, Conduction, and Convection.

Note: Courtesy of NOAA NWS

Speaking of heat transfers, it can occur through three modes; conduction, convection (natural or forced), or radiative process (Machowski, 2010; Holman, 2010). In atmospheric science, these three heat transfers are involved in every atmospheric process, from the global general circulation to the local transfer of radiative, sensible and latent heat between the surface and the atmosphere and the micro-physical processes producing clouds and aerosol as seen in Figure 6. Specifically, convection process is the prominent vertical energy transport; heat and moisture. Atmospheric

convection was laid down by Rossby (1932) who develop the theory of convection where small convective currents is established through mixing and constant potential temperature. This form of convection is made visible by cu clouds characterized by deep, saturated updrafts and downdrafts, and unsaturated downdrafts driven largely by the evaporation and melting of precipitation. Thus, convection currents are responsible for many weather patterns in the troposphere as the hot air mass rises, the air is replaced by the surrounding cooler, more dense air, what a person feel as wind.

Air Parcel Theory: from ground to cloud

Most, if not all, procedures to measure and analyze atmospheric stability are caused by the Parcel Theory or Air Parcel Theory by applying certain physical laws of hydrostatics and thermodynamics such as the conservation of energy (or 1st Law), primarily its convection transfer mode as simply shown in Figure 7.

Before it came to fruition, it was the contribution of Lewis Fry Richardson, FRS (LFR) towards modern meteorology and fluid mechanics, where he focused on water in clouds and thermodynamics of moving and radiating parcels of air (Richardson, 1919, 1922). This air parcel is a simple idea described by Bjerknes (1938) as a rising convective cloud generated by adiabatically lifting a parcel in an environment as assigned any or all of the basic dynamic and thermodynamic properties. By adiabatic, this is indicative of zero heat transfer while one thermodynamic parameter, temperature, decreases with height. This is known as lapse rate and defined as the negative of vertical temperature gradient;

Figure 7

Schematic Diagram of Rising Warm, Less Dense Air compared to Sinking Cooler and Denser Air, a staple of the Air Parcel Theory and overall Convection Process.

Note: Courtesy of NOAA NWS

$$\Gamma = -\frac{\Delta T}{\Delta z} = -\frac{T_2 - T_1}{z_2 - z_1}$$

The theory is based on the following assumptions;

- The air parcel does not mix with the environmental conditions, no external heat is added to the parcel.
- The initial low-level parcel rises dry adiabatically until it becomes saturated. This level is called Lifting Condensation Level (LCL). We define this dry adiabat as dry adiabatic lapse rate (DALR) as a constant;

$$\Gamma = 9.8^\circ\text{C km}^{-1}$$

similar to the acceleration due to gravity. This is due to gravity's role as it pulls cooler, denser air toward the earth's surface. As the denser air reaches the earth's surface it spreads and undercuts the less dense air which, in turn, forces the less dense air into a rising motion.

- Upon saturation where relative humidity reaches 100%, the air parcel then follows the saturated adiabats or Moist Adiabats within the thermodynamic diagram. We define this as the Moist Adiabatic Lapse Rate (MALR) as in Bakhshaii and Stull (2013) by integrating the following differential equation;

$$\frac{\delta T}{\delta P} = \left(\frac{b}{P} \right) = \frac{R_d T + L_v r_s}{C_{pd} + \frac{L_v^2 r_s e b}{R_d T^2}}$$

Where r_s is the saturation mixing ratio straightforwardly implemented and defined by Wallace and Hobbs (1977);

$$r_s = \epsilon \frac{e_s}{p - e_s}$$

for T in kelvins, and where the reference vapor pressure is $e_0 = 0.6112$ kPa at 0° C. Included in Bolton (1980) are also the parameters including the latent heat vaporization L_v of 2.5×10^6 J kg^{-1} at 0° C, gas constant of $R_d = 287.053$ J kg^{-1} , and the specific heat at constant pressure C_{pd} (~ 1004 J K^{-1} kg^{-1} at 0° C) all of which are at dry air.

The MALR is not a constant like the DALR, but is dependent on the parcel profile. Any saturated parcel cools at a slower rate because the process of water vapor condensing into a liquid releases heat. The released heat that is added to the atmosphere slows the rate of cooling.

- By then, the condensed water falls out of the parcel, so there is no freezing of the condensed water. Once the temperature of the rising parcel decreases to less than the surrounding atmosphere (due to its cooling), the parcel will become denser than the surrounding environment and gravity will slow, or even

reverse, the rise. This is called negative energy and means the atmosphere at that level is 'stable'. Meanwhile, once the temperature of the rising parcel remains higher than the surrounding atmosphere (despite its cooling), the parcel, being less dense than the surrounding environment, will continue to rise. That level is called Level of Free Convection (LFC), and the sounding is comprised by potentially unstable due to the positive buoyancy. The air chaff is then lifted until the Equilibrium Level (EL) is reached, i.e. when the parcel density becomes again equal to that of the environment.

Theory of Tornadogenesis

As discussed before, TSTMs can evolve into vigorous and highly organized units of convection known as supercells formed through sufficient thermos and ground-relative winds that turn and increase with height. In the northern hemisphere, like the Philippines and U.S., most supercells have a cyclonically rotating updraft that propagates to the right side of the observed environmental-wind hodograph curve (Bluestein, 2013). The cyclonically rotating region of a right-moving (RM) supercell is a mesocyclone. While the other being a meso-anticyclone due to its left-moving (LM) characteristics.

The genesis of the initial tornado in a supercell is a complicated process that generally takes over an hour after storm initiation. The tornado is generally preceded by a near-ground cyclone that is intermediate in size between a mesocyclone and a tornado. As documented by Davies-Jones (2015, and references therein) tornadogenesis in supercells likely occur in three-stages;

Figure 8

Model Simulation of EF5 Tornado on 24 May 2011, in Central Oklahoma. Looking at North, a Train of Vortices within the Vertical Vorticity Sheet (VVS) move in a Southwestward Storm-relative Direction along the Forward Flank. SVC marks the feature Streamwise Vorticity Current. The Red Arrow indicates the Vortex that becomes the Tornado. The Yellow Arrow indicates the Storm-relative Path of the Air within the SVC as it is approaching the Updraft.

Note: Courtesy of Orf et al. (2017)

1. Formation of a mid-level rotating updraft aloft caused by the tilting of environmental horizontal vorticity (Rotunno, 1981).
2. Development of a vortex at the ground.
3. Formation of the tornado (collapse and spin-up of the above cyclone)

Linear theory of dry convection in shear virtually explains initial net rotation of the storm's updraft at mid-levels as a consequence of tilting toward the vertical of low-level environmental streamwise (horizontal) vorticity by the updraft (Lilly, 1982, 1986; Davies-Jones, 1984; Dahl, 2017). The concept of Streamwise Vorticity

has been around since the second half of 1970s to 80s, firstly mentioned by Scorer (1978) and later on by Davies-Jones (1984) and Rotunno and Klemp (1985), that refers to the direction parallel to the local storm-relative wind;

$$\zeta_s = \frac{(v - c) \cdot (\nabla \times v)}{|v - c|}$$

where v and c are the wind velocity and storm motion vectors, respectively.

The resulting vertical vorticity is then amplified by vertical stretching in the lower part of the updraft and transported upward in the rising air, thereby extending the mesocyclone to anvil height in some cases. In the realm of forecasting mesocyclone formation and intensity, the storm-relative environmental helicity (SREH; Droegemeier et al., 1993), short for Storm-Relative Helicity (SRH), is evaluated (Davies-Jones et al., 1990) as it is far less sensitive to measurement error and sampling resolution than the streamwise vorticity.

In conjunction, more recent work has focused on the importance of environmental streamwise vorticity in the 0–500 m layer above ground level (AGL) (an integrated flux of the 0–500 m SRH) as an important forecasting toolkit for identifying between tornadic and non-tornadic modes (Craven & Brooks, 2004; Coffey & Parker, 2018; Coffey et al., 2019), and for its connection to low-level mesocyclone (LLM) development through modelling efforts (Coffey & Parker, 2015, 2017, 2018; Coffey et al., 2017). LLM formation precedes tornadogenesis in most long-lived TSTMs with rotating updraft, although the development of a LLM does not guarantee tornadogenesis (Trapp et al., 2005).

Previous supercell modeling efforts (e.g. Klemp & Rotunno, 1983; Rotunno & Klemp, 1985; Markowski & Richardson, 2014) and observational studies (Markowski et al., 2012) indicate that the LLM derives its rotation from horizontal vorticity induced baroclinically along the supercell's forward-flank. However, tornadoes can also form barotropically as a result of some high-angular-momentum air being transported downward and inward towards the axis of rotation as observed and modelled by Fujita (1975) and Davies-Jones (2008), respectively. More recent large eddy simulation (LES) modeling and visualization work by Orf et al. (2017) identified a highly-resolved and coherent structure in the forward flank of the storm termed the "streamwise vorticity current" (SVC) shown in Figure 8.

The SVC is a helical tube of streamwise vorticity that develops and oriented along the cool side of the forward-flank downdraft boundary (akin to the FFDB; Beck & Weiss, 2013) in a baroclinic zone where horizontal vorticity can be generated baroclinically and rises steadily as it approaches the updraft. This flow of streamwise vorticity tilted within the storm outflow is then by the storm updraft to create updraft helicity, providing a source for the LLM as a result of vertical perturbation pressure gradient force (VPPGF). The modeling study by Schueth et al. (2021) revealed that the SVC largely arises from the development of a Kelvin-Helmholtz billows (KHBs) located immediately behind the FFDB, with the strong streamwise vorticity arising primarily from stretching. The SVC has also been identified in other simulations, including mobile Doppler radar observations of both tornadic and non-tornadic supercells (Murdzek et al., 2020; Schueth et al., 2021).

Theoretical Model

Figure 9

Theoretical Diagram as Utilized in This Paper that involving the Atmospheric Processes and Scales, Air Parcel Theory derived from the 1st Law of Thermodynamics, and Vorticity-based Tornadogenesis. Interplay between these Theories results to a complete Atmospheric Dynamics to understand the cause and nature of a Hazardous Convective Weather (HCW).

Combining the theories discussed in previous sub-sections of theoretical framework and used for this study is presented in Figure 9.

While tornadoes are microscale to mesoscale phenomena, they are influenced by larger-scale synoptic conditions. Synoptic high- and low-pressure systems create areas of convergence (where air comes together) and potentially, divergence aloft (where air spreads out), which can influence the initiation of deep convection such as TSTMs.

For TSTMs to form, the atmosphere needs to be unstable, meaning warmer air is above cooler air. This instability can be caused by various factors like solar heating, differential cooling, or boundaries. Lifting mechanisms like cold fronts, orographic lift (air forced upwards by mountains), or convergence zones provide the initial upward

push for air parcels, triggering the release of positive buoyancy i.e. CAPE (to be discussed in Ch. III) and TSTM development. Storm-relative inflow winds feeds the TSTM allowing the storm's updraft to mature and intensify.

The environmental kinematics, particularly vertical wind shear; the change in wind speed or direction with height, plays a crucial role in magnifying TSTM development and its potential for tornadic activity. It allows TSTMs to be stout and attain mid-level rotation such as that it contributes to the stretching and tilting of the rising air parcel, creating a horizontal spinning motion. This rotation is then stretched vertically, concentrating the spin and forming a vortex. The stronger the shear, the more intense the rotation and the higher the chance of a tornado developing.

All these variables are interconnected and influence each other. Subtle forcing mechanism, high buoyancy, strong vertical wind shear, and sufficient moisture create a favorable environment for explosive TSTM development. The storm relative inflow feeding onto the updraft interact with the wind shear to create and intensify the rotation, eventually leading to tornado formation or any other HCW under the right conditions. Melding these theories allow the researcher to understand the '*complete picture*' – Atmospheric Dynamics, that act as the conductor, orchestrating the complex interplay between various forces that can ultimately lead to tornado formation. However, it's important to remember that this is a complex system and the exact mechanisms of tornado initiation are still being researched. Still, understanding these interconnections aids us to nail down the processes, better predict, and prepare for these dangerous weather events.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 10

Meteorological Thesis Framework as Utilized in This Paper that Includes Micro-, Meso-, and Synoptic-scale Processes and Models (on the Last Two Enunciated Scales) to determine the Severe Weather Event that occurred on 14 August 2016.

Synoptic and mesoscale models and its patterns are two tools in the same toolbox to determine microscale elements, thus they are interdependent variables where each driver act as an independent variable. As analogy from the *Comet MetEd*

Program deduced to simple conceptual idea displayed at Figure 10, the details on microscale patterns such as gathered from surface observations like meteograms serve to understand the mesoscale processes such as convective systems suitable for tornadogenesis and other HCWs; in this case serving as the "carves". While mesoscale discussion can be in form of upper-air soundings and even NWP models that provide mesoscale indices acting as a more precise tool like a "chisel". Thus, involves combining the parcel method and looking at the wind profile of the area of interest.

At the same time, mesoscale environment is accompanied and driven by synoptic process providing larger-scale context that guides the development of mesoscale phenomena by inducing insight into the structure, movement, and dynamics of weather systems over a wide geographic area. The conditions provided by the synoptic environ serve as the "hammer" that guides the development of the mesoscale elements. Thus, in an 'artist's eye', this requires a combination of scientific knowledge, experience, and intuition especially in this fringe case of the tornadic event on 14th of August 2016, hence the dependent variable. Synoptic drivers can be depicted through observed synoptic charts every principal hours and in conjunction with large-scale NWP models such as those from ECMWF and GFS. Overall, larger-scale features set the stage for smaller-scale events. Thus, synoptic systems like high and low pressure create conditions that favor the development of mesoscale phenomena like TSTMs that affects the microscale such as pressure, temperature, and other microscale parameters/drivers.

Statement of the Problem

This research seeks to shed light on the tornadic event using available observations and numerical systems that occurred on 14th August 2016. Thus, answer the following questions:

1. What is the case description of the severe weather event during 14th of August 2016 i.e. general weather condition and tornado characteristics?
2. What is the synoptic setting during 14th of August 2016 when the severe weather event occurred?
 - a. From Gridded Data Products
 - b. From Upper Air RAOB conducted at Laoag, Baguio, Tanay and Legaspi Upper Air Stations
3. What is the mesoscale atmospheric environment of the target area during 14th of August 2016?
 - a. From Gridded Data Products
 - b. From Upper Air RAOB conducted at Tanay Upper Air Station
4. From the vertical cross section, what is the dynamic evolution of the target environment during 14th of August 2016?

Hypothesis

The environmental condition, both synoptic- and mesoscale, are accompanied by stable conditions inhibiting severe weather and tornadic initiation to occur on 14th of August 2016 around Metro Manila, Philippines such as that of EF1 Manila Tornado.

Research Paradigm

Figure 11

Research Paradigm as Utilized in This Study.

Research paradigm allows the proponent to display the systematic flow of the procedures to be conducted as entirely displayed in Figure 11.

Initially, we will look and gather for the advisory on the TSTM and snapshots (photographic and video evidences) of the Tornado from different news outlets, including the PAGASA Damage Assessment for document/content analysis

containing radar images. Consequently, we will request for the Advanced Himawari Imager (AHI) data products from Data Integration and Analysis (DIAS) that includes Bands 1 to 3. Each individual bands of the HIMAWARI-8's bands were stacked together and visualized using Matplotlib. Additionally, we will request AWS measurements from the networks operated by the Manila Observatory, lightning data from World Wide Lightning Location Network (WWLLN), and *in situ* observations near the severe weather target area; Port Area, Manila from the DOST-PAGASA. Specifically, the in-situ data is accompanied by a 3-hour temporal resolution, observations' synoptic codes (SYNOP) are decoded accordingly using NumPy, all of which are visualized in Matplotlib.

Next, the University of Wyoming (UWyo) contains archived soundings around the world that's regionally. Primarily, our interest will be the 98433 Tanay RAOB at 00 and 12 UTC (8 AM and PM). However, we also include other stations such as RPLI 98233, RPUB 98328, and RPMP 98444 in order to compute for the atmospheric (in)stability across the whole country. Focusing on our interest, we will analyze the RAOBs using different meteorological tools that computes for the thermodynamic and kinematic profile of the atmosphere for the preceding severe TSTM. This includes UWyo's pre-computed convective parameters, COMET MetEd's interactive Skew-T, pyMeteo (Webster, 2022), MetPy (May et al., 2022), thundeR rawinsonde package (Taszarek et al., 2021), and PAGASA's Damage Report that includes the vertical profile computed via the Universal Rawinsonde Observation Program (RAOB).

On the other hand, we acquired our observed synoptic charts from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) through Digital Typhoon and most importantly, Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) models from two different centers. Firstly, we source for the ERA5 Reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) by Copernicus and Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) of the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) via the Copernicus' Climate Data Store (CDS). Lastly, we also used NCEP FNL (Final Analysis; NCEP, 2015) as generated by Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS) and used in Global Forecasting System (GFS) through Research Data Archive in the National Center for Atmospheric Research managed by the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (NCAR/UCAR).

Both products are $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grids with ERA5 Reanalysis (hereafter ERA5 Re) having a 60-minute temporal resolution, both for single and pressure levels. Meanwhile, the NCEP FNL have a temporal resolution of 360 minutes (6 hours) as the cycle across all the variables. We analyze and visualization as maps and charts both NWP products using MetPy with Matplotlib and Cartopy module.

Overall, the study will generate an in-depth case description, provided thermodynamic and kinematic profiles coming from observed and model-based; both pre and post-initiation, synoptic-scale and mesoscale charts/maps, cross-section diagrams, and compare this case to other severe weather environment being published as in U.S. Great Plains (Rasmussen & Blanchard, 1998; Thompson et al., 2003). All of these results are used to depict, document, and understand the tornadic event.

Significance of the Study

This study entitled, **Severe Weather Analysis of Tornado (SWAT): Synoptic and Convective Setting of EF1 Manila Tornado (14 August 2016) over Philippines** is essential to the following; **World Meteorological Organization (WMO) in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), National Government, Meteorological science students and alike, and Proponents.**

At the top, the **WMO and its SDGs**, more specifically; SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 13 (Climate Action), is the co-custodian of those facets. The WMO community's challenge is to provide decision-makers with the scientific facts and analyses they need to adapt to climate change impacts and build climate resilience. As severe weather can damage or destroy vulnerable infrastructure, resulting in both economic and human losses. Thus, this study will benefit to countries of investing in weather and climate-resilient infrastructure in accordance to the WMO Severe Weather Forecast Demonstration Project such as the use of sophisticated radars and Automated Weather Stations (AWS) and climate-proofing of infrastructure in coastal and other climate-vulnerable areas. Additionally, we contribute to the body of knowledge that the mesoscale driver is also driven by climatological setting of the country that affect our day-to-day and local environment.

On the other hand, the **National Government**, especially embodied in the primary weather bureau; DOST-PAGASA and its meteorologists. There are gaps in the study of dynamics and forecast methods of mesoscale systems and

tornadogenesis. Through this research, it will help them review the current understanding about tornado and tornadogenesis and align forecasting strategies and parameters to predict which severe TSTM can spawn tornadoes and improve accuracy of TSTM and tornado warnings to reduce the damage and casualties in the long run. As such, this allows possibilities to prevent them before they can do any damage.

Additionally, the findings of this study could be utilized by the **Meteorological science students and alike** as a starting step toward developing a concept inventory to measure the meteorology students' understanding of tornado behavior. Furthermore, students can obtain data and information relevant to their studies through this research. It will be of help gathering additional information needed for studies about tornadogenesis. Their studies and career in meteorology could be greatly impacted by this study.

Tornadoes are still among the least understood weather phenomena. Tornado size and intensity are almost never determined directly; instead, indirect inferences are used almost exclusively. More so, very little is known about the interactions between factors, their interaction and its impact on tornadogenesis. To better forecast which storm in a region with tornado potential will create a tornado, a deeper understanding of science during tornadogenesis is important. Thus, this study will aid and supplement **proponents** for future research regarding mesoscale-related themes, TSTMs and its potential HCW entailed, including the expansion of theories and concepts that are addressed in this paper.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study is only focused in determining the environmental condition of the tornadic event that occurred on August 14, 2016 located in the Manila, NCR, Philippines. A case description along the historical pictures and video evidences, radar and satellite visualization and most importantly, the respective synoptic and convective stability indices are presented which will be the primary variables and needs. We are only limited to acquiring radar images as we are not able to completely source for the raw reflectivity and velocity product in PAGASA perhaps due to confidentiality.

Our synoptic environment from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL cases are primarily derived as in the model runs at 06 UTC (2:00 PM PhST) in align to the standard conceptual regional charts. Hence, this is a pre-convective environment. The extent of the bounding box for the synoptics are zonally from 105° E to 140° E and meridionally from 0° N to 25° N which puts the archipelago right on the center of the synoptic structures.

From there, the dynamical cross section analysis (Vertical Cross Section, VCS) covers zonal direction of 115° E to 125° E. The temporal resolution of the VCS starts at 00 UTC to 09 UTC at a timestep of 3 hours. Furthermore, the cross section involved and map out Potential Temperature and Vorticity for determining convection as it decreases with height along a stable layer. We will further discuss these two meteorological parameters and importantly, the others related and utilized in this study at Ch. III.

Meanwhile, our mesoscale environment was partitioned into two; an observed and calculated/modelled. Our observed mesoscale features the upper-air soundings that are principally flew at 00 and 12 UTC (8:00 AM and 8:00 PM PhST). This makes the 00 UTC as the start of the 'Pre-Tornadic Environment' and 12 UTC as the 'Post-Tornadic Environment'. We will take only the available balloon launching stations as indicated via the UWyo's server for RAOB as the rest of other stations scattered in the country are used for surface observations.

Lastly, the modelled environment, that includes the charts from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL, starts at 08 and 06 UTC, respectively. Both datasets were offset by few hours as the ERA5 Re was gathered in an hourly basis while NCEP FNL releases the 'analysis' (nowcast) every 6 hours in line with those of the regional synoptics. Spatial extent of the mesoscale maps is from 117° E to 125° E towards the zonal direction and 13° N to 20° N, meridionally. We extrapolated, created, and modelled upper-air soundings from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL that are based on 121.00° E and 14.60° N; the coordinates of target area Manila. This also entails its environmental wind profile of the sounding displayed in the hodograph for the kinematics. Here, the temporal resolution takes in as an intermediate forecasting hour for every 3 hours starting from 00 to 18 UTC.

We did not add other meteorological and/or climatological parameters such as the Madden-Julian Oscillation (MJO) Amplitude signal, Outgoing Longwave Radiation (OLR), and El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phases which are other forms that may affect DCI and used to generate an acceptable initial consensus to the event and

succeeding severe ones. We will also use the upper-level and surface synoptic charts provided by JMA for quick observation reference. Additionally, the paper did not tackle the performance of the ensemble models utilized, but evaluating instead the severe weather environment it may portray. Last, but not the least, we did not conduct any high-resolution compute model simulations by using a set of atmospheric profile of interest. We leave this as another subject matter open for further research especially in the country's meteorological setting.

Furthermore, it is also plausible that the particular geographical configuration of Metro Manila has also an affect. Directly across Manila Bay, around 60–70 km from Metro Manila, are the Natib and Mariveles stratovolcanoes which partly encloses the Manila Bay. Lagmay et al. (2015) assessed the orographic influence of these two volcanoes especially during SWM seasons. The aforementioned work found out that the orography of these volcanoes leads to air mass rising and converging rapidly on the lee side, hence a lee-side TSTM, exhibited as a plume-like pattern under the radar. In a future work, terrain and orographic features should be also a point of consideration with regards to studying severe mesoscale events i.e. tornadoes, hails etc.

Overall, the study will then allow to stimulate and increase the interest in providing further studies regarding TSTMs, including severe ones, and other mesoscale processes in the future by analyzing synoptic and mesoscale indices, including that of conducting advance computing platforms for rapid dissemination of TSTM advisories from various convective parameters.

Definition of Terms

The following are the prominent meteorological terms used in this study and as described in the *Glossary of Meteorology* of Glickman (2000) and other articles;

Cb. Abbreviation for Cumulonimbus clouds exceptionally dense and vertically developed, occurring either as isolated clouds or as a line or wall of clouds with separated upper portions. From this cloud leads to its popular appellations; Thunderstorm (AMS, 2012a).

Debris Ball. Also known as radar Tornadic Debris Signature (TDS) is an area of high reflectivity on weather radar data caused by debris lofting into the air, usually associated with a tornado (Bunkers & Martin, 2011, Bodine et al, 2013).

Hodograph. A component of the Skew-T diagram i.e. sounding/RAOB, where individual wind vectors at selected levels are plotted, typically on a polar coordinate diagram, from the region of the diagram toward the direction from which the wind blows. The lengths of the vectors are proportional to the corresponding wind speeds. Each line corresponds to the wind shear vector in the layer concerned (AMS, 2012d).

Hook Echo. A feature of a severe TSTM i.e. tornadic supercell identifiable in a radar scan caused by the precipitation being pulled into the mesocyclone. This is typically shallow hook-shaped area of reflectivity is often associated with a tornado (AMS, 2012e).

Inverted Trough. Also known as an Easterly Wave (or inverted pressure perturbation), is a wave within the broad easterly current and moves from east to west,

generally more slowly than the current in which it is embedded and consists of a weak trough of low pressure. Occasionally, associated into tropical cyclones (AMS, 2012b).

Mesoscale. Pertaining to atmospheric phenomena having horizontal scales ranging from a few to several hundred kilometers, including thunderstorms, squall lines, fronts, precipitation bands in tropical and extratropical cyclones, and topographically generated weather systems such as mountain waves, and sea and land breezes (AMS, 2012f).

Overshooting Top(s). Abbreviated as OTT(s), a domelike protrusion above a cumulonimbus anvil, representing the intrusion of an updraft through its equilibrium level (EL). Persistent OTTs are frequently observed with severe TSTMs and its updraft plumes (AMS, 2012g)

Severe Weather. Also called as Hazardous Convective Weather (abbreviated as HCW) or storm is usually applied to severe local storms in particular, that is, intense thunderstorms, hailstorms, and tornadoes (AMS, 2012c, 2012h).

Synoptic-scale. Used with respect to weather systems ranging in size from several hundred kilometers to several thousand kilometers, the scale of migratory high- and low-pressure systems (frontal cyclones) of the lower troposphere (AMS, 2012i).

Tornado. A rapidly rotating column of air extending vertically from the surface to the base of a cumuliform cloud, often with near-surface circulating debris/dust when over land or spray when over water. Although its presence is not required, a funnel

cloud is often visible and may partly or fully extend from the cloud base to the ground (AMS, 2020).

Tornadogenesis. A complex and dynamic process, influenced by a range of atmospheric conditions involving thermodynamics and kinematics. A key factor in tornado development is the wind profile and its difference, as it creates a horizontal rotation in the atmosphere that can be tilted vertically by updrafts within the storm (Markowski & Richardson, 2010).

TSTM. Abbreviation for a Thunderstorm. A cloud type caused by atmospheric instability by which always accompanied by lightning and thunder, and occasionally by strong gusty winds, hail, heavy rains, and possible tornadoes (Byers & Braham Jr, 1949; AMS, 2012j).

Upper Air Sounding. Also called as upper air observation, radiosonde or rawinsonde observation (abbreviated as RAOB), and shortly known for sounding and vertical profile. A measurement of the thermodynamic and kinematic state of the atmosphere received from a balloon-borne instrument (AMS, 2012k, 2022).

Weak Echo Hole. Also known as Weak Echo Region (WER), is an area of markedly lower reflectivity, resulting from an increase in updraft strength that can develop during the maturing phase of a tornadic TSTM (AMS, 2012l).

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter contains all of the related studies and literature, both foreign and local that are related with this study.

General Weather Condition

Weather conditions within the archipelago are determined by its climatological norms interlinked to mesoscale drivers. One of the HCWs that have significance to such agricultural countries and associated to moist mesoscale processes such as TSTM complexes is that of rainfall. The climate of the Philippines is classified by PAGASA under four climate types using the Modified Coronas Classification (Coronas, 1920; Kintanar, 1984) based on variation in space and time of rainfall visualized in Figure 12 and in a climatological assessment of Villarin et al. (2016).

Initially, Metro Manila is located on an isthmus between two bodies of water, Manila Bay, which opens to the West Philippine Sea and Laguna de Bay. Elevation is typically at 10 - 30 m making its characteristics as flat to rolling. The area is then enclosed by Sierra Madre Mountain Range (SMMR), the Marikina River which joins the Pasig River and drains directly toward the two bays, and the northern slopes of Ancestral Taal Volcano at the south. This makes the metropolis as one of the widest floodplains in the Philippines underlain by mostly volcanic and coastal sediments (Lagmay et al., 2010).

The distinction of floodplain is further worsen by its geographic location with respect to the country's climatological normal. Situated at the western portion of the

Figure 12

Four Climate Types of the Philippines based on Modified Coronas Classification Scheme. Location of the 49 PAGASA stations are denoted. Elevation is indicated as shading.

Note: Courtesy of Peralta et al. (2020)

Philippines, it was characterized by pronounced wet season influenced by the southwesterlies from May to October and the dry season from November to April caused by the prevailing winds are the north Pacific easterlies, with maximum rainfall during June to September (Jamandre & Narisma, 2013). However, the timing of the

wet season can vary depending on the onset of the southwesterly wind that flows at the country, tied to the Asian summer monsoon (Akasaka, 2010).

Other types such as Type II climate has a pronounced peak in the wet season from November to December without a defined dry season caused to the northeast monsoon, trades, and easterlies. In addition, Type III environ has no pronounced seasonal cycle but has relatively high rainfall from May to October, similar to Type I, while the last of the climate topology, Type IV climate, has rainfall more or less distributed throughout the year (Francisco et al., 2006; Moron et al., 2009).

Meanwhile, Cruz et al. (2013, and references therein) classifies the Philippines to have three seasons based on rainfall variability and prevailing wind pattern: the influence of the northeast monsoon (NEM) running at November to March, the summer trade winds (SUM) from April to May, and the southwest monsoon (SWM) season starting from June to October. Despite that, both classifications are widely used in conjunction with each other for various atmospheric scales and climatological normal studies.

By identifying diurnal and seasonal characteristics within the area from years 2013-2014, Bañares et al. (2021) uncover the frequency of rainfall events in line with the seasons enunciated by Cruz et al. earlier depicted in Figure 13. Specifically, the persistence of rainfall (and the likelihood of convective TSTM) within the area of interest occurs throughout the day, evident in the SWM period. In the recently mentioned study, there were two small peak occurrences at 0200 PHT and 0800 PHT,

Figure 13

Diurnal Variation of Rainfall across Metro Manila defined by Rainfall Variability and Major Wind Pattern.

Note: Seasons are based on Cruz et al. (2013). Courtesy of Bañares et al. (2021)

contributing 4% and 5% to the total number of occurrences of rainfall events in this season, respectively. The highest number of rains during the SWM season occurred at 1500 PHT, which is 10% of the total number of downpour events observed during the period of study. This is contributed by the warm, moist monsoon winds initiating deep convective activity over the western coast of the Philippines (Akasaka et al., 2007; Akasaka, 2010; Cruz et al., 2013; Kubota et al., 2017).

Other seasons such as the NEM and SUM seasons have peak occurrence of 14.5% at 1600 PHT and 19% observed at 1400 PHT, respectively. Overall, most of these rainfall events induced by convective clouds occurred for approximately 6 hours, from noontime towards the late in the afternoon due to favorable thermodynamics (Johnson, 2010; Bañares et al., 2021, and references therein).

Mesoscale Drivers

During the wet season in the Philippines, particularly in Metro Manila, the SWM act as wind pattern in the western coast of the country bringing warm and humid air mass as a result of passing of parcels over large areas of warm equatorial body of water. Warm air is more buoyant, tending to rise, which is aided by the already warmed land surface; as the moisture-heavy air cools, it then precipitates as a downdraft caused by TSTMs (Wakimoto, 1982; Bhate et al., 2016). Thus, forming a sea breeze, which can effectively alleviate the urban heat island effect (UHI; Lutgens et al., 1995; He, 2018) and acting as a large convection cell assisted by the presence of stronger surface heating at daytime in triggering TSTMs (Silva Dias & Jaschke Machado, 1997; Lericos et al., 2002).

Sea breeze occurs under relatively cloud-free skies (sometimes even in obscure cases), when the surface of the land heats up more rapidly than the sea. The thermal contrast creates a local to mesoscale pressure gradient force (PGF) directed from sea to land, as a shallow layer of marine air moves inland in response. Miller et al. (2003) provided in-depth review of 'sea breeze system' (SBS) shown in Figure 14.

Generally, the SBS is consist of sea breeze circulation (SBC), mathematically modeled and described by using the Bjerknes circulation theorem in combination of ideal gas law (IGL) and mean wind speed (Holton, 1992). However, the formulation assumes friction is negligible, and hence tends to overestimate. Other authors (Masselink, 1998, e.g.) have suggested that speeds as high as 10 m s^{-1} are common.

Figure 14

Illustration of Sea Breeze System (SBS).

Note: Courtesy of Miller et al. (2003)

Meanwhile, the other components such as the sea breeze gravity current (SBG) is the low-level landward flow of moist marine air. The leading edge of the SBG is usually marked by a sea breeze frontal zone (SBF) that resembles a synoptic-scale cold front (Chiba, 1993; Finkle et al., 1995; Simpson, 1999). The SBF may be bifurcated into a thermodynamic front and a kinematic front, where the former is the leading edge of the marine air's influence and interaction between the SBC and horizontal convective rolls (HCRs), and the latter is the point of maximum low-level convergence between the marine and continental air masses. At the boundary-layer and the interface between the sea-breeze and the return flow aloft, Kelvin-Helmholtz instability billows (KHB) develop when the Richardson number (Ri) is smaller than ~ 0.25 (Taylor, 1931).

Strong vertical currents are associated with the front creating a raised sea breeze head (SBH) above the SBF that may reach twice the height (~2 km) of the feeder flow behind the SBF. Thus, these vertical currents initiated and/or amplified by the post-frontal vortex of the SBF, including other external features, can cause convective clouds and TSTM initiation (Atkins et al., 1995; Nicholls et al., 1991; Shepherd et al., 2001; Fovell, 2005). This allows low-level moisture, characterized by high humidity, to be modulated by the frequency of moist convection along the SBF (Baker et al., 2001; Crosman & Horel, 2010). TSTMs are observed on 70% of the sea-breeze days with SW streamflow such as SWM. In cases such as Cape Canaveral, Florida, the periods with SW sea breeze passage have been found to be the most humid and most favorable for convective development due to the coupled instability (López & Holle, 1987).

Once a balloon sounding is launched at such occasion of an unstable atmosphere where sea breeze like SWM is in effect and plotted in a thermodynamic diagram known as Skew-T chart (Herlofson, 1947), the accompanied profile is characterized by deep moist layer with relative humidity over 70% to above 6 km, close to moist adiabatic, representative of fairly minimal variations to the dewpoints and temperature values. Without (or with minimal) presence of capping inversion layer, the lapse rate is conditionally unstable with measured stability indices (Lifted Index and Total Totals Index; to be discussed in Chapter 3) owing some resemblance to a 'loaded-gun' scenario.

Figure 15

A sample of 'Rain sounding' coming from a Tropical Cyclone as plotted on Skew-T log P Diagram. The varying Blue and Red lines corresponds to Dewpoint and Temperature profile with decreasing order by Height (and/or Pressure). X-axis, coupled with Diagonal Lines, is Temperature, while Isobaric Pressure on Y-axis.

Note: Courtesy of NOAA NWS

Though, convective activity may initiate as a single cb due to lack of ambient vertical wind shear or wide-spread cells at any given time as the modest vertical wind profile restrains the gust front, hence maintaining the storm mode and developing new cells adjacent to it (Chisholm & Renick, 1972; Weisman & Klemp, 1982), even evident on Tropical Cyclones (TCs) as studied by Edwards et al. (2012). This is known as a "Tropical sounding" or "Rain sounding" after Lt. Col. Robert C. Miller analyzed 38 representative CONUS soundings and classified them as Miller Type 2 soundings. A sample Miller Type 2 sounding is illustrated in Figure 15.

In line with Bañares et al. convective initiation during the afternoon, maximum rainfall over these stations and at the said time is shown to be consistent with the late-afternoon undiluted potential thermodynamics due to the warming of the surface throughout the day (Diurnal Convective Heating; Dai, 2001) and perhaps caused by the planetary boundary-layer (PBL) heating in the daytime, and the land and sea breeze circulation (Byon & Lim, 2005).

Synoptic Drivers

Synoptically, SWM develops through a convergence zone where northeasterly trade winds on the north side of the equator and southeasterly trade winds on the south side collide. The air is heated on its approach to the equator leading to a general rising motion in the lower latitudes, the Intertropical Convergence Zone with a corresponding sinking at higher latitudes (Hadley, 1735), completing the equatorial general circulation now known as the Hadley Cell. In addition to that, due to the planetary movement, the northward movement of the ITCZ drives the monsoonal circulation (Pant & Kumar, 1997). The land-sea thermal contrast leads to a pressure gradient (during the monsoon, the land is low pressure, and the sea is high pressure), which was discussed earlier as a sea breeze circulation (SBC), and drives the monsoonal circulation. Dai et al. (2013) enunciated that the converging wind is dynamically coupled with the upper wind interaction.

Almost 80% of all sea-breeze days with TSTM have synoptic-scale flow from the southeast or southwest. Located over the western rim of the Pacific Ocean, the Philippines is vulnerable to such events that inducing extreme heavy rainfall/flood

(HRF) events in the country (Cayanan et al., 2011; Cruz & Narisma, 2016; Kubota et al., 2017). Thus, synoptic weather types have been shown to provide information on local-scale rainfall occurrence (Deme et al., 2003) of monsoon circulation systems. Using decadal-worth of data, Neumann (1970) found that these southwesterly winds are prominent at 850-hPa favorable for TSTM development. Furthermore, the middle troposphere between 400- and 600- hPa is the layer of greatest convergence, all increasing from the periphery inward leading to an upward motion. The result then can be categorized into two circumstances;

1. Deep nimbostratus with embedded cumulonimbus when vertical wind shear and lower tropospheric convergence both are large (although rain intensity may fluctuate considerably, skies remain predominantly overcast), or
2. Scattered towering cumulus or cumulonimbus, when vertical wind shear and lower tropospheric convergence both are small.

These two circumstances were supported by the findings of Ye et al. (2018). It was found out that the main mechanism of mesoscale convective activity is through the lower convergence of low-level airflow strengthened by the uplift of terrain, and the middle-level divergent flow. The uplift of terrain strengthens the convergence of low-level airflow forcing an ascent.

Other types of synoptic-scale phenomena include low pressure areas intensifying into TCs, tropical easterly wave (TEWs) troughs, and ridges. In particular, TEWs are the other low-pressure systems observed in the WPAC and within the trade wind belt, initially described and identified by Riehl (1954) in the Caribbean Sea as the

Figure 16

Tropical Easterly Wave Model. Progressing from East to West, note that Winds Shift generally from Northeasterly to Southeasterly within the Pressure Perturbation and its associated Low Pressure Area as seen in the Wind Barbs. The Inverted Trough is often preceded by Good Weather and followed by wide Cloud Cover and Precipitation.

Note: Courtesy of Nicholson (2017)

source of many TCs. Typically, they have a horizontal wavelength typically between 2000 and 5000 km, and a preferred periodicity of 2–7 days (Burpee, 1972; Carlson, 1969b, 1969a; Kiladis et al., 2009). The disturbance axis, usually oriented SSW-NNE, coincides with an inverted pressure trough moving westward.

As noted by Frank (1969), local winds shift from northeast to southeast once it passes. Since most easterly waves move more slowly than the environmental air, changes in vorticity along air parcel trajectories imply sinking motion and fine weather west of the axis, this is known as divergence. Meanwhile, rising motion and poor weather east of the axis is indicative of convergence. Indeed, Frank (1970) observed

that these tropical cloud clusters are generally associated with synopticscale features in the wind field. The notion is then supported by previous modelling efforts of such systems by Kiladis et al. (2006) (and references therein) where dynamical forcing, which induces vertical motion at low levels, is possibly needed for deep convection to initiate and mature, respectively. A diagram of tropical wave is shown as in Figure 16.

Recent studies (Ferreira & Schubert, 1997; Serra et al., 2008; Toma & Webster, 2010) have provided further observational and theoretical evidence to suggest many of these waves in a form of in situ at the Pacific and are generated through barotropic or inertial instability of the ITCZ, evident at 850- to 700-hPa levels. Absolute instability (Lindzen et al., 1983; Diaz & Aiyyer, 2015) may also have important implications for easterly wave genesis, where barotropic or inertial instability is present and the zonal flow may be absolutely unstable where moist convection may initiate. Others authors (e.g. Hill & Lin, 2003; Mozer & Zehnder, 1996) have suggested that inverted tropical troughs can be generated by mountain-induced lee vortices.

Tornado Climatology and Events in the Tropics

Tornadoes are known to occur in all regions of the world where TSTM develop (Feuerstein et al., 2005). They have been observed on every continent, except Antarctica (Goliger & Milford, 1998; Brooks & Doswell, 2001) and are most likely to occur at latitudes between 20° and 60° N of the equator (Berz et al., 2001; Fujita, 1973; Goliger & Milford, 1998). Places such as Mexico, Europe, western Asia, Japan, Bangladesh, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, China, and Argentina also have a relatively fair amount of tornadoes that occur each year (Goliger & Milford, 1998).

Figure 17

Monthly Distribution of Florida Tornadoes from 1987 to 2016.

Note: Courtesy of Ryan (2018)

Some tornadoes, however have occurred outside of this region and are not limited to these given latitudes. If conditions are favorable, tornadoes may occur anywhere on Earth. In Florida, situated in the subtropics above the Tropic of Cancer line, tornadoes occur within lines of TSTM ahead an advancing cold front from the northwest, within single isolated TSTMs, or within the rotating TSTMs associated with a TC (Hagemeyer & Schmocker, 1991; Hagemeyer, 1997). Due to its proximity to the Gulf of Mexico and the Atlantic Ocean, Florida typically has enough moisture content in the air to support TSTMs. Under these conditions, the main ingredient for tornadoes are winds above the ground moving with increasing speeds and veering directions.

Figure 18

Monthly Distribution of Tornadoes, Waterspouts, and Total Tornadoic Activity in Mexico from 2000–2020. The Black Line indicates the Monthly Mean Precipitation (1961–2000) in Mexico.

Note: Monthly-Averaged Rainfall Data from Muñoz-Arriola et al. (2009) and Zhu and Lettenmaier (2007). Courtesy of León-Cruz et al. (2022)

Specifically, the wet seasons are accompanied by deep moist layer with greater undiluted potential energy due to diurnal heating and veering westerly winds in the mid-levels and upper-levels indicating increasing wind shear. Over the period from 1987 through 2016 as conducted by Ryan (2018), there were 1,765 tornado reports in the state, >1000 tornado cases happened based on the wet season classification of Gerrish (1969) shown in Figure 17. The peak frequency occurs during the month of June with the overall tornado distribution mimicking the TC distribution of the North Atlantic hurricane season.

Some countries also exhibit tornadic activities within the tropical belt (roughly 23.5° N and S) where it was home to 40% of the world's population as of 2014. In Mexico, 378 tornadoes and 99 waterspouts were reported up to year 2020. The tornado season, which involves tornado and waterspout events, runs from March to October. León-Cruz et al. (2022) untangled that the tornado season peaks in the warm spring and summer period, primarily in May and in July as seen in the monthly distribution in Figure 18. A sample of significant event in the mentioned country is the EF3 Coahuila Tornado observed on May 25, 2015 in the state of Coahuila documented by Barrett et al. (2017) and León-Cruz et al. (2017).

The late cold front passage activity from the North and arrival of easterly waves to Mexico (Dominguez et al., 2020) favors the moisture advection from Gulf of Mexico (GOM) or Eastern Pacific Ocean (EPAC) to the continental areas which is a primary ingredient in convective environments, thus for instability (Romero et al., 2007). With the right ingredients in place at such timescale albeit a passive, if not sufficient, wind shear, tornadic activity is intensified over the influence zone of the Transmexican Volcanic Belt (TMVB) that runs from EPAC to GOM in central Mexico due to the environmental conditions (León-Cruz et al., 2021).

By late fall, the sufficient moisture within the area results to maximum undiluted convective energy especially in the areas of Sierra Madre Occidental (SMOc) at the EPAC region that coincides with the North America Monsoon System (Adams & Comrie, 1997). This area is also influenced by the northward displacement of the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) as discussed by Cerezo-Mota et al. (2016).

Figure 19

Photographs of EF2 Wenchang Tornado and Damage indicators such as Farmstead and Tree Damages.

Note: Courtesy of Xue et al. (2016)

Closer to our country in China, tornadoes occur in front of a southwest to northeast trough at 500-hPa, with the subtropical high-pressure area (hPa) located in the east or southeast (Zhou et al., 2022). Along its territorial limits, in the Hainan Islands/Province, southwesterly wind flow and (extra)TC with strong upper-level jet streams enable the production of environments that are rich in VWS in the warm sector, thus enhancing the potential of tornado outbreaks in the area (Mercer et al., 2012; Tochimoto & Niino, 2016).

The highest rated tornado incident in the area was an EF3 back in May 29, 2008 which remains unstudied while recent tornadoes back in 2016 were documented by Xue et al. (2016). In particular, the Wenchang Tornado that formed at Fengpozheng of Wenchang City on June 5, 2016 was associated with an afternoon SBF along which convection was initiated verified through surface observations shown in Figure 19. As we have tackled, SBFs tend to be also associated with southwesterly winds, in this case, monsoonal flow. Thus, it kickstarted the tornadogenesis. Additionally, the intense updraft accompanying the explosive storm development provided the intense low-level stretching for the stove-pipe vortex intensification.

SYNTHESIS

Located in a tropical country, Metro Manila is susceptible to mesoscale processes across different climatological seasons every year. The nation's capital is flagged as a Type I environment due to the pronounced rainfall starting at May to October due to the SWM, associated with large-scale Asian monsoon system, with its maximum during June to September. And as we have learned of, rainfall is caused by convective patterns in the troposphere such as TSTMs. Current literature supports the occurrence of TSTMs in the afternoon due to the favorable instability the SWM brings, especially in the western portion of the Philippines.

Speaking of western portion of the Philippines where Metro Manila is located, the warm buoyant air that passes in the previously-mentioned area tends to rise assisted by the surface heating. The thermal contrast creates a pressure gradient force directed from sea to land acting as a convective cell, thus a sea breeze

circulation (SBC). The leading edge of the known as the gravity current of the sea breeze (SBG) may resemble as a mid-latitude frontal system that can transform either a thermodynamic front and a kinematic front, where the former is the leading edge of the marine air's influence and interaction between the SBC and horizontal convective rolls (HCRs), and the latter is the low-level convergence between the marine and continental air. Within the frontal-like system, vertical currents exist and may cause TSTM due to the low-level moisture being advected. In most cases, SBCs are accompanied by SW winds and instability generating convective TSTMs. Furthermore, the return flow aloft of the SBC may develop Kelvin-Helmholtz Billows, which when tackled earlier, is linked to horizontal vorticity and tornadogenesis.

The typical thermodynamic profile of such environment can be classified as a Miller Type 2 sounding. This is entailed by deep moist layer with high relative humidity to above 6 km, close to moist adiabatic. Without (or with minimal) presence of temperature inversion, the warm air parcels is then easily lifted. The storm mode however may diverge into an air mass TSTM (single cell) if lack of vertical shear or multi cells if the wind profile is sufficient to restrict the gust front. The thermodynamics of the SWM and the associated possible storm modes, especially in the tropics, initiate during the afternoon and is consistent with the undiluted CAPE, diurnal maximum cycle, PBL heating, and presence of an SBC system.

SWM, overall, is formed through synoptic-scale interaction between northeasterly trade winds on the north side of the equator and southeasterly trade winds on the south side forming a convergence belt, which then sinks at higher

latitudes. The synoptic system is dynamically evident in the boundary-layer pressure level and maximum convergence at the mid-levels leading to upward motion of parcels which can trigger convective development and HCWs. Thus, providing local-scale phenomena once it performs its transition to a mesoscale low.

There are other synoptic-scale systems that may occur during the SWM period. In particular, tropical waves moving west are inverted pressure perturbations. Furthermore, these waves occur within few days to a span of a week generated via barotropic and zonal instability. They are also known as inverted trough comprised by '*entrance*' and '*exit*' gate where changes in vorticity along air parcel trajectories imply sinking motion while rising motion and poor weather east of the axis is indicative of convergence, respectively but depending the environmental wind field direction. In the case of SWM once applied, the gates are then flipped around with the *entrance* of the inverted trough is the convergence implying convective initiation while the other being divergent for fair weather.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research method used, sampling scheme, description of variables, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis and its corresponding treatment of the data.

Research Method Used

A case study and its quantitative scheme was utilized on this paper to document and explore the event or phenomenon in depth and in its natural context. In this paper, the natural environ would be the tornadic event that happened in Manila dated back 14th of August 2016. Although the methodology is heavily connected to qualitative forms, the quantitative model can be used to profoundly describe and explain the phenomena using elements of the empirical-analytical scientific approach that would not have been possible in the classical way (Mills et al., 2010). Thus, the researcher was presented with the numerical data obtained from the in-situ observations in Manila, the Tanay sounding and from a couple of weather models; NCEP FNL and ERA5 Re. Jointly, a short qualitative analysis is used due to the integration of archived documents and warnings coming from PAGASA, including several news agencies.

Generally, the approach such as a case study is useful for multi-faceted explorations of complex and contemporary issues in their real-life settings across a wide variety of disciplines (Crowe et al., 2011), including meteorology. Several authors have conducted and have case accounts for tornadic events. This includes, but not

limited to, recent studies by Davies (2017), Meng et al. (2018), and Mathias et al. (2021), even utilized alongside modelling efforts as in Litta et al. (2012) and Orf et al. (2017).

Sampling Scheme

Under the non-probability, purposive sampling or *expertise sampling*, is utilized as deliberate choice of data to align the qualities the event and its surrounding possesses, in this case the severe weather event and its environmental conditions, respectively. It does not need underlying theories or a set number of parameters. Simply put and in meteorological application, the researcher decides what needs to be known and sets out to find the variables and key aspects with an aim to increase depth. Gathering this appropriate and useful information-rich cases is conducted per some logic, carefully but not randomly (Kelly et al., 2010; Patton, 2014). In this study, we will combine the schemes conducted by Meng et al. (2018) and Mathias et al. (2021) (and other related authors) that includes an overview to cover and linked across three atmospheric scales. Locally (or in micro-scale), we employ surface observations from the nearest PAGASA station in Port Area at Manila, photos of the tornadic event, satellite image of the TSTM using HIMAWARI-8 acquired through DIAS, and the radar images and advisories provided by PAGASA through its published damage assessment document as part of the case description.

Next, we source for the upper air sounding across the country, primarily the Tanay Station with a WMO ID of 98433 through University of Wyoming (UWyo) server for RAOB. The said server does provide a pre-computed thermodynamic profile such

Table 1

Characteristics of NCEP FNL and ERA5 Re domain, synoptically used in this study.

NWP Model	Characteristics	Remarks
NCEP FNL	Horizontal Grid spacing	0.25° x 0.25°
	Vertical levels (sigma)	26 vertical levels
	Temporal resolution	3-hr forecast and 6-hr analysis
	Timeframe	08/14/16; 06 UTC
	Latitude extent	0° N - 25° N
	Longitude extent	105° E - 140° E
ERA5 Re	Horizontal Grid spacing	0.25° x 0.25°
	Vertical levels (sigma)	137 hybrid sigma-pressure levels
	Temporal resolution	Hourly
	Timeframe	08/14/16; 08 UTC
	Latitude extent	0° N - 25° N
	Longitude extent	105° E - 140° E

as CAPE, CIN and other parameters (to be discussed in Data Analysis section) and cumulatively, balloon launch stations across the Philippines can be used to compute for the Brunt Vaisala Frequency Squared as for atmospheric stability and observed synoptic measurement.

In relation to synoptics, we will acquire gridded-data products such as ERA5 Re and NCEP GFS FNL from CDS and NCAR data servers, respectively. Both datasets provide extensive synoptic parameters to identify large scale meteorological processes such as, but not limited to, vorticity, hourly average precipitation, mean sea level pressure (MSLP), and heights, including model-based convective parameters to be discussed in succeeding sections. A procedure of data gathering of meteorological data, is also presented in a detailed fashion and paradigm suitable for case studies to be discussed in the following sections of this chapter.

Description of Variables

Synoptic-scale Indices are variables that describe the large-scale weather patterns and features that are typically observed and analyzed based on a combination of observations and model output. Temporally and spatial can scale hundreds to thousands of kilometers and of a few hours to a few days. These indices are used to help diagnose and forecast weather on this scale and can provide insight into the structure, movement, and dynamics of weather systems over a certain region or area. These are mostly derived with NWP models based on NCEP FNL and ERA5 Re. The characteristics of each NWP models are in Table 1.

Meanwhile, Mesoscale Indices, also known as Convective Indices, quantifies various thermodynamic and kinematic parameters that have been designed in the past decades. These reflect the potential for thunderstorm development according to the prevailing properties of the air mass. Mesoscale indices from NWP models and the ones derived by soundings made it possible to explore convective environments and their corresponding climatologies in a way that was not possible with prior reanalyses. Generally, the characteristics were similar to that of synoptics except for the spatial and temporal extent as marked in Table 2.

Another is the Micro-scale Indices. These are known for various parameters and measurements that are used to describe and quantify atmospheric conditions at a very small scale, as measured through in-situ or Automated Weather Stations (AWS). These indices are used to describe the behavior of the atmosphere in the lowest few meters AGL or typically at the surface where local variations in

Table 2

Similar to Table 1 but for mesoscale domain used in this study.

NWP Model	Characteristics	Remarks
NCEP FNL	Horizontal Grid spacing	0.25° x 0.25°
	Vertical levels (sigma)	26 vertical levels
	Temporal resolution	3-hr forecast and 6-hr analysis
	Timeframe	08/14/16; 00 - 12 UTC
	Latitude extent	13° N - 19° N
	Longitude extent	117° E - 125° E
ERA5 Re	Horizontal Grid spacing	0.25° x 0.25°
	Vertical levels (sigma)	137 hybrid sigma-pressure levels
	Temporal resolution	Hourly
	Timeframe	08/14/16; 00 - 12 UTC
	Latitude extent	13° N - 19° N
	Longitude extent	117° E - 125° E

temperature, humidity, and wind speed, particularly in urban areas, can have a significant impact on weather conditions and people's daily lives.

Overall, the basic starting point of this account is the analysis of the local- and meso-synoptic system, as well as quantifying main thermodynamic instability and kinematic indices which caused the tornadic development. Taking into account the fact that this tornado belongs to extraordinary and HCWs, research methodology for extreme weather events have been used consequently. In order to get a better understanding of this meteorological phenomenon, the method of synoptic and mesoscale analysis, rawinsounding, and its associated thermodynamic and vertical wind profile analysis was performed (For further reading, see analysis and methodology of Choo et al., 2018; Mathias et al., 2021; Meng et al., 2018; Rockwood & Maddox, 1988, and references therein). We discuss each technique that was utilized in succeeding sub-sections of this chapter.

Research Instrument

We will use different meteorological instruments to source for all the available and appropriate data inline to the study of interest. Highlighted below are the research instruments;

- **Climate Data Store** – Abbreviated as CDS, is the heart of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S; Thépaut et al., 2018; Buontempo et al., 2022). CDS contains observations, historical climate data records, Earth Observation-based datasets in terms of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs), global and regional climate reanalyses, global and regional climate projections and seasonal forecasts through a unified web interface. Thus, acts as ‘one-stop shop’ for users to discover and process the data and products that are provided through the data repositories and even toolboxes (Raoult et al., 2017).
- **COMET MetEd Skew-T** – This is an interactive tool provided by the MetEd University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR) and its COMET Program; Skew-T Mastery. The interactive Skew-T is used to plot vertical profiles of atmospheric profiles. These come from numerous sources such as RAOBs, dropsondes, NWP model output, and satellite sounders.
- **Manila Observatory** – Established through a public-private partnership, the Manila Observatory operates 16 automated weather stations (AWS) acting as a mesonet (or mesonet) such that weather features on the mesoscale can be resolved. The AWS model used in collecting data is the Davis Vantage Pro 2 Plus, which has a tipping-bucket rain collector, temperature and humidity

sensors, a cup-style anemometer and wind vane, ultraviolet, solar radiation sensors and a barometric pressure sensor. With a temporal resolution of 5 minutes, the collated data were screened and checked to verify if the values for each meteorological variable were within acceptable range limits for the region based on a pre-determined data screening criterion (Meteorological Resource Center, 2002).

- **Research Data Archive** – Abbreviated as RDA, contains a large and diverse collection of meteorological and oceanographic observations, and operational and reanalysis model outputs, integrated via NCAR High Performance Compute (HPC) resources to support atmospheric and geosciences research. The RDA is managed by facilities within the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), a program by the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR).
- **Personal Computer** – The corresponding author's system is composed of a 6C12T Ryzen 5 5600x, RTX 3070, 32 GB of DDR4 3600 CL16 RAM, two (2) 500 GB of Samsung 970 EVO NVMe used to host two (2) different operating systems; Windows 10 Pro and Ubuntu 21.04 Long Term Support (LTS). For the data analysis and visualization, Ubuntu was used together with Anaconda Navigator and its Jupyter Notebook.
- **PAGASA Damage Assessment** – PAGASA released a Damage Assessment report after the tornadic episode that occurred on 14th August 2016 which highlights observational data, i.e. upper-air sounding, radar images, and

photos, utilized to incorporate impacts as provided and conducted by the Manila Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office (MDRRMO). The said publication file is available through the agency's publication section.

- **Pictures and Videos** – With pictures and video evidences from various netizens and news outlets, the researcher then managed to add credibility, illustrate and provide additional context towards the tornado episode. This makes a conclusive evidence supporting the claims made in this case study.
- **Python** – A high-level programming language that emphasizes code readability and simplicity. Python supports various programming paradigms, including procedural, object-oriented, and functional programming. For this study, it was used for scientific computing, data analysis and visualization. The libraries I used are enumerated as following;
 - **Cartopy** – A Python package designed for geospatial data processing in order to produce maps and other geospatial data analyses that is utilized in this study, both synoptics and mesoscale in the Philippines. Elson et al. (2021) described the package as a tool that uses PROJ, NumPy and Shapely libraries and includes a programmatic interface built on top of Matplotlib for the creation of publication quality maps.
 - **Matplotlib** – Matplotlib is a 2D graphics package used for Python for application development, interactive scripting, and publication-quality image generation across interfaces and operating systems (Hunter, 2007). This is a core package in the entire suite of python packages.

- **MetPy** – MetPy is an open-source and community-driven Python package for meteorology, designed to fit well within the scientific Python stack (numpy, matplotlib, etc.). Its goal is to bring the scripted weather analysis capabilities of GEMPAK (and tools alike) to the powerful scientific Python ecosystem. Thus, MetPy’s general functionality breaks down into: reading data, meteorological calculations, and meteorology-specific plotting (May et al., 2022). In this case, this was intended for synoptic and mesoscale computation and applications across the entire case study.
- **NumPy** – NumPy arrays are the standard representation for numerical data and enable efficient implementation of numerical computations in a high-level language (Harris et al., 2020). Hence, a requirement to all of the python packages utilized in this case.
- **Pandas** – A Python library of rich data structures and tools for working with structured and common data sets, mostly evident in the sounding profiles in this study. The library provides integrated, intuitive routines for performing common data manipulations and analysis on such data sets (McKinney, 2010).
- **pyMeteo** - This package contains general meteorological routines and specific routines to work with CM1 and WRF (Hoyer & Hamman, 2017). The general routines include the generation of Skew-T/Log-P plots used in this study sourced from the Tanay Upper Air Station.

- **SciPy** – A library of numerical routines for the Python programming language that provides fundamental building blocks for modeling and solving scientific problems. SciPy includes algorithms for optimization, integration, interpolation, algebraic and differential equations and many other classes of problems (Virtanen et al., 2020). This makes SciPy as the foundation upon which higher-level scientific libraries are built.
- **Seaborn** – A library for making statistical graphics in Python. It provides a high-level interface to Matplotlib and integrates closely with Pandas data structures (Waskom, 2021). The functions of the seaborn library expose a declarative, dataset-oriented API making it easy to translate questions about data into graphics. In this case, used to generate box plots intended for the analyzing the cumulative severe weather characteristics.
- **SounderPy** – This packaged used to access vertical profile data for calculations or plotting of a vertical profile (Gillett, 2023). SounderPy's main use is for getting the datasets such as observed RAOBs from UWyo and IGRAv2 and from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL that are utilized in this study for the mesoscale analysis of the tornadic environment.
- **xarray** – An open-source project and Python package that provides a toolkit and data structures for N-dimensional labeled arrays. Inspired by Pandas with the Common Data Model for self-described scientific data, the package includes label-based indexing and arithmetic,

interoperability with the core scientific Python packages and out-of-core computation on datasets that don't fit into memory. xarray, as a data model and analytics toolkit (Hoyer & Hamman, 2017). This has been widely adopted in the geoscience community, multi-dimensional data analysis in physics, and even machine learning. In particular, used to read and process NetCDF and/or GRIB files associated in the study.

- **thundeR** – A freeware R package and collection of functions for rapid computation and visualization of convective parameters commonly used in the operational forecasting of severe thunderstorms (Taszarek et al., 2021). This is the 'primary' tool used in the sounding analysis of the Tanay RAOBs.

Data Gathering Procedure

In this study, the proponent considered different ideas such as synoptics and mesoscale meteorological indices, instruments that must be used, and where to gather the applicable and sufficient meteorological data. Foremost, case studies utilize the 'triangle' technique or Data Triangulation. This allows to investigate between the phenomenon (in this case the tornado) and context (meteorological environment from various scales) that is shrouded in question(s); hence requires multiple sources of evidence (Yin, 2014).

Preceded on Figure 9, we dissected and transformed the conceptual diagram into three (3) parts as a source procedure of the required data and show interconnection between scales upon obtaining the needs. The data gathering method is displayed in Figure 20 and is conducted thoroughly by the enumerated steps:

Figure 20

Triangulation Method conducted to acquire the Necessary Meteorological Datasets for the Case Account of the Tornado. Arrows indicate that each information are Dynamically Interconnected as in the Thesis Framework presented in Figure 8.

1. Requesting of surface observations initially with AWS Measurements from Manila Observatory across Metro Manila with its 5-minute temporal resolution and surface variables. These are distributed over an area of about 625 km²

with locations at large cities, populated low-lying areas, and near the coastline. In this study, we follow Bañares et al. (2021) where the stations within Metro Manila are described and grouped accordingly into five sectors: Sector A in the northwest (near Manila Bay), Sector B for central inland, Sector C in the northeast (near Sierra Madre Mountains), Sector D in the east (near Laguna Lake), and Sector E in the south. The previously mentioned author provided a map of the sectors as in Figure 21. In relation, we will also source for 3-hr temporal resolution in-situ measurement from DOST-PAGASA's station in Port Area, Manila as archived through OGIMET Synops section. These are released via specific lines for international exchange purposes.

2. Gathering of Pictures and Videos of the Tornadic event posted from various media/news outlet, including from social media (e.g. ABS CBN, Rappler, Facebook, Twitter), as reported by common folk and netizens with complete courtesy. This will be put to use for the case account of the HCW event.
3. Acquiring of lightning activity data from the WWLLN. WWLLN is a network of ~70 sensors that detect very low-frequency (3-30 kHz) radiation packets produced by lightning strikes. Furthermore, by providing global coverage due to its downrange detection at distances of thousands of kilometers, the network is able to detect both intracloud (IC) and cloud-to-ground (CG) lightning strikes. Since detection efficiency increases with the peak current of each, WWLLN is more efficient at detecting CG lightning due to the associated higher peak currents (Dowden et al., 2002; Jacobson et al., 2006).

Figure 21

Map of National Capital Region with locations of the Manila Observatory AWS Instruments categorized into Five Sectors (White Circles). Colors indicate Levels of Residential Density: Low (Orange), Medium (Red), and High (Maroon). Topography of the Sierra Madre Mountain Range is indicated in contours (m).

Note: Map courtesy of GED-Manila Observatory and Bañares et al. (2021)

4. Acquiring of Weather Advisories from DOST PAGASA and Upper Air Soundings of 14th August 2016 through UWyo's Department of Atmospheric Science as conducted by the previously mentioned weather bureau. The measurement is conducted with a 12-hr principal interval at 00 and 12 UTC. Balloon launch stations include; (1) Tanay (98433; Area of Interest), (2) Legaspi (RPMP - 98444), (3) Laoag (RPLI - 98233), and (4) Baguio (RPUB –

98328). Other stations, aside from Tanay station, are included to allow computation of atmospheric stability across the country.

5. Requesting of raw HIMAWARI-8 Bands 1, 2, and 3 through DIAS which have access and ports to the HIMAWARI-8 and 9 satellite. Each band we're stacked together using Python and Matplotlib to create a visualization of the target area using RGB image as in AHI. DIAS is an infrastructure for collecting and analyzing Earth Observations (EOs) and socio-economic data.
6. Solely for the synoptics, we acquired observed weather charts released by the Japan Meteorological Agency. the Regional Specialized Meteorological Center (RSMC) of the Asia-Pacific Regime. These maps are queried via the Digital Typhoon. The database was spearheaded by the National Institute of Informatics which provide daily satellite images and weather maps, even past images, through Japan Meteorological Business Support Center (JMBSC).
7. Gathering of synoptic and mesoscale meteorological indices from gridded NWP products. First is the ECMWF and its ERA5 Reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) in the Copernicus' C3S as provided by the CDS (Raoult et al., 2017; Thépaut et al., 2018). ERA5 includes the single (surface quantities) and pressure levels (upper air fields) on an hourly basis with a latency of 5 days. The product and the associated and queried levels have a grid resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. Overall, the reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world benefiting from improved model physics, core dynamics, and data assimilation.

8. Another and last gridded data are sourced via the NCAR Research Data Archive (RDA) that is the NCEP/GDAS FNL (NCEP, 2015) made from the same core of GFS model. This gridded data as acquired has $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grids prepared every 6 hours. NCEP FNL contain the same data sources with difference in the amount of 'real' data assimilated into the initial conditions for FNL, ingesting around 10% more observational measurements.

Data Analysis and Treatment

Synoptically, we computed the following parameters to illustrate large-scale processes, measure the instability, and give prognosis prior to the tornadic event using and from NWP products and upper-air soundings. Enumerated below are;

1. Geopotential Height ($Z_g(h)$; decameter/dam) – The height of a given point in the atmosphere in units proportional to the potential energy of unit mass (geopotential) at a height relative to sea level. This is typically seen on upper air maps where a plot of geopotential height for a pressure level in the atmosphere shows the troughs and ridges. Wallace and Hobbs (2006) express this as the;

$$Z_g(h) = \frac{\Phi Re}{gRe - \Phi}$$

where Φ is the geopotential and Re is the average radius of Earth.

2. Divergence (∇F ; s^{-1}) – Divergence, and its opposite Convergence, usually used to refer specifically to the horizontal inflow or outflow of air. The convergence of horizontal winds causes air to rise, whereas the divergence of horizontal

winds causes downward motion of the air. Mathematically, this is invariant with respect to coordinate transformations and may be written as;

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}$$

In meteorological applications, the divergence usually refers to the 2D horizontal divergence of the wind velocity field;

$$\nabla F = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$$

where u and v are the x and y components of the velocity, respectively. These are then taken as partial derivatives.

3. Absolute Vorticity (η ; s^{-1}) – The absolute vorticity of the air parcel is the sum of the relative vorticity imparted to the air parcel by the flow around it (positive or negative) and the vorticity imparted to it by the rotating surface of the earth. This is simply represented as;

$$\eta = \zeta + f$$

where ζ is the relative vorticity (to be discussed below) and f is the Coriolis parameter, both of which have units of s^{-1} .

4. Absolute Vorticity Advection (η_{ADV} ; s^{-2}) - Vorticity advection is indicative of rising motion/falling pressures at the surface. This in turn leads to the formation of areas of convergence or divergence and the development of circulation patterns. Generally, we can use the classical vorticity to give a representation on how advection works. Thus, is represented as;

$$\frac{D(\zeta + f)}{Dt} = (\zeta + f)(\nabla \cdot \vec{v})$$

where ζ is the relative vorticity, f is the Coriolis parameter, \vec{v} is the horizontal wind vector, and D/Dt is the material derivative, which accounts for both the advection of vorticity by the wind and the change in vorticity due to time varying flow.

5. Relative Vorticity (ζ ; s^{-1}) – The parameter concerning the rotation of air in the horizontal plane, around a vertical axis, relative to a fixed point on the surface of the Earth. On the scale of weather systems in the northern hemisphere, troughs that can include rain are associated with counter-clockwise (CCW) rotation, and ridges that bring light or still winds are associated with clockwise (CW) rotation. This is expressed as the vector wind difference;

$$\zeta = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$$

where u and v are the wind components, specifically the eastward and northward component of the wind, taken as partial derivatives.

6. Wind Speed (kt) – Generally, the measurement of the speed at which air moves in the Earth's atmosphere. This is computed as the magnitude of;

$$\text{Wind Speed} = \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}$$

where u and v correspond to the eastward and northward wind components, respectively.

7. Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP; hPa) – According to List (1951), MSLP is the atmospheric pressure value obtained by the theoretical reduction of barometric pressure to sea level by assuming that atmosphere extends to sea level below the station and that the properties of the atmosphere are related to conditions observed at the station. This were then depicted through synoptic charts, primarily intended in the surface.

The average pressure at mean sea level (MSL) in the International Standard Atmosphere (ISA) is $p_0 = 1013.25$ -hPa, or 1 atmosphere (atm) and by following Wallace and Hobbs (1977), this is implemented through;

$$p_{SL} = p_{station} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta Z}{H}\right)$$

where ΔZ is the elevation in meters as;

$$\Delta Z = Z_2 - Z_1 = \frac{R_d T_v}{g_0} \ln\left(\frac{p_1}{p_2}\right)$$

and H is the scale height in atmosphere;

$$H = \frac{R_d T}{g}$$

with R_d being the dry air constant, T and g are the temperature parameter and acceleration due to gravity, respectively.

8. Vertical Wind Shear (VWS; kt) – Vertical wind shear refers to the variation of wind speed and direction with height in the atmosphere. Specifically, it describes the change in wind speed or direction over a vertical distance in the

atmosphere. One common way to determine the VWS is to subtract the wind vector at one height from the wind vector at another height.

9. Dewpoint Temperature (T_D ; °C) commonly termed dew point, is the temperature to which a parcel of moist air must be cooled at constant atmospheric pressure and constant water vapour content in order for saturation to occur.

10. Atmospheric Thickness (dam; decameter) – A measure of how warm or cold a layer of the atmosphere is, usually a layer in the lowest 5-km of the troposphere. We can calculate the thickness through the use of pressure and temperature profiles via the hypsometric equation with virtual temperature adjustment to account for moisture. This is shown in Wallace and Hobbs (2006) as;

$$Z_2 - Z_1 = -\frac{R_d}{g} \int_{p_2}^{p_1} T_v d \ln p$$

as R_d is the dry air constant and T_v is the virtual temperature.

11. Isobaric Temperature (°C) – A constant pressure (or isobaric) surface is a surface in the atmosphere where the pressure is equal everywhere along that surface. Therefore, an Isobaric Temperature (typically for NWP models), or Isotherm, shows the distribution of equal temperature at the surface or on a chart indicating constant level or constant pressure.

12. Precipitable Water Vapour (PWV; kg m^{-2}) – Also known as Precipitable Water, is the total atmospheric water vapor contained in a vertical column of unit cross-sectional area extending between any two specified levels, commonly

expressed in terms of the height to which that water substance would stand if completely condensed and collected in a vessel of the same unit cross section.

This is applied by using Salby (1996) formulation of;

$$PWV = \frac{1}{\rho g} \int_{p_2}^{p_1} r dp$$

where ρ represents the density of water and r is the mixing ratio at a certain pressure. p_2 and p_1 meanwhile are the layer bounded pressures as a column of unit cross section from top to bottom of atmosphere.

13. Mean Precipitation (mm hr^{-1}) – A measure of the intensity of rainfall by calculating the amount of rain that would fall over a given interval of time if the rainfall intensity were constant over that time period. In NWP models, this is the sum of the rates resulting from large-scale precipitation and convective precipitation.

14. Vertical Velocity Pressure (ω ; Pa s^{-1}) – This is the speed at which the air is rising or sinking. ω was used to understand the large-scale dynamics of the atmosphere, including areas of upward motion/ascent and downward motion/subsidence. Locations where air is rising are the locations most likely to produce precipitation. This is expressed as in Wallace and Hobbs (2006) as;

$$\omega = -\rho g w$$

where ρ is the density from a given pressure and temperature and w is the vertical velocity in terms of height given as $w = Dz/DT$, a Lagrangian derivative of vertical position that is positive in direction with increasing pressure.

15. Brunt-Vaisala Frequency Squared (N^2 ; s^{-2}) – The square of the Brunt-Vaisala frequency is the measurement of atmospheric stability where the frequency at which a vertically displaced fluid parcel oscillates within a stratified environment.

This is expressed according to Wallace and Hobbs (2006);

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{\theta} \frac{d\theta}{dz}$$

where $g = 9.81 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ is gravitational acceleration, θ is the potential temperature, and $d\theta/dz$ is the vertical gradient of the potential temperature.

16. Potential Temperature (θ ; K) – Also known as Theta, is the temperature that an unsaturated parcel of dry air would have if brought adiabatically and reversibly from its initial state to a standard pressure, p_0 , typically 1000-hPa.

This is mathematically known for as;

$$\theta = T \left(\frac{p_0}{p} \right)^k$$

where T is the temperature, k is the poisson constant typically known for the ratio of the gas constant to the specific heat capacity at constant pressure.

17. Potential Vorticity (PVU; $K \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) – A measure of the capacity for air to rotate in the atmosphere. Assuming negligible effects of heating and friction, potential vorticity (PV) is conserved following an air parcel. Large wind storms develop when a column of air in the atmosphere starts to rotate. Thus, this is

used to look for places where large wind storms are likely to originate and develop. The baroclinic solution was described by Bluestein (1992) as;

$$PV_{BC} = -g \left[\frac{\partial u}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial v}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial p} (\zeta + f) \right]$$

where the aforementioned equation requires the use of vorticity ζ and coriolis parameter f . Furthermore, the baroclinic solution also takes into account the potential temperature θ .

18. Equivalent Potential Temperature (θ_e ; K) – Also known as Theta-E, corresponds to the maximum potential temperature an air parcel could achieve via condensation of all the water vapor content, when brought to a standard pressure of 1000-hPa. This is expressed by Bolton (1980) as initially looking for the temperature of the LCL (T_L);

$$T_L = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{T_D - 56} + \frac{\ln(T_K/T_D)}{800}} + 56$$

where T_D is the dewpoint temperature. This is then used to calculate the potential temperature at the LCL (θ_{DL});

$$\theta_{DL} = T_K \left(\frac{1000}{p - e} \right)^k \left(\frac{T_K}{T_L} \right)^{.28r}$$

The non-iterative approach on computing the Equivalent Potential Temperature is therefore defined as;

$$\theta_E = \theta_{DL} \exp \left[\left(\frac{3036}{T_L} - 1.78 \right) * r(1 + .448r) \right]$$

19. Geostrophic Winds (V_g) – These are gradient winds that flow parallel to the straight pressure lines (isobars) or height contours. Under these conditions the Coriolis effect is balanced by the pressure gradient force. This is calculated by the following equation;

$$V_g = \frac{g}{2\Omega \sin \phi} \frac{\Delta z}{d}$$

where g is the acceleration of gravity, Ω is rotational speed of the earth, ϕ is the latitude, d is the distance over which the pressure or $Z_g(h)$ changes takes place, and Δz is the change in $Z_g(h)$.

20. Ageostrophic Winds (V_{ag}) – These are the component of the actual wind that is not geostrophic due to friction and other effects. This is represented as the vector difference between the actual (or observed/real) winds (V) and geostrophic wind (V_g);

$$V_{ag} = V - V_g$$

21. Duct Function (DF; dim) – Also known as Duct Factor, is a dimensionless value used to measure the stable layer or duct strength, and the degree to which the 400- to 700-hPa layer is conditionally unstable and suitable for gravity wave formation and propagation. This is described by Koch and O’Handley (1997) as;

$$DF = \theta(800 \text{ mb}) - \theta(950 \text{ mb}) + \theta_e(800 \text{ mb}) - \theta_e(400 \text{ mb})$$

where θ is potential temperature at 950-hPa and 800-hPa, and θ_e is equivalent potential temperature at 800-hPa and 400-hPa.

Meanwhile, for convective indices, the following are the environmental parameters that we computed using the soundings from Tanay Upper Air Station provided in UWyo;

1. Bulk Wind Shear – Also known as Bulk Wind Difference (BWD), refers to the change in wind speed and direction over a given distance, typically in the vertical direction as they can enhance the vertical motion and organization of storms. In a given sounding, this is typically measured between two levels in the atmosphere, such as between the surface and 6-km AGL, as an example. BWD is computed through the vertical wind profile (or Hodograph) as;

$$\Delta V = V_1 - V_2$$

where V_1 and V_2 are corresponding wind profile and the difference between two levels. The same concept can be applied to isobaric winds for computing the VWS (as discussed above).

2. Lifted Index (LI; Galway, 1956) – LI is a commonly utilized measure of stability which measures the difference between the parcel's temperature at 500-hPa and the environmental temperature at 500-hPa. It incorporates moisture and lapse rate into one number. It is defined as;

$$LI = T_{500} - T_{p500}$$

where T_{500} and T_{p500} are the environmental temperature at 500-hPa and the temperature of a parcel lifted from the surface to 500-hPa.

3. Showalter Index (SI; Showalter, 1953) – SI is based on the properties of 850- and 500-hPa levels. The SI is calculated by lifting a parcel dry adiabatically from 850-hPa to its LCL, then moist adiabatically to 500-hPa, and comparing the parcel versus environmental 500-hPa temperatures similar to the LI. This is represented as the following;

$$SI = T_{500} - T_{p500}$$

where T_{500} and T_{p500} are the environmental temperature at 500-hPa and the temperature of a parcel lifted from 850- to 500-hPa.

4. K Index (George, 1960) – K Index is measure of TSTM potential based on the vertical temperature lapse rate, and the amount and vertical extent of low-level moisture in the atmosphere. This shown below as;

$$KI = (T_{850} - T_{500}) + T_{d850} - DD_{700}$$

where T_{850} and T_{500} are the temperatures at planetary boundary-layer (PBL) and mid-levels, respectively. Meanwhile, T_{d850} is the dewpoint temperature at PBL, and DD_{700} is the dewpoint depression calculated as the difference between the environmental temperature and dewpoint temperature at 700-hPa (Steering Level).

5. Totals Total Index (TT; Miller, 1967) – The Total Totals Index is a stability index consists of two components, the Vertical Totals (VT) and the Cross Totals (CT). The VT represents static stability or the lapse rate between 850- and 500-hPa.

The CT includes the 850-hPa dewpoint. This is represented as the following equation;

$$TT = VT + CT,$$

$$TT = (T_{850} - T_{500}) + (T_{d850} - T_{500})$$

Where T_{850} and T_{500} are the temperatures at PBL and mid-levels, respectively.

Meanwhile, T_{d850} is the dewpoint temperature at PBL.

6. Severe Weather Threat Index (SWEAT; Bidner, 1970) – Abbreviated as SWEAT, is a stability index which incorporates low-level moisture (850-hPa Td), instability (Total Totals Index), lower and mid-level (850- and 500-hPa) wind speeds, and warm air advection (veering between 850- and 500-hPa).

From a given sounding, it is calculated as follows;

$$SWEAT = 12T_{d850} + 20(TT - 49) + 2f_{850} + f_{500} + 125(S + 0.2)$$

where each of the term is described as;

- a) T_{d850} is the Dewpoint temperature at 850-hPa. This term is set to zero if T_{d850} is negative.
- b) TT is Totals Total Index. This term is set to zero if TT is less than 49.
- c) f_{850} and f_{500} is the wind speed at 850-hPa and 500-hPa.
- d) S is the directional shear term expressed as: $\sin(\text{deg}_{850} - \text{deg}_{500})$, where deg_{850} and deg_{500} are the wind directions at 850-hPa and 500-hPa, jointly.

7. Convective Available Potential Energy (CAPE; J kg^{-1} ; Moncrieff & Miller, 1976)
– Abbreviated as CAPE, is a measure of convective buoyancy in the atmosphere that incorporates the instability and moisture parameters. Plotted through Skew-T diagram, this is the positive shaded region between the parcel profile curve and the environmental sounding from;

- Surface-based (or SBCAPE)
- Mixed-layer (or MLCAPE)
- Most-Unstable (or MUCAPE)

In this case, I applied the virtual temperature (T_v) correction enunciated by Doswell and Rasmussen (1994) as it is the 'standard temperature' in the IGL EOS $p = \rho R T_v$ and its gas constant. In order to apply the correction, one may initially calculate the mixing ratio (w) of an air parcel from a given sounding; its relative humidity (RH) and r_s , as in Wallace and Hobbs (1977);

$$w = (rh)(r_s)$$

Then, computing for T_v can be applied straightforwardly as outlined by Wallace and Hobbs (2006);

$$T_v = T \frac{w + \epsilon}{\epsilon(1 + w)}$$

with ϵ being the molecular weight ratio of a dry air. The undiluted CAPE measured from a sounding is simply integrated between the LFC and EL as the difference between the density of the parcel profile and environment results to

a positive buoyant region. Refining the formula of Wallace and Hobbs (1977) with the T_v correction gives;

$$\text{CAPE} = \int_{LFC}^{EL} -R_d (T_{vp} - T_{ve}) d \ln p$$

where T_{vp} is the virtual temperature of an ascending air parcel moist adiabatically from the pressure of LFC to EL (or neutral buoyancy), T_{ve} is the virtual temperature of the environment, R_d is the specific gas constant for dry air, and p is the atmospheric pressure profile as logarithmically interpolated for crossing points of T_{ve} and T_{vp} .

8. Convective Inhibition (CIN; J kg^{-1} ; Colby, 1984) – Also called as CINH, represents the amount of negative buoyant energy available to "inhibit" (acting as a "lid") or suppress upward vertical acceleration of the parcel to ascend towards the LFC. Specifically, it is the region on the sounding where the parcel temperature curve is cooler than that of the environment. With T_v correction, this is integrated between the surface and LFC as a difference between the parcel's temperature to its environmental conditions;

$$\text{CIN} = \int_{SFC}^{LFC} -R_d (T_{vp} - T_{ve}) d \ln p$$

9. Theoretical Maximum Updraft Velocity (W_{\max} ; m s^{-1} ; Lebo & Morrison, 2015) – A meteorological parameter used to describe the maximum thermodynamic velocity at which air is rising within a TSTM or convective cloud. Updrafts are

columns of warm air that rise due to buoyancy and can lead to the development of TSTMs and severe weather.

The theoretical approximation of W_{\max} uses the undiluted CAPE by;

$$W_{\max} = \sqrt{2\text{CAPE}}$$

Also, ECAPE (to be discussed below) can be used in place of the undiluted parcel to include entrainment effects in W_{\max} (Peters et al., 2020);

$$W_{\max} = \sqrt{2\text{ECAPE}}$$

which have similar traits to kinetic energy per unit mass $\text{KE}/m = 0.5(w^2)$, where w is updraft speed. This is supported as the 'base unit' of J kg^{-1} is $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$.

10. Entraining CAPE (ECAPE; J kg^{-1} ; Peters et al., 2023a) – This is a newly-derived severe weather parameter that measures and incorporates entrainment effects to the updraft steadiness and mixing. Thus, estimating diluting effect on the positive buoyancy of air parcels within TSTM updrafts. This is analytically given and adjusted as;

$$\text{ECAPE}_A = \frac{V_{\text{SR}}^2}{2} + \frac{1 + \Psi - \frac{2\Psi}{V_{\text{SR}}^2} \text{NCAPE}}{4\frac{\Psi}{V_{\text{SR}}^2}} + \frac{\sqrt{\left(1 + \Psi + \frac{2\Psi}{V_{\text{SR}}^2} \text{NCAPE}\right)^2 + 8\frac{\Psi}{V_{\text{SR}}^2} (\text{CAPE} - \Psi \text{NCAPE})}}{4\frac{\Psi}{V_{\text{SR}}^2}}$$

where V_{SR}^2 is the storm-relative inflow at the lowest 1-km using internal dynamics (ID; Bunkers et al., 2000) and NCAPE is the potential buoyancy loss that could be induced by the tropospheric dryness and temperature on buoyancy via entrainment. This is calculated through;

$$\text{NCAPE} = - \int_{LFC}^{EL} \frac{g}{c_{pd}T} (\hat{h}_0 - h_0^*) dz$$

h_0^* is the saturated moist static energy. Meanwhile, ψ is a constant parameter defined by;

$$\Psi = \frac{k^2 a^2 \pi^2 L_{mix}}{P_r \sigma EL}$$

where EL is the Equilibrium Level of a sounding. Each constant is provided and set by Peters et al. (2023a) in their Section 4.

11. Storm-Relative Helicity (SRH; $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$; Davies-Jones et al., 1990) – Also known as the Storm-Relative Environmental Helicity (SREH), is the integral over the inflow's vertical range (typically at 0-1 and 0-3 km) of the scalar product of the storm-relative inflow velocity and the horizontal streamwise vorticity. This is defined by Markowski and Richardson (2010) as the following;

$$\text{SRH} = \int_0^d (\bar{v} - c) \cdot \bar{\omega}_h dz$$

12. Bulk-Richardson Number (BRN; Weisman & Klemp, 1982) – This is a nondimensional ratio that is inversely proportional to the vertical wind shear of the lowest 6-km and directly proportional to CAPE, shown as;

$$\text{BRN} = \frac{\text{CAPE}}{0.5 \cdot (\Delta M)^2}$$

The denominator in the equation above is known as the BRN Shear term and ΔM is the shear magnitude given by;

$$\Delta M = \sqrt{\Delta U^2 + \Delta V^2},$$

$$\Delta U = \bar{U} - U_{SL}$$

$$\Delta V = \bar{V} - V_{SL}$$

where ΔU and ΔV are the shear components between the mean wind \bar{U}, \bar{V} in the 0-6 km layer and the surface-layer winds U_{SL}, V_{SL} estimated as an average over the bottom 500 m of the atmosphere.

13. Energy-Helicity Index (EHI; Hart & Korotky, 1991) – EHI is a non-dimensional index used to identify tornado potential by combining CAPE with SRH in the lowest 1- and/or 3-km AGL. Generally, this is computed using;

$$EHI = \frac{(CAPE)(SRH)}{1.6 \times 10^5}$$

14. Supercell Composite Parameter in Fixed Layer (SCP_{fix} ; Thompson et al., 2003) – A multiple component index that is meant to highlight the co-existence of ingredients favoring and supporting supercell TSTM. The intent of the SCP_{fix} was to normalize CAPE and measures of vertical shear to approximate threshold values for supercells, and combine these parameters into a single non-dimensional parameter. This is computed as;

$$SCP_{fix} = \frac{MUCAPE}{1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}} \times \frac{SRH_{0-3km}}{100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}} \times \frac{BRN \text{ Shear}}{40 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}}$$

15. Supercell Composite Parameter in Effective Layer (SCP_{eff} ; Thompson et al., 2007) – This is the updated version of SCP_{fix} as developed by Thompson et al. (2007). It is a composite index that includes effective SRH (ESRH, based on Bunkers ID) and BWD (EBWD), and MUCAPE where each ingredient is

normalized to supercell threshold values. The term effective indicates the effective inflow layer of the TSTM which parcels have CAPE of $\sim 100 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and CIN $> -250 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$. In particular, EBWD takes into account the difference over the lower half of the storm depth. This is computed as;

$$\text{SCP}_{\text{eff}} = \frac{\text{MUCAPE}}{1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}} \times \frac{\text{ESRH}_{0-3\text{km}}}{100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}} \times \frac{\text{EBWD}}{20 \text{ m s}^{-1}}$$

16. Significant Tornado Parameter in Fixed Layer (STP_{fix} ; Thompson et al., 2003) –

A multiple ingredient, composite index that includes 0-6 km BWD, 0-1 km SRH, Surface-based CAPE and LCL. This version of STP mimics the formulation presented by Thompson et al. (2012) by using fixed-layer calculations of vertical shear, and substitutes the surface lifted parcels as an alternative to the mixed-layer parcels in the effective layer version of STP. The new version is slated as;

$$\text{STP}_{\text{fix}} = \frac{\text{SBCAPE}}{1500 \text{ J kg}^{-1}} \times \frac{2000 \text{ m} - \text{SBLCL}}{1000 \text{ m}} \times \frac{\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}}{150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}} \times \frac{\text{BWD}_{0-6\text{km}}}{20 \text{ m s}^{-1}}$$

in which the LCL is set to zero when the height is above 2000 m and capped at 1 when below 1000 m, and the 0-6 km BWD is set to 0 when below 12.5 m s^{-1} while maxed out at 1.5 when it exceeds 30 m s^{-1} .

17. Vorticity Generation Parameter (VGP; m s^{-2} ; Rasmussen & Wilhelmson, 1983)

– Although a depreciated parameter in severe weather analysis already, with VGP, it estimates the rate of tilting and stretching of horizontal vorticity by a TSTM updraft. This is given as;

$$VGP = [S (CAPE)^{1/2}]$$

As S is the mean shear in the lowest 4-km or the environmental hodograph curve length divided by depth;

$$S = \frac{\int_0^d \frac{\delta V}{\delta z}}{\int_0^d \delta z}$$

18. Streamwise Helicity (SWH; $m s^{-2}$) – Different to the well-known SRH parameter, SWH and Helicity itself is a scalar variable at any point in the parcel that combines rotation around some axis with the aligned mean motion. SWH is simply computed using ambient environment-relative winds outside the TSTM that has only VWS of horizontal winds;

$$SWH = \bar{V} \left(\frac{\Delta U}{\Delta z} \right) - \bar{U} \left(\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta z} \right)$$

Where \bar{U}, \bar{V} are the mean environment-relative wind components up to a certain height/layer i.e. at the first 3-km.

19. Streamwise Vorticity Magnitude (ζ_{SWM} ; s^{-1}) – In the hodograph, the streamwise component of vorticity is typically represented as a scalar, with the magnitude of the vorticity vector aligned with the direction of motion. Hence, along the environmental flow. This is determined as;

$$\zeta_{SWM} = U_{SR} \left(-\frac{dV}{dz} \right) + V_{SR} \left(\frac{dU}{dz} \right)$$

Where U_{SR} and V_{SR} are the storm-relative wind components, that can be approximated as the difference between the layer/pressure-specific winds and 0-6 km mean wind.

20. Streamwise Vorticity Fraction ($\zeta_{SW\%}$; %) – Also known as streamwiseness of vorticity, is the ratio of the streamwise component of vorticity to the shear vector, expressed as a fraction or percentage. The measure of streamwiseness is expressed as;

$$\zeta_{SW\%} = \left(\frac{\zeta_{SWM}}{\overline{\Delta V}} \right) \cdot 100\%$$

As ζ_{SWM} is the magnitude of the streamwise vorticity and $\overline{\Delta V}$ represents the mean BWD.

21. Bunkers Storm Motion (Bunkers ID; kt; Bunkers et al., 2000)– Also known as Bunkers Internal Dynamics (ID), is a galilean invariant method; does not depend on the orientation of the ground-relative winds rather than shear-relative winds, used in the Hodograph profile to estimate storm motion of TSTMs. This gives two components of a right-mover (RM) and left-mover (LM) calculated as;

$$V_{RM(LM)} = \overline{M_W} \pm D \left[\frac{\Delta V(\hat{k}) \times \hat{k}(\Delta V)}{|\Delta V|} \right]$$

Where $\overline{M_W}$ is the 0-6 km *non-pressure weighted* mean wind, Deviation D is set to 7.5 m s^{-1} while \hat{k} is the unit vector in the z-axis. This is taken as the cross product of ΔV which is the VWS vector calculated by taking the difference

between 5.5-6 km and 0-500 m mean winds both acting as the head and tail, respectively. The \pm operator indicates orthogonality (+) and reversing (-) of the cross product which correspondingly, indicates the RM and LM components (LM are enclosed with parenthesis in the equation above).

22. Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM; kt; Nixon & Allen, 2021) – A hodograph method that can be used to anticipate the trajectory of LM deviant tornadoes. Depending on the Bunkers ID component being utilized, DTM is represented as;

$$\mathbf{DTM}_{B2K} = \frac{\mathbf{c}_{B2K} + \mathbf{v}_{300}}{2}$$

Where C_{B2K} is the storm motion vector using the galilean invariant method and V_{300} is the mean wind from the surface to 300-m layer.

All of the enunciated synoptic and convective parameters were incorporated to the area of interest that requires to be examined. We summarized all of these parameters in short detail at Table 3.

Table 3*Synoptic and Convective Parameters applied to the Study Interest.*

Parameter	Abbreviation	Units
Synoptic Parameters (27)		
Upper-level 300-hPa Geopotential Height	$Z_g(h)300$	dam
Mid-level 500-hPa $Z_g(h)$	$Z_g(h)500$	dam
Steering-level 700-hPa $Z_g(h)$	$Z_g(h)700$	dam
Boundary-layer 850-hPa $Z_g(h)$	$Z_g(h)850$	dam
Surface to Mid-level Thickness	1000-500 hPa	dam
Upper-level 300-hPa Winds	V_{300}	kt
Mid-level 500-hPa Winds	V_{500}	kt
Boundary-layer 850-hPa Winds	V_{850}	kt
0-6 km Vertical Wind Shear	$VWS_{850-400}$	kt
Surface Winds	V_{SFC}	kt
Surface Dewpoints	T_D	$^{\circ}C$
Mean Sea Level Pressure	MSLP	hPa
Boundary-layer 850-hPa Temperature	T_{850}	$^{\circ}C$
Mean Precipitation Rate	Mean Precip.	$mm\ hr^{-1}$
Precipitable Water Vapour	PWV	$kg\ m^{-2}$
Steering-level 700-hPa Vertical Velocity Pressure	ω	$Pa\ s^{-1}$
Upper-level 300-hPa Relative Vorticity	ζ	s^{-1}
Mid-level 500-hPa Absolute Vorticity	η	s^{-1}
Mid-level 500-hPa Absolute Vorticity Advection	η_{ADV}	s^{-2}
600-hPa Divergence	∇F	s^{-1}
Potential Temperature	θ	K
Potential Vorticity	PV	$K\ m^2\ kg^{-1}\ s^{-1}$
Brunt-Vaisala Frequency Squared	N^2	s^{-1}
Equivalent Potential Temperature	θ_e	K
Boundary-layer 850-hPa Geostrophic Winds	V_g	kt
Boundary-layer 850-hPa Ageostrophic Winds	V_{ag}	kt
Duct Factor/Ducting Function	DF	dim

Parameter	Abbreviation	Units
Parcel and Thermodynamic parameters (13)		
Surface-based Convective Available Potential Energy	SBCAPE	J kg ⁻¹
SBCAPE up to 3 km AGL	SBCAPE _{0-3km}	J kg ⁻¹
Surface-based Convective Inhibition	SBCIN	J kg ⁻¹
Mixed-layer CAPE	MLCAPE	J kg ⁻¹
0-500 m AGL MLCAPE up to 3 km AGL	MLCAPE _{0-3km}	J kg ⁻¹
Mixed-layer CIN	MLCIN	J kg ⁻¹
Most unstable CAPE	MUCAPE	J kg ⁻¹
MUCAPE up to 3 km AGL	MUCAPE _{0-3km}	J kg ⁻¹
Most unstable CIN	MUCIN	J kg ⁻¹
Entraining CAPE	ECAPE	J kg ⁻¹
Maximum Updraft Velocity	W _{max}	m s ⁻¹
Lifted Condensation Level	LCL	m
Equilibrium Level	EL	m
Temperature gradients (4)		
0-1 km lapse rate	LR _{0-1km}	K km ⁻¹
0-3 km lapse rate	LR _{0-3km}	K km ⁻¹
700-500 hPa lapse rate	LR ₇₀₀₋₅₀₀	K km ⁻¹
800-600 hPa lapse rate	LR ₈₀₀₋₆₀₀	K km ⁻¹
Kinematic parameters (11)		
0-1 km AGL Bulk Wind Difference (Low-level Shear)	LLS	kt / m s ⁻¹
0-3 km AGL BWD (Mid-level Shear)	MLS	kt / m s ⁻¹
0-6 km AGL BWD (Deep-layer Shear)	DLS	kt / m s ⁻¹
Bunkers Storm Motion	Bunkers ID	kt
0-1 km AGL Storm-Relative Helicity	SRH _{0-1km}	m ² s ⁻²
0-3 km AGL SRH	SRH _{0-3km}	m ² s ⁻²
0-3 km AGL Streamwise Helicity	SWH	m s ⁻²
0-500 m AGL Streamwise Vorticity Magnitude	ζ _{SWM}	s ⁻¹
0-500 m AGL Streamwise Vorticity Fraction	ζ _{SW%}	%
0-4 km AGL Vorticity Generation Parameter	VGP	m s ⁻²
Deviant Tornado Motion	DTM	kt / m s ⁻¹

Composite and Stability parameters (15)

Lifted Index	LI	°C
Showalter Index	SWI	°C
K Index	KI	°C
Totals Total Index	TT	°C
Severe Weather Threat Index	SWEAT	dim
Bulk-Richardson Number	BRN	dim
0-1 km AGL Energy-Helicity Index	EHI _{0-1km}	dim
0-1 km AGL Mixed-layer EHI	MLEHI _{0-1km}	dim
0-1 km AGL Entrained EHI	ENT _{EHI} _{0-1km}	dim
0-3 km AGL EHI	EHI _{0-3km}	dim
0-3 km AGL MLEHI	MLEHI _{0-3km}	dim
0-3 km AGL ENT _{EHI}	ENT _{EHI} _{0-3km}	dim
Fixed-layer Supercell Composite Parameter	SCP _{fix}	dim
Effective-layer Supercell Composite Parameter	SCP _{eff}	dim
Fixed-layer Significant Tornado Parameter	STP _{fix}	dim

CHAPTER IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

1. Case Description of the Tornado Event

Most case studies initially start with a narrative of an event (or even a person, situation etc.) comprised by detailed background information. In this section, a concise case description is developed following the severe weather. Thus, encompassed and subdivided into three (3) parts; (1.1) The general condition along NCR based documents, radar and satellite image, (1.2) The Ground Observation Measurements in Bluementritt and Tayuman AWS platforms and lastly, (1.3) the first ever tornado survey corresponding to the evidences from various Netizens.

1.1. Weather Condition in Metro Manila

In the afternoon of August 14, 2016 at 05 UTC, DOST-PAGASA issued a HRW No. 19 with Yellow Warning over the northern portion of greater Metropolis. Consequently, light to moderate with occasional heavy rains may experience within the Metro Manila extending towards Southern Tagalog due to effects of SWM causing TSTMs indicative of cloudy and inclement stormy skies within the capital. 3 hours later at 08 UTC, another warning was issued which specified that a TSTM is on its way towards Metro Manila, with sights on Manila City specifically, that can last for the next several of hours (DOST-PAGASA, 2016).

Satellite imagery taken by the AHI aboard the HIMAWARI-8 at 0820 UTC reveal a small TSTM along Metro Manila area. An overshooting top (OTT) was seen with the storm's top anvil layer distinguishing between a low-level stratocumulus runoff

Figure 22

Satellite Imagery on 0820 UTC around Luzon, focusing on NCR, where a severe TSTM is affecting the said area. Overlaid as circle, Lightning Detection along the bounding area from University of Washington's WWLLN Team and its associated sensors. Each CG and IC strokes were detected by stations greater than 5. Mean Sea Level Pressure (MSLP, Isobars; hPa) based of ERA5 Re in 08 UTC. Red box denotes the severe TSTM activity.

from a previous convection. In larger picture, the tornadic storm was marching along with a cluster of cellular storms in the western of Luzon landmass. Increasing lightning activity was detected over the afternoon by the WWLLN sensors as the severe storm intensified along the bay and propagated towards the Metropolis due to SW to W winds. Figure 22 depicted the Himawari-8 satellite image along Luzon.

Before the satellite image was being taken, radar reflectivity scan by the nearest C-band Doppler Radar at Tagaytay operated by the aforementioned weather bureau revealed a TSTM with a small hook feature, reportedly as high as 63 dBz seen

Figure 23

Reflectivity Scan by the nearest Doppler Radar operated by DOST-PAGASA at (a) 0815 UTC and (b) 0830 UTC. Supercellular storm characteristics and features were annotated and included to each of the scan. Colorbar units is dBz.

in Figure 23, at the vicinity of Manila Bay approaching the city. Hook signatures or *hook echoes* depicted via weather radars are the staple of severe TSTM such as supercells or those TSTMs with supercellular characteristics capable of producing tornadoes (Markowski, 2002).

The additional panel of radar cross section of the TSTM suggest that its convective updraft tower was tilted due to the presence of strong shear and possibly divergence aloft, resembling to a chimney effect. Such features may imply that the TSTM was low-topped reaching ~10 km AGL along a protruded overshoot in its anvil seen in satellite imagery. The snapshot of the radar scan was provided and shown in Figure 23a. With a tilted updraft above the base, this allowed for efficient intake of storm inflow, tilting, and stretching of streamwise vorticity (SWV), while contributing to both the updraft column and possibly, tornadogenesis.

The storm intensifies as the radar scan at 0830 UTC by the same radar site showed a supercell storm about to plow over Manila City. Seen in Figure 23b, the reflectivity showed signs of classic structures such as a debris ball with its high dBz markings and potentially, a weak echo hole/region evident as a small orange pixel/spot encircled by the >50 dBz signatures acting as a proxy for the Tornado Vortex Signature (TVS). There is also a Bounded Weak Echo Region (BWER) area characterized by a local minimum in the reflectivity (arrow) and is an area associated with a strong, persistent updraft found in the inflow region (Browning, 1964).

With characteristics pointing into a classic supercell (Lemon & Doswell, 1979), it allowed for the storm to drop a tornado with a well-defined wall cloud that hovered on its path. The severe weather episode lasted for around half an hour starting from around 0830 to 09 UTC, or beyond by few minutes. As we approach beyond a quarter to 09 UTC, the vortex started to weaken substantially and by few minutes past 09 UTC, the tornado 'on-the-ground' (OTG) and funnel cloud had dissipated.

We discussed the morphology and possible dynamics entailed within the tornadic event in the coming subsection by analyzing the photos and videos, culminated by stitching of each scene to create an estimated map of the tornado's path.

1.2. Ground-relative Observations

A simple Mesonet analysis in Metro Manila using in-situ observations from AWS networks and those of DOST-PAGASA was carried out and revealed a moist environment due to the relatively small spread between the ground-relative temperature and dewpoint values, an ingredient for TSTM development depicted in Figure 24a. Wind direction were mostly coming from SW further rectifying the prognosis of the damage assessment report where the severe TSTM developed from the prevailing SWM that tapped along an already placed conditional instability.

Furthermore, there's possibly an accompanying surface low entrenched in Manila City along a convergence boundary or temperature gradient line given some AWS reported northerly winds at the northern part of the metropolis while nearly southwesterly in the southern corridor. Whether this is signature coming from an Outflow Boundary (OFB) or a ducted gravity wave, this is can intensify the TSTM development along the present instability in place.

To further examine the situation, we narrowed down and picked the AWS closest to the tornadic event, Bluementritt and Tayuman stations. Upon examining as seen in Figure 24b, both temperatures and dewpoints have increased in the late morning up to early afternoon due to the diurnal maximum heating. This causes the-

Figure 24

(a) Mesonet Observations from PAGASA's Stations and Manila Observatory's AWS Network within Metro Manila at 08 UTC. Wind barbs, Dewpoints (Green), and Temperature (Red) readings, including their Station IDs, are annotated accordingly. (b) In situ Measurements with a Temporal Resolution of 5 min. from the Automated Weather Station located in Manila; primarily Bluementritt (Solid lines) and Tayuman (Broken lines), between 00 UTC and 12 UTC (8 AM and PM PhST) on 14 August 2016. (Upper) Instantaneous T_V (Red; °C), Temperature (Orange Red; °C) and T_D (Green; °C) readings. (Middle) Rainfall (Dark blue; mm), Humidity in both Percent (Light blue; %) and mass fraction (Light purple; $g\ kg^{-1}$). (Lower) Barometric Pressure (Black; hPa) measured 2 m AGL. The Thin Dashed Lines at each column corresponds to the Tornadoic Initiation at 0830 UTC (4:30 PM PhST).

already buoyant parcels of air to precipitously rise coming from the SW direction, with dewpoints as high as 28 °C making the developing storm base lower, a signature and prime for severe weather storm.

Prior to the passage of the tornadic storm (0830 to 09 UTC), both temperatures and surface moisture from both stations started to rapidly decrease with the onset of precipitation resulting in an increase and saturation of the relative humidity to values

of 92.5 to 95%. Pressure profile had also steadily decreased starting at the high-peak noon.

When the tornadic circulation hovered around the station, the temperature and dewpoints had decreased by ~1 to 2 °C hinting at a modest cold pool where the rainfall of up to 4 to 7 mm was measured. Furthermore, the pressure also decreased slightly due to the approach of the mesolow especially evident in the Bluementritt area. Following Lee et al. (2004) and Yao et al. (2019), we assume that the relatively sharp pressure-drop observed at 0845 UTC was partially caused by the short-term pressure perturbation of the tornadic wind circulation, along a sudden rainfall spike suggests that the tornado is rain-wrapped and the parent TSTM transitioning into outflow dominant.

1.3. Morphology and Survey

Here, we tied down the pictures and videos as seen by the Netizens and various news channels in the Philippines to grab insight to the twisted process of the Manila Tornado. From evidences, a survey was carried out that approximately maps out the track of tornado, including vortex morphology, over the course of more or less 30 mins. of its lifetime. The complete and estimated tornado track was shown in Figure 25 with its corresponding snapshots of ground damages and events as evidences. However, close up images and videos of the tornadic event were only available, hence the full view of the mesocyclone, updraft column, and other TSTM features were left unseen.

Figure 25

Ground Damage Survey of the EF1 Manila Tornado based of Pictures and Videos from various Netizens. Identified snapshots were marked by Vortex Symbol and traced. Corresponding Lats and Lons, Areas, and estimated Time of Impact were included to each Documented Landmark along its Corresponding Distances to one another.

Figure 26

Snapshots of the Multi-vortex Tornado from various Netizens. (a) From Joemarie Bacos highlighting the ingestion, stretching, and tilting process of horizontal vorticity. (b) Full view of Manila Tornado by Karen Daphne along a wide funnel/wall cloud and two giant subvortices OTG. (c) Nearly at the same time, Paulo Domingo's photo of a developing vortex around Intramuros featuring a wall cloud rotating cyclonically. (d) While crossing the Pasig River, Sunshine Yu caught up the primary vortex and orbiting satellite vortices that makes up the Tornadic structure.

Upon development and spin up, the vortex and the parent cell ingested near ground-relative vorticity where it first touched down in the form of a funnel cloud along the Baseco Compound Beach where it hit several homes made of light-weight

materials that can be easily tossed up by some meters. We placed the startup of the severe weather event at 08:31 UTC, less than 4 mins. than the time considered as the initiation on the damage assessment organized by the LGU and PAGASA. It then moved towards Brgy. 649 Zone 68 which several concrete homes and shacks were impacted. At that point, the initial vortex started to pick up considerable debris given the damages being captured by the authorities, hinting that the cellular mode is intensifying fast.

After 2 mins., the storm tracked towards the port and continued to ingest, tilt, and stretch these horizontal vortex (HV) tubes coming from the south caused by surface friction and large near-ground vorticity (Oliveira et al. 2019). This is evident as a column of inflow wrapping around the intensifying tornado OTG, ascending in its circulation as it passed and struck near the Philippine Red Cross in Port Area, Manila seen in Figure 25, At one point for level of detail, another HV was also seen being ingested, stretched out, and possibly tilted by the dominant tornadic circulation indicative of its strengthening stage. A scoop from Joemarie Bacos in Figure 26a depicted the tornado crossed Road 10 and near the Anda Circle all the way towards the vicinity of Palacio del Gobernador, Intramuros for approximately 3 mins.

As it moved along Fort Santiago approaching the Bureau of Immigration Head Office at around 0838 UTC, both Karen Daphne (Figure 26b) and Paulo Domingo (Figure 26c) have a great view of the tornado. Daphne's timelapse featured two subvortices coursing the Intramuros area, while Domingo's shot of the event shows a

Figure 27

Additional Photographs of Damages left by the Manila Tornado to Residential houses and Commercial establishments.

single vortex tube touched down along a funnel cloud and tilted wall cloud aloft cyclonically, rotating. It then crossed the Pasig River a minute after where Sunshine Yu had an aerial-like view of the tornadic event on her condominium unit as seen in Figure 26d. From the video, it took shape as a multi-vortex type of tornado (or multiple-

vortices), where the funnel cloud was accompanied several sub-vortices carouseling within the base. The orbiting sub-vortices allowed the funnel cloud and the tornadic wind field to expand. From our perspective, it appears that there are 2 suction vortices and a primary vortex under the wide center.

Traversing the Pasig River, the tornado was on its way towards the heavy populated vicinity of Quiapo area, where building stores and vendors gather, line up, and crowd within the tight spaces of various streets. At around 0841 UTC as captured by the nearest CCTV, the vortex started to impact the Carlos Palanca St. corner Padre Gomez St. with Security Bank being the landmark. Approximately 30 s after, it crossed directly at the Minor Basilica-Plaza Miranda vicinity then at the Quezon Blvd inflicting minor damages to buildings and street vendors.

Upon crossing Quezon Blvd., it was closing in at Recto Ave. as it heads to Bustillos Area where it impacted more vendors and tricycles as caught by another CCTV in the area near Bank of the Philippine Islands (BPI) timed at around a quarter beyond 0844 UTC. Over the next few minutes, it further coursed near the National University (NU) and in Brgy. 435 Zone 44 at Sampaloc District where residents at a nearby basketball court and barangay hall took a hit at ~0847 UTC.

The tornado then crossed along the Lacson Ave. and tracked along the G. Tuazon St. still at the previously-mentioned district. There, it damaged a nearby 7 Eleven Convenience store and tore up some roof trusses on 0850 UTC. At one point, a netizen saw debris wrangling around the vortex located at Palawan St., Balic Balic, near to G. Tuazon. Therefore, given that the proximity of the Palawan St. were

completely near to the damaged 7/11 store, we timed the arrival of the tornado and separation between the previous impact point and the landmark by an additional 20 s.

The tornado was at the verge of end as it approached New Manila at around 09 UTC. The circulation and its associated tornadic wind field had thinned and narrowed out as captured by Adesa Ferraris. The last landmark that the multivortex, which at the "rope" stage that time, went through was at New Manila, Quezon City where it tracked within the vicinity near the Madison 101 Tower. However, one caveat was that the final dissipation stage was completely out of sight due to the lack of evidence, aside from Ferraris' capture of the roping vortex. Typically, the narrowing form of a tornado is a representation of winding down of the severe weather episode. Thus, we timed and placed the dissipation of the tornado at 0902 UTC, along Gilmore Ave in New Manila, Quezon City.

Overall, the tornado had been OTG lasting for about 30 mins. which tracked 8.86 km. or nearly 9 km. due NE at an average forward ground speed of 4.92 m s^{-1} . It impacted more than 10 Brgys. and 100 houses along the way, with residential being the hardest hit in Baseco Compound-Port Area, Manila. Although the houses' foundations were still intact, exterior damages structurally visible from the photographs. In addition, business establishments are substantially affected as it coursed around Quiapo to Sampaloc, Manila. Two people also sustained minor injuries of finger laceration though no evacuees were reported. Additional pictures as evidences of the damages left by the tornadic episode are included in Figure 27.

2. Synoptic-scale Condition

Figure 28

ERA5 Re Synoptic Chart with Monthly Means for August 2016. Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), V_{SFC} (kt), and Average Precipitation rate per hour. 10m and 100m wind rose diagrams (kt) are based of Metro Manila coordinates. Beaufort scale is included from 0 to 7 scale number.

Typically, the month of August in the Philippines and whole Western Pacific (WPAC) Basin is identified as an active period for Tropical Cyclonegenesis (TCG) and SWM. In this case, the HCW event happened on the month of August 2016 where the SWM is highly active, a sign of a volatile atmosphere. From the ERA5 Re model in Figure 28, monthly mean V_{SFC} and precipitation rate are indicative of equatorial monsoonal flow along the country.

On 00 UTC shown in Figure 29, observed 300-hPa charts provided by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA or RMSC-Tokyo) are indicative of a divergent upper-level high (HPA) centered in Northern Luzon extended towards Southern Tagalog. Meanwhile, an UL low near South China Sea (SCS) was also detected which

Figure 29

Upper-level (UL) 300-hPa Synoptic Chart for the Asia-Pacific Region. Geopotential Height contour lines (Isohypse; black solid lines), Wind barbs and Isotachs (black dashed lines, kt), and Temperature (C) were given. Both High- and Low Pressure Areas are annotated by letters H and L that corresponds using Isohypse.

influences and curves the larger anticyclone in Southern China and Burma where the midlatitude jetstream core rides along associated with a cold front. The curved ridge due to the influence an UL low then served as an appendage to a larger anticyclone situated on the previously-mentioned countries. Furthermore, a trough of sub-Tropical Cyclone (sTC), which developed initially at WPAC, had tracked near the coast of Japan's Northeast Region was also captured by the instruments.

Figure 30

UL 300-hPa Synoptic Chart from ERA5 Re. Isohypse (black dashed lines), Wind Streamlines (kt) with varying width and color intensity, and Relative Vorticity (contour filled; s^{-1}) are given.

At 06 UTC from both ERA5 and NCEP FNL (Figure 30 and 31), a cyclonic UL low is situated at Southern China along a maximum vorticity of >9 to $11 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. Wind streamlines and isohypse on the same hPa level shows N to NE of 5 to 10 kt light winds rotating clockwise on a HPA located in Mainland Luzon. Comprised by negative earth vorticity from -3 to $-4 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$, the high had moved towards the West Philippine Sea (WPS) with its anticyclonic feature. Additionally, a weak positively-tilt trough connected to a sTC was identified. The UL low near SCS also had moved on-shore comprised by ample cyclonic vorticity.

Figure 31

Similar to Figure 30 but NCEP FNL. Isohypse (black dashed lines), Wind Streamlines (kt) with varying width and color intensity, and Relative Vorticity (contour filled; s^{-1}) are given.

Depicted in Figure 32 and as observed from the surface on the same time indicates a Tropical Cyclone named Chanthu with Tropical Storm (TS) intensity feeding of the strong SW winds along the WPAC. Another TS identified as Conson was also observed within the northeast coast of Japan. Meanwhile, a broad LPA was spotted intensifying in the SCS which was associated the UL cyclonic vorticity earlier depicted. This surface low was coupled along the surging SWM to the Philippine Archipelago. More importantly, a subtle inverted trough was observed within the Philippines further amplifying the SWM, especially in the Western section of Luzon landmass due to increase gradient ascent.

Figure 32

Similar to Figure 29 as provided by JMA but in the Surface-level at 06 UTC. Isobars (hPa) are given as Black Contour Lines. Both High- and Low Pressure Areas are annotated by X Marks for its center, with letters H and L, respectively and their corresponding Minimum Pressure.

With an observed HPA at the UL and inverted trough axis in the surface centered in Luzon, potential for instability to occur seems likely on the said area due to the volatile atmosphere in place. Coupled along an already warmed surface as seen in previous section, this sets the stage for a strong SBC to occur where air parcels tend to rise due to the warmed surface causing local instability as a low-pressure center and high pressure aloft with its divergent property. Such process is similar to an efficient convective heat transfer.

To further give in this condition, we supplemented the observed charts further by analyzing the gridded data products from various pressure levels. Arranged in a 3 x 2 matrix, these are shown through Figure 33 and 34, consequently.

In ERA5 Re solution, a strong η signal of $\sim 2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ was depicted along the 3 LPAs located in SCS and China seen with the height field at 500-hPa (Figure 33a). This vorticity was then weakly transported across Northern Philippines through the ~ 21 kt westerly streak zonally crossing the country. In the NCR, the η profile is at $\sim 2.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with advection measured at $\sim 1.5 \times 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-2}$. The η field then reintensified as it approaches another 500-hPa low in the open WPAC.

At 700-hPa (Figure 33b), the height contours became more concentrated along the axis of the low pressure at SCS. ω in pressure coordinates is indicative of strong uplift (negative value, red broken lines), including along the western section of Luzon, especially in the Iloilo Region, while subsidence on the latter half of Luzon landmass. At NCR, ω is determined to be at -0.19 Pa s^{-1} supporting the upward motion of air. This field of ascent movement of air parcels further extends up to Southern Luzon which can indicate that the synoptic low has extension belt along the western coast. With upward motion of air in the atmosphere, this led to DCI to occur along the aforementioned area. As a result, average rainfall can reach $\sim 3 \text{ hr}^{-1}$ in Metro Manila over the next couple of hours. Additionally, the quantitative mean precipitation was seen along the WPAC basin riding the weak signal of 500-hPa low center.

At PBL (Figure 33c), the isophyse contour lines continued to encircle the LPA in SCS. More importantly to the interest, an 850-hPa inverted trough was depicted pa-

Figure 33

ERA5 Re valid at 06:00 UTC 14 Aug 2016. (a) 'Mid-level' 500-hPa Isohypsες (blue; dam), Wind Streamlines (kt) with varying width and color intensity, Absolute Vorticity (dashed contour lines; s^{-1}), and Vorticity Advection (contour filled; s^{-2}). (b) 'Steering level' 700-hPa Isohypsες, Vertical Velocity Pressure (dashed contour lines; $Pa s^{-1}$), and Average Precipitation rate per hour with magnitudes greater than $1 mm hr^{-1}$ shaded. (c) 'Boundary-layer' 850-hPa Isohypsες, Isotherms (red; $^{\circ}C$), and Winds (kt). (d) Isobars (black solid lines, hPa), Thickness line from Near-surface to Mid-level (dashed contour lines; red and blue; dam), and PWV in the Atmosphere ($kg m^{-2}$). (e) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), 0–6 km VWS (kt), and Divergence contours (contour filled; s^{-1}). (f) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), V_{SFC} (kt), and Moisture T_D (contour filled; $^{\circ}C$). On the last 3 charts, Red Line denotes the Axis of the Surface Trough. High- and Low Pressure Areas are labelled.

rallel to the western coast of Luzon. Another oddly feature was the PBL ~ 19 °C isotherm contour demarking and stretching from the LPA towards the western section of Luzon. Along NCR, the PBL temps are at 18.8 °C. With ~ 40 kt SW V_{850} cross equatorial flow acting as low-level jet (LLJ) and a marginally warm PBL temp of ~ 22 °C set in WPS, the wind profile can quickly transport warm moist condition to the parallel cold sector indicative of a possible warm-air advection (WAA) due to the perpendicularity of height contours and isotherms. Additionally, it could be bifurcated due to the enhanced pressure gradient above the friction layer. In turn, it can allow increase in upward ascent prime for DCI.

Near-surface AGL (Figure 33d), the pressure perturbation became more distinct along the surface trough in Luzon landmass (red line). The inverted streak also has a 2-cell pattern that bears resemblance to the bulge at the 1000-500 hPa gradient. It can be identified that a thickness advection may occur as an excitation of the possible WAA. And WAA in the lower troposphere contributes to a lifting of air, synoptically. Therefore, DCI and precipitation can be expected in this section, especially as it responds to region of upward motion in the surface trough. A tropical LPA is also depicted along SCS further enhancing the SWM. Furthermore, since the lower atmosphere is highly saturated with PWV of 61.5 kg m^{-2} and T_D at ~ 25 °C at the presence of enhanced SWM (Figure 31f), the veering wind profile aided the moisture transport to the western Luzon and allowing more latent heat to be released once DCI kicks in along the trough.

Additionally, along the SWM and westerly jet (Figure 33e), a decent 25 kt 0-6 km vertical shear ride along and crosses the country which can aid TSTM intensification and proliferation. Distinctively, a strong area of convergence line was seen along the Babuyan straight all the way towards province of Negros Occidental, with Metro Manila area reporting a ∇F of $-1.27 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. This suggest that the area of convergence brought by the surface trough interacts SCS low system. That being said, the surface trough mechanism could have 'flipped' over as the *entrance* located at the western coast and *exit* gate along the Luzon landmass instead. Therefore, area of potential convective activity can be located instead in the western flank of the country.

On the other hand, NCEP FNL have solutions that have points of agreements and differences to the earlier ERA5 Re. Complementing the previous model, a strong η signal reaching $\sim 2.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ was shown but this time centered along a mid-level Low in SCS with the isohypse field at 500-hPa (Figure 34a). The vorticity was then weakly transported across Northern Philippines by the background zonal ~ 21 kt westerly streak crossing the country. In NCR, the η reaches $\sim 3.35 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ with advection of $\sim 8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-2}$. Vorticity field then subtly reintensifies as it approaches another 500-hPa Low in the subtropical region, likely associated with TS Chanthu.

On the steering-level (Figure 34b), the isohypse contours became more concentrated along the axis of the low pressure at SCS. More importantly, height contour lines along the western flank of Luzon shows a subtle, low-amplitude inverted pressure perturbation in a pronounced area of negative ω hinting enhanced upward

Figure 34

NCEP FNL valid at 06:00 UTC 14 Aug 2016. (a) 'Mid-level' 500-hPa Isohypsες (blue; dam), Wind Streamlines (kt) with varying width and color intensity, Absolute Vorticity (dashed contour lines; s^{-1}), and Vorticity Advection (contour filled; s^{-2}). (b) 'Steering level' 700-hPa Isohypsες, Vertical Velocity Pressure (dashed contour lines; $Pa s^{-1}$), and Average Precipitation rate per hour with magnitudes greater than $1 mm hr^{-1}$ shaded. (c) 'Boundary-layer' 850-hPa Isohypsες, Isotherms (red; $^{\circ}C$), and Winds (kt). (d) Isobars (black solid lines, hPa), Thickness line from Near-surface to Mid-level (dashed contour lines; red and blue; dam), and PWV in the Atmosphere ($kg m^{-2}$). (e) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), 0–6 km VWS (kt), and Divergence contours (contour filled; s^{-1}). (f) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), V_{SFC} (kt), and Moisture T_D (contour filled; $^{\circ}C$). On the last 3 charts, Red Line denotes the Axis of the Surface Trough. High- and Low Pressure Areas are labelled.

movement of air parcels that extends down to Southern Luzon, while subsidence on the latter half of Luzon landmass. In NCR, the ω was recorded at -0.11 Pa s^{-1} supporting the area of upward motion in the aforementioned region. The idea is somewhat similar to a 700-hPa shortwave trough in midlatitudes which can amplify inclement weather especially in the right exit gate (ahead of it). With upward motion of air in the atmosphere, this led to amplified DCI and activity along the aforementioned area. As a result of the convection, average rainfall can reach $\sim 1.5 \text{ mm hr}^{-1}$ in Metro Manila over the next couple of hours. The areas and activity of mean precipitation around the 700-hPa disturbance remained loose and patchy with similar characteristics towards the WPAC due to TS Chanthu looming.

Furthermore at 850-hPa (Figure 34c), the height contours continued to outline the LPA in SCS though circulation was quite elongated. An 850-hPa inverted trough was also rendered parallel to the western coast of Luzon and with more extent than the ERA5. The PBL inverted wave coincides along the amplified steering-level pressure bulge where it modulates upward parcel acceleration and TSTM development. The PBL $19 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ temp sector simulated in ERA5 Re was also captured as in this solution stretching from the Ilocos Norte region down to the tip of Sulu Sea. In NCR specifically, the PBL temp is nearly the same as in ERA5 Re solution at $18.9 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The orientation of this feature is different than the reanalysis counterpart, more so as a thermal ridge coincident with the 850-hPa inverted trough. This in turn could promote steep low-level LRs and increase the potential for rapid parcel ascent along the initiating boundary (e.g., Davies 2006).

Along the WPS, PBL temps are marginally warm that can reach up to ~ 21 °C. This was transported by the low-level monsoonal flow with 35 kt V_{850} functioning as LLJ to the 19 °C contour along the western section of Luzon. The air is responding to the pressure aloft that is slightly perpendicular to PBL isotherms inducing a possible WAA. As indicated before, since SWM acts like an SBC especially in the coast, such wind profile can be also bifurcated due to the enhanced pressure gradient and upward ascent prime for volatile atmosphere. This leads to the development and back building of instability in the lower levels (e.g. 700- and 850-hPa) leading to the enhancement of storm activity, especially along the western section of Luzon where the area of interest; Manila, is located.

The pressure perturbation near-surface AGL was at full display, distinct as highly curved, inverted surface trough in Luzon landmass (red line) through the isobars and completely shaping-overlapping the conventional Thickness lines seen along the aforementioned area (Figure 33d). Similar from the previous solution and as diagnosed from the PBL chart, possibly a low-level WAA can be triggered by the pronounced vertical gradient that further contributed to DCI and succeeding HCW. This is conceivable and supported by the last chart at Figure 34f wherein the environment acts as a moisture-rich source with PWV at 63.3 kg m^{-2} and T_D at ~ 25 °C. This can be transported by the enhanced SW to westerly winds aloft towards the western coast of Luzon landmass. Thus, promoting more latent heat to be released once convection initiates. Likewise, the tropical LPA was also shown with the probable center located inland at Zhanjiang City, Guangdong Province in China.

Figure 35

Atmospheric Stability represented as the Mean Brunt-Vaisala Frequency Squared (N^2 ; s^{-2}) across available Sounding Launch Sites in the country. 00 UTC and 12 UTC Soundings is represented by Red and Blue Bar, respectively.

Within the SWM, a strong ~40 kt 0-6 km VWS ride along and crosses the country which can aid long-lived TSTM intensification and proliferation (Figure 34e). Distinctively, another curve of convergence was seen along the Babuyan straight all the way towards province of Mindoro. In the area of interest where the severe weather occurred, a ∇F of $-1.25 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ is recorded inducing upward motion along the ω being simulated from previous runs. This suggest that the surface trough is connected to the low's circulation in the SCS acting as an extension of the disturbance. Furthermore,

the trough sectors probably have also flipped over as the *entrance* located at the western coast and *exit* gate along the Luzon landmass, that can exhibit DCI, so as a HCW such as TSTM activity, due to the moist profile of SWM and westerly winds aloft.

Overall, the atmospheric stability measured in N^2 within NCR using available RAOBs at 00 and 12 UTC recorded $> -0.0002 \text{ s}^{-1}$ across the archipelago. This is shown in Figure 35 as the Square of Brunt-Vaisala recordings across the available RAOBs on 14th of August 2016. When N^2 becomes negative, the stratified layer of the lower atmosphere is convectively unstable; in this case, up to $\sim 4 \text{ km AGL}$. In turn, it allows DCI e.g. TSTMs on the concerned location due to the strong damping and modulation of the displaced parcel along the vertical temperature gradient.

3. Mesoscale Storm Environment

In this section, we dive deeper to the mesoscale environment of the tornadic event with the use of model and conventional RAOBs. We divided this section into four (4) parts; (3.1) we analyzed the RAOB data as launched at Tanay Station on 00 and 12 UTC, (3.2) provided a mesoscale sector of convective and kinematic parameters from the utilized models i.e. ERA5 Re and NCEP, (3.3) a grid point sounding with from the aforementioned solutions and (3.4) lastly, a benchmark of the mesoscale environment based on the baseline climatology from U.S. Great Plains.

3.1. Rawinsonde Observations

At 00 UTC, a weather balloon was fired up at the Tanay Synoptic station. From the RAOB seen in the Figure 36a, the pre-convective environment is unstable and saturated up to 100 hPa with the equilibrium pressure level (EL) reaching nearly the

tropopause height. The setup is applicable for convective forcing as warm air parcel profile rise towards to the Level of Free Convection (LFC) bringing marginally to moderately large LI ranging from -2 to -4, while -3 to -5 in the mixed-phase layer. At the same time while passing through the Lifting Condensation Level (LCL), below the LFC, the parcel raised is considerably warmer than the 500-hPa environmental temperature by -1.1 to -3 °C (SWI) indicative of positive buoyancy well below the mid-levels for DCI.

With LFC half-way from the surface in mean-layer, this results into a thin-long CAPE with a theoretical undiluted buoyancy of ~ 1600 to ~ 2100 J kg⁻¹ accompanied by little to no inhibiting layer, based on both SB-parcel and MU-parcel profile. This is supported by the low-level lapse rates (LRs) in the first 1 km and 3 km where -4.17 K km⁻¹ and -5 K km⁻¹ were recorded, respectively. In the mid-levels, LR₇₀₀₋₅₀₀ and LR₈₀₀₋₆₀₀ of -4.32 K km⁻¹ and -4.5 K km⁻¹, correspondingly were tallied. Both levels are citing a conditionally unstable atmosphere starting to form and can be prime in the afternoon. As positive buoyancy is in place, it is possible for penetrative overshooting beyond the terminal height to occur as the thermodynamic velocity of ~ 57 to ~ 65 m s⁻¹ is recorded. Meanwhile, MLCAPE values are at modest ~ 1200 to ~ 1600 J kg⁻¹ and updraft velocity estimates of ~ 49 to ~ 57 m s⁻¹.

In fact, the pre-severe weather environment is efficient in generating TSTM and its associated updrafts. This is associated with an ECAPE of ~ 1500 J kg⁻¹ allowing any TSTM to proliferate and realize $\sim 70\%$ of its undiluted maximum buoyancy. This also contributes to wide updrafts to be resistant to entrainment due to dry air or lack

Figure 36

Skew-T Log P Diagram from the Rawinsonde of Tanay Synoptic Observatory at: (a) 00 UTC and (b) 12 UTC, both 14 Aug 2016. The Ambient Temperature and Dewpoint Profiles are represented by the Solid Green and Red lines, respectively. The Broken Red lines correspond to the T_v while the Solid Yellow-Orange line and Highlights is the Undiluted Parcel Profile lifted to the Equilibrium Threshold. Included as well is the Magenta line depicts the Diluted Parcel Profile subject to entrainment.

of ambient wind shear. By substituting the undiluted buoyancy with ECAPE to the W_{\max} equation instead yields an updraft kinetic velocity of $\sim 55 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ hinting a minor entrainment-driven dilution to the updraft plume.

Important to tornadogenesis is the low-level positive buoyancy (SB/MU/MLCAPE_{0-3km}) which allows vertical vorticity to be stretched and ingested. Of the initial conditions, a strong CAPE_{0-3km} of 232 J kg^{-1} is recorded, while 197 J kg^{-1} with the ML-parcel initially lifted 500 m AGL is also in place. This shows that the LFC is considerably close to the ground for parcels to rise wet-adiabatically and have better overlap between near-ground SWV and updraft formation.

A K-Index of $39.2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was recorded that is extremely sufficient for potential TSTM sometime over the day accompanied by heavy rains. However, TT stability index somewhat poorly discriminates the storm initiation. Though by evaluating each of the encompassed term, the Cross Totals (CT) of $21 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is indicative for convection process to kick in supplemented by the observed SI ranges. Such pitfall is entailed on using TT as it varies with season and location. Additionally, the composite index may have a misleadingly low value as the moisture content is located below 850 hPa. In this case, moisture resides within the first 2 km AGL with RH% at $\sim 95\%$ then followed by hydrolapse.

Although by incorporating the TT just cancels out as the recorded is $< 49 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the SWEAT Index plays between 310 to 370 units with some veering winds caused by the SWM in the surface and westerly winds in the mid-levels in accordance with the NWP synoptic charts presented. This illustrates that there's a vigorous low-level

Figure 37

Hodograph and the Observed Storm Motion associated with the Tanay RAOBs from; (a) 00 UTC and (b) 12 UTC. Bunkers ID Components are included.

moisture, deep layer instability, along ambient speed and directional shear as DLS of 26.6 kts is reported. Hence, is sufficient to produce potential severe TSTMs and some tornadoes despite the SWEAT value below 400 units.

Meanwhile, the combined shear and CAPE parameter; BRN, was recorded at around 80 to 90 units. This suggests that the storm mode can support multicellular TSTM due to the increased buoyancy brought by the high CAPE. But not supercells that requires persistent vertical shear to generate rotating updraft. Despite such, multicells can still produce severe weather by overcoming the limited shear.

Kinematic mechanism using the first 6 km AGL of the wind profile depicted a veering with height winds (or veering winds). This is shown in Figure 37a as part of the hodograph with a well-defined sickle-shape. Included as well are the right mover (RM), mean-wind (MW), and left-mover (LM) storm components computed via Bunkers ID. Any convective storms that will develop may likely parallel to the MW

component of ~27 kts or propagate via the RM motion's vicinity of ~25.5 kts caused by the synoptic wind profile that time; southwesterly to westerly direction.

Shear vector calculations being carried out on the hodograph reveal ample shear magnitude all the way to the deep 0-6 km layer. Initially, the LLS at the 1 km AGL is reported to be at 31 kts while having a DLS of 26.6 kts in the mid-levels. With Bunkers RM, SRH in the 1 km and 3 km AGL are diagnosed revealing substantial kinematic support for HCW and consequently, for tornado to initiate. SRH_{0-1km} and SRH_{0-3km} in the morning recorded at $187 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $206 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively induced by the veering kinematic profile.

Despite the 17 to 20 kts of storm inflow (storm-relative winds; SRW) across 3 km AGL, the large values of SRH up to the 3 km AGL owe its existence to the accompanied ambient and rich streamwise vorticity in the background as caused by the extreme 31 kts of LLS. The streamwise component of vorticity (ζ_{SWM}) close to ground reported $\sim 0.03 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 0.017 s^{-1} ascending to the 1 km AGL that can supply the TSTM and make an updraft rotate upon tilting and stretching. Kinematics playing along the horizontal vorticity is highly streamwise with $\zeta_{SW\%}$ are $>70\%$ all the way to the 3 km AGL; specifically, the streamwiseness of the $\sim 0.03 \text{ s}^{-1}$ vorticity magnitude was at 85% in the first 500 m AGL and was recorded.

Additional composite indices such as STP_{fix} and SCP_{fix} are 1 unit and 6 units, respectively. This is supported by the EHI parameters in the 1 km AGL and 3 km AGL of 2.5 and 2.8 units consequently, with $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ also >2 units (~ 2.1 units). The high CAPE and SRH environment as shown across the board contributed to such resultant

Table 4

Inter-comparison of Skew-T/Log P Stability Measurements of the Pre-Convective Environment at 00 UTC for each Implementing Tool.

Implementation & Indices	MetPy	COMET MetEd	RAOB (PAGASA)	UWyo	pyMeteo	thundeR [†]	Range
SBCAPE	2000	1905	1756	—	1840	2140	1750 to 2150
SBCAPE _{0-3km}	—	—	239	—	—	232	230 to 240
MUCAPE	2000	1905	1756	—	1840	2140	1750 to 2150
MUCAPE _{0-3km}	—	—	239	—	—	232	230 to 240
MLCAPE	1302	1208	1092	1372	1487	1636	1100 to 1650
ECAPE	—	—	—	—	—	1500	1500
CIN	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
MLCIN	-18.65	0.00	0.00	—	0.00	0.00	0.00 to -18.65
TT	42.50	43.00	42.50	42.50	—	42.50	42.50
KI	39.20	39.00	39.20	39.20	—	39.20	39.20
SWI	-1.31	—	-1.10	-1.12	—	-2.88	-1.10 to -3.00
LI	-2.47	-2.50	-2.00	—	-2.80	-3.85	-2.00 to -4.00
Mixed LI	—	-1.60	-1.00	-1.65	—	-3.40	-1.00 to -3.50
SWEAT	371.15	314.00	371.20	314.20	—	371.15	310 to 370
BRN	—	91	75	82	90	81	75 to 90
LLS	30	—	31	—	—	31	31
MLS	25	—	25	—	—	25	25
DLS	26	—	26	—	—	27	26
SRH _{0-1km}	169.38	—	150.50	—	—	186.91	150 to 190
SRH _{0-3km}	193.92	—	180.90	—	—	206.26	180 to 210
ESRH	—	—	162.00	—	—	191.73	160 to 190
EHI _{0-1km}	2.11	—	1.60	—	—	2.50	1.60 to 2.50
EHI _{0-3km}	2.42	—	2.00	—	—	2.76	2.00 to 3.00
SCP	5.07	—	—	—	—	6.02	5.00 to 6.00
STP	1.12	—	—	—	—	1.21	1.10 to 1.20

Note: [†] denotes that it is the primary tool being utilized across the study.

composite values. With EHI greater than 1 to 1.5 units as baseline for tornadoes (Brooks et al., 1994a; Brooks et al., 1994b; Rasmussen & Blanchard, 1998), TSTMs can likely attain supercell nature with potential threat for meso/misocyclone-induced tornadoes due to the presence of ample buoyancy, especially in the low-levels, and supportive kinematics.

On the other hand, a different environment is being captured by the RAOB conducted in Tanay Station at 12 UTC shown in Figure 36b. Similarly, a relatively moist-profile is being depicted along a steep LR in the 1 km and decent 3 km AGL of -6.2 K km^{-1} and -4.96 K km^{-1} , respectively. This is in turn produced a large undiluted buoyancy of 2550 J kg^{-1} , with MLCAPE reaching 1767 J kg^{-1} . The setup is applicable for convective forcing as warm air profile rise towards to the LFC bringing large LI ranging from -4.5 to -6, while -3 to -5 using the ML-parcel. While ingested by the storm base, the composite SWI parameter have ranges between -1 to -2 °C warmer than the 500-hPa temperature. This can mean that the positive buoyancy and instability is well below the mid-levels for TSTM development.

The post-tornadic profile remains saturated with the terminus height past above 100-hPa indicative convective overshooting. This is due to the maximum thermodynamic velocity between ~ 59 to $\sim 71 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ being recorded. Meanwhile, MLCAPE values are well spread out by at least 1000 J kg^{-1} with 500 to 1750 J kg^{-1} across all implementation being used. This yields an updraft velocity estimates within the range of ~ 32 to $\sim 59 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

Additionally, the post-environment remains efficient in generating potential TSTMs and updrafts with an ECAPE of 1888 J kg^{-1} allowing any TSTM to proliferate and realize $\sim 71\%$ of its undiluted maximum buoyancy. This further adds up to wide updrafts to be resistant to environmental entrainment due to dry air or lack of ambient vertical shear. By substituting the undiluted buoyancy with ECAPE to the W_{\max}

Table 5

Inter-comparison of Skew-T/Log P Stability Measurements of the Post-Convective Environment at 12 UTC for each Implementing Tool.

Implementation & Indices	MetPy	COMET MetEd	RAOB (PAGASA)	UWyo	pyMeteo	thundeR [†]	Range
SBCAPE	2416	2320	2164	—	1745	2550	1750 to 2550
SBCAPE _{0-3km}	232	—	251	—	—	250	230 to 250
MUCAPE	2416	2320	2164	—	1745	2550	1750 to 2550
MUCAPE _{0-3km}	232	—	251	—	—	250	230 to 250
MLCAPE	588	477	473	1444	1523	1767	470 to 1750
ECAPE	1526	—	—	—	—	1821	1500 to 1800
CIN	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-10.00	0.00	0.00 to -10.00
MLCIN	-31.00	0.00	0.00	—	-10.00	0.00	0.00 to -31.65
TT	42.70	43.00	42.70	42.70	—	42.70	42.70
KI	36.10	36.00	36.10	36.10	—	36.10	36.10
SWI	-0.94	—	-0.80	-0.78	—	-2.42	-1.00 to -2.50
LI	-4.61	-4.60	-4.00	—	-4.40	-6.05	-4.50 to -6.00
Mixed LI	—	-2.80	-2.00	-3.35	—	-5.09	-2.00 to -5.00
SWEAT	304.80	305.00	304.80	304.80	—	304.80	304 to 305
BRN	—	>100	>100	—	>100	>100	>100
LLS	27	—	27	—	—	27	27
MLS	25	—	25	—	—	25	25
DLS	15	—	15	—	—	15	15
SRH _{0-1km}	197.84	—	181.50	—	—	180.66	180 to 200
SRH _{0-3km}	233.93	—	223.60	—	—	231.03	220 to 230
ESRH	—	—	133.00	—	—	139.31	130 to 140
EHI _{0-1km}	2.88	—	2.80	—	—	2.87	2.00 to 3.00
EHI _{0-3km}	3.40	—	3.20	—	—	3.68	3.00 to 4.00
SCP	7.04	—	—	—	—	0.00	7.00*
STP	1.56	—	—	—	—	0.00	1.50*

Note: [†] denotes that it is the primary tool being utilized across the study. *Used MetPy instead.

equation instead yields an updraft kinetic velocity of 61.45 m s^{-1} , 11% better than the morning sounding, still hinting a small dilution to the updraft column.

Important to tornadogenesis is the low-level positive buoyancy (SB/MU/MLCAPE_{0-3km}) which allows vertical vorticity to be stretched and ingested. By 12 UTC, low-level buoyancy remains highly sufficient reaching a CAPE_{0-3km} of 251 J

kg^{-1} , while 178 J kg^{-1} with the ML-parcel initially lifted 500 m AGL was recorded. This can indicate that the LCL and LFC remains considerably close to the ground for parcels of air to rise along the MALR and have better overlap between near-ground SWV and updraft formation.

KI have slightly wined down to $36.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ though still sufficient for potential TSTM accompanied by heavy rains. However, TT index remains indistinguishable to discriminate the storm profile. Though by evaluating each of the encompassed term i.e. the Cross Totals (CT) of $\sim 21 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ remains an indication for convection supplemented by the observed SWI ranges. The composite index may have a misleadingly low value as the moisture content is located below 850-hPa. In this case, moisture resides within the first 2 km AGL with RH% at 94% and 83% between the 2 km AGL and mid-levels.

SWEAT Index also have dropped down to tight ranges between 304 to 305 units still with veering profile caused by the SWM in the surface and westerly winds aloft inline with the discussed synoptic charts. This indicates that there was low-level moisture and instability in place. However, the vertical shear were far and have regressed to 15 kts of DLS is reported. Still, it can produce potential severe TSTMs and some tornadoes despite the SWEAT value below 400.

The composite BRN parameter on the other hand was recorded above 100 units across all tools we utilized. The parameter still suggests that the storm mode can support multicellular TSTM cluster due to the increased buoyancy brought by the high CAPE, though may break apart into single cells. But not supercells that requires

persistent sheared environment to generate rotating updraft. Despite such, multicells can still produce severe weather as it can overcome the limited shear.

Additional shear vector calculations being carried out on the hodograph reveal ample shear magnitude all the way to the 0-3 km layer. Initially, the LLS at the 1 km AGL is reported to be at 27 kts while having an MLS of 25 kts. However, the DLS takes a large toll here at just 15 kts which is important for persistent meso/misocyclonic rotation along the 6 km AGL.

In relation to vertical shear, as depicted in Figure 37b, the first 6 km AGL of the wind profile depicted veering winds as a semi-curved hodograph. Potential convective storms may likely move parallel to the MW component of ~27.4 kts or propagate more via the LM motion of ~26.6 kts caused by the presented wind profile. Majority, the large helicities lean more towards the LM storm. This in turn reveals a large SRH in the 1 km and 3 km AGL providing substantial kinematic support for nocturnal HCW and consequently, for tornado to initiate, perhaps even deviant too due to the LM injection. SRH_{0-1km} and SRH_{0-3km} in the evening recorded at $181 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $231 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively.

Along the LM motion component, 17 to 23 kts of SRW across 3 km AGL is recorded which contributed to the large SRH_{0-1km} and SRH_{0-3km} . Furthermore, this were exacerbated by the rich background vorticity in the background were ζ_{SWM} close to ground reported $\sim 0.027 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 0.015 s^{-1} ascending to the 1 km AGL which can supply the TSTM and make rotating updraft, despite the shallow DLS. The LM-based kinematics playing along the horizontal vorticity is highly, if not purely, streamwise with

$\zeta_{SW\%}$ of $\geq 70\%$ all the way to the 3 km AGL, specifically, the streamwiseness in the first 500 m AGL was at 88%.

The EHI parameter in the 1 km and 3 km AGL recorded 2.8 and 3.7 units consequently, with $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ also at ~ 2 units. The high CAPE and SRH based of LM-component contributed to such resultant composite values. As different EHI values are above the baseline (Brooks et al., 1994a; Brooks et al., 1994b; Rasmussen & Blanchard, 1998), potential TSTMs with supercell nature and threat for meso/misocyclone-induced nocturnal tornadoes remains plausible. Meanwhile, other composite indices such as STP_{fix} and SCP_{fix} were not able to completely discriminate and ascertain (valueless) the mesoscale environment.

Across the two observations as analyzed and discussed thoroughly, a summary of basic forecasting thermodynamic and composite parameters based of various implementations used in this study is created. Tables 4 and 5 is organized based of the soundings initiated on 00 and 12 UTC, accordingly.

3.2. Mesoscale Sectors and Panels

In this section, we turned our attention and set the bounds within the Mainland Luzon to capture the mesoscale events that happened before the HCW took place. We developed basic techniques, visualized, and analyzed both the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL grids in the fixed-mesoscale 'bounding box' being set. Each panel are composed of convective and kinematic parameters in a 2x2 matrix format, with the exception of NCEP FNL having LI parameter than the ERA5 Re.

Figure 38

ERA5 Re Mesoscale Panels. (a) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface-based CAPE (contour filled; $J kg^{-1}$) with outlines of CIN (blue dashed lines; $J kg^{-1}$). (b) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), V_{SFC} (kt), and BRN Shear (contour filled; $m^2 s^{-2}$). (c) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface Gust (kt), and K Index (contour filled; K). (d) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface Gust (kt), and Totals Total Index (contour filled; K). Surface Trough's Axis is denoted with Red Dashed Lines.

Firstly, in the ERA5 Re solution at 08 UTC, the convective environment were poorly depicted as CAPE measurements in the NCR are in the lower $500 J kg^{-1}$ along a relatively large CIN of $80 J kg^{-1}$ shown in Figure 38a. High CAPE values were displaced at Northern Luzon and along the open waters instead, though with large cap

Figure 39

Additional TSTM indices from ERA5 Re composed of; (a) Right-moving, Mean Wind, and Left-moving Storm motion vectors based of Bunkers ID (RM, MW, LM, quivers; kt) and Storm-Relative Helicity (SRH_{0-3km} & SRH_{0-1km} , black dashed lines and contour filled; $m^2 s^{-2}$) at 0-1 and 0-3 km layer. (b) 0-3 km Streamwise Helicity (SWH; contour filled; $m s^{-2}$) and 0-500 m Streamwise Vorticity (ζ_{SWM} , black dashed lines; s^{-1}). (c) V_{SFC} (kt) and SWEAT Index (contour filled). (d) W_{max} (contour filled; $m s^{-1}$), 0-3 km Energy Helicity Index (EHI_{0-3km} , black solid lines), and Fixed-layer Supercell Composite Parameter (SCP_{fix} , white dashed lines). Surface Trough's Axis is denoted with Red Dashed Lines.

in place still, potentially requiring strong lifting mechanism for parcels to reach the free convection layer.

Kinematic wise through Figure 38b, the environment along the area is highly favorable along the surface trough with BRN Shear reaching $\sim 50 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ at Central Luzon. At its periphery, the BRN Shear value in NCR by that time is at $13 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, though the dimensionless BRN itself recorded at 41 units indicative of TSTM development with supercell nature due to the modest wind shear relative to the low available buoyancy. It may have been hinting a similar environment to a Low CAPE, High Shear situations in other countries.

Composite indices such as KI and TT were indicative of TSTM potential in NCR seen via Figure 38c and 38d. A KI of $\sim 38 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is suitable for TSTM with heavy rains due to the available moisture below 700 hPa, unstable air, and a lifting mechanism provided by the inverted trough. Meanwhile, TT at Manila recorded $\sim 44 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, however since TT is the sum of Vertical Totals and Cross Totals, it is possible that the VT component is lower but the CT $\geq 18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which is important for convection to persist. Therefore, it can be slightly unrepresentative of the environment where the moisture resides below the 850-hPa.

In conjunction to the wind profile of the environment as seen in Figure 39a are the SRH in standard heights and TSTM movement components based of Bunkers ID Method. Within, the distinct feature that can be clearly see is the area of relatively large $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ values in the East Philippine Sea of $95 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ which overlays a relatively large CAPE values of $\sim 1500 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ depicted in the previous chart.

Meanwhile, caused to the SWM and westerly winds aloft, considerable SRH values are also being transported from the WPS towards the Central Luzon-NCR-

Southern Tagalog region. $\geq 80 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is being recorded in the 3 km AGL, while $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ were in the lower 50s around Manila as seen and supported by a small contour area of $40 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ centered at Central Luzon. Potential TSTMs may likely be Bunkers RM dominant or move along advective component of ~ 20 to 40 kts.

Accompanied by SRH parameter itself are the helicities or helical parcels containing streamwise vorticity to be ingested by a TSTM. Seen Figure 39b, SWH values of $\geq 0.03 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ in the East Philippine Sea coincides relative to the available buoyancy and conventional kinematic parameters discussed previously. The large area of helicity-rich environment also contains an ample streamwise vorticity with ζ_{SWM} of $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$ can be ingested by TSTMs' base making it tornadogenic.

At the western section involving NCR, the SWM and westerlies aloft are also rich in SWH recording $\geq 0.04-0.05 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ and similarly, ambient horizontal vorticity reaching $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$. These kinematic properties were then transported by the wind profile towards the area of interest. In Manila, SWH values is recorded to be 0.021 m s^{-2} while inside and comprised by a ζ_{SWM} contour of $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$. This makes the background wind profile susceptible and ready for HCW, though the available buoyancy lagging as previously shown.

Other and additional composite indices such as SWEAT, $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$, and SCP_{fix} , including the updraft velocity, also depicted some instability along the western section of Luzon. These parameters were combined in Figure 39c and 39d with SWEAT value maxing out at ~ 400 units in Zambales' coast suggesting potential HCW, especially if convective storm and boundary interactions happen that can increase the local shear.

The said area also coincides on CAPE values well above 1500 J kg^{-1} hinting modest updraft velocities $\geq 50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, fixed-layer SCP of 0.3 units and EHI in the 3 km AGL of 0.3 to 0.5 units.

Within eastern sea board, W_{\max} of $\geq 50 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ were also reported overlaying an area of large $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ and SCP_{fix} of 1 unit and 1.6 unit, respectively. Despite being located in open waters, warm moist air parcels can have a hard time breaking away and overcoming the capping layer to generate TSTMs as CIN is $\geq 200 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$. If one does so, then convective cells can proliferate and attain some supercellular characteristics due to the favorable simulated environment.

Along the metropolis on the other hand, both $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ and SCP_{fix} values were ≤ 0.3 units as contributed by the meager SBCAPE values capped by the suppressing negative buoyancy layer, though accompanied by modest BWD possibly depicting as a Low CAPE, High Shear convection. So as its W_{\max} was also affected and only limited to reach $\sim 33.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ within the convective storm's updraft. This points the finger that more exertion of work for lifting air parcels needs to be done, either through moisture return flow and continuous destabilization over time for DCI. However, as we shall see, CAPE values in NCR; likely on the others areas within the grid including other parameters, are vastly underestimated and poorly discriminates the actual HCW than the extracted sounding in succeeding subsection.

Meanwhile, NCEP FNL have a different take on the severe weather environment for the TSTM-producing tornado than the previous solution earlier discussed. At 06 UTC, large instability ranging from 1500 to 3000 J kg^{-1} is located in

Figure 40

NCEP FNL Mesoscale Panels. (a) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface-based CAPE (contour filled; $J kg^{-1}$) with outlines of CIN (blue dashed lines; $J kg^{-1}$). (b) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), V_{SFC} (kt), and BRN Shear (contour filled; $m^2 s^{-2}$). (c) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface Gust (kt), and K Index (contour filled; K). (d) Isobars (black solid lines; hPa), Surface Gust (kt), and Totals Total Index (contour filled; K). Surface Trough's Axis is denoted with Red Dashed Lines.

the WPS, facing the *entrance* gate of the inverted trough annotated in Figure 40a. With moisture being transported towards inland, an SBCAPE of $1456 J kg^{-1}$ with no CIN is recorded along Manila and co-located within a patch of instability reaching $\geq 1000 J kg^{-1}$ in Central Luzon.

Figure 41

Additional TSTM indices from NCEP FNL composed of; (a) Right-moving, Mean Wind, and Left-moving Storm motion vectors based of Bunkers ID (RM, MW, LM, quivers; kt) and Storm-Relative Helicity (SRH_{0-3km} & SRH_{0-1km} , black dashed lines and contour filled; $m^2 s^{-2}$) at 0-1 and 0-3 km layer. (b) 0-3 km Streamwise Helicity (SWH; contour filled; $m s^{-2}$) and 0-500 m Streamwise Vorticity (ζ_{SWM} , black dashed lines; s^{-1}). (c) V_{SFC} (kt) and SWEAT Index (contour filled). (d) W_{max} (contour filled; $m s^{-1}$), 0-3 km Energy Helicity Index (EHI_{0-3km} , black solid lines), and Fixed-layer Supercell Composite Parameter (SCP_{fix} , white dashed lines). Surface Trough's Axis is denoted with Red Dashed Lines.

This patch of unstable atmosphere coincides with an area of weak mean vertical shear shown in Figure 40b. BRN Shear in particular is at $10 m^2 s^{-2}$ in Manila while the dimensionless BRN resides at 134 units supporting weak shear relative to

Figure 42

Additional TSTM indices from NCEP FNL. V_{GUST} (kt) and LI based of; surfac-ebased (contour filled; °C) and most-unstable parcel (dashed contour lines; °C).

the ample available buoyancy. Thus, favoring multicellular cluster of free TSTMs.

From both Figure 40c and 40d, KI and TT composite indices are showing signs of TSTM potential in NCR. A KI of ~ 37 °C is suitable for TSTM with heavy rains due to the low-level moisture and growing instability while at the presence of a lifting mechanism brought by the pressure trough. Similarly, TT at Manila recorded ~ 43 °C, a degree less than the ERA5 Re. As indicated before, it is possible that the VT

component is lower but the $CT \geq 18 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which is important for convection to persist. Therefore, it can be slightly unrepresentative of the environment where the moisture resides below the PBL.

Similar to the previous solution presented and in conjunction to the wind profile of the environment as seen in Figure 41a are the SRH in standard heights and TSTM movement components based of Bunkers ID Method. Similarly, to ERA5 Re, the distinct feature that can be clearly see is the area of relatively large $SRH_{0-3\text{km}}$ values in the East Philippine Sea of $\geq 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ which overlays a relatively large CAPE values of $\sim 2000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ depicted in the previous chart.

Meanwhile, due to the SWM and westerly winds aloft, small SRH values are also being propagated from the WPS towards the Central Luzon-NCR-Southern Tagalog region. $\sim 60 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is being recorded in the 3 km AGL, while $SRH_{0-1\text{km}}$ of $\sim 20 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ is seen around Manila. Although the solution lags considerable than the ERA5 Re and observed ones, the moisture transport may also include the increase of SRH throughout the layers indicated where the WPS is coupled by the $100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. Additionally, TSTMs that will develop likely will also move parallel to the Bunkers RM and 0-6 km MW of ~ 20 to 40 kts.

Seen in Figure 41b, SWH values of $\geq 0.03 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ in the East Philippine Sea also coincides relative to the available buoyancy and conventional kinematic parameters discussed previously. The large area of helicity-rich environment also contains an ample streamwise vorticity with ζ_{SWM} of $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$ that can be ingested by the potential TSTMs' base making it more tornadogenic.

At the western section involving NCR, the SWM and westerlies aloft are also rich in SWH recording ≥ 0.04 to 0.05 m s^{-2} and similarly, ambient horizontal vorticity reaching $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The wind profile can also transport these kinematic properties towards the area of interest. In Manila, SWH values is recorded to be 0.017 m s^{-2} while located at the outer periphery of a ζ_{SWM} contour of $\geq 0.012 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Similarly, the background wind profile is susceptible and ready for HCW with more than $\geq 1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ of CAPE for vertical stretching and tilting.

Additional composite indices such as SWEAT, $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$, and SCP_{fix} and undiluted W_{max} , also depicted a growing instability along the Eastern section of Luzon instead. These parameters were combined in Figure 41c and 41d with SWEAT value reaching ~ 385 units in Eastern sea board of Luzon landmass suggesting some risk of HCW. The said area also coincides on CAPE values $\geq 1500 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ hinting high updraft velocities $\geq 70 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and SCP_{fix} and $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ of ≥ 1 unit.

Towards the WPS, W_{max} of $\geq 70 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ were also reported overlaying both contour lines of large $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ and SCP_{fix} of ≥ 1 unit. Generally, with no capping present, warm moist air parcels can easily be transported by the previously-discussed wind profile. This is further exacerbated by the favorable synoptic condition making volatile free convective TSTMs along western coast.

Along the metropolis on the other hand, SCP_{fix} values were at ≤ 0.3 units due to the low SRH values, but $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ are at 0.61 units counteracted by the CAPE values $\geq 1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and supported by Figure 42 where the temperature deficit between the parcel and environment (LI) of ≥ -4 . As such, the W_{max} within the convective storm's

updraft may potentially reach 54 m s^{-1} . Overall, the NCEP FNL may have been hinting a High CAPE, Low Shear environment different the ERA5 Re mesoscale situation substantially. Though still accompanied by the sufficient background vorticity and may further destabilize as moisture return kicks in.

3.3. Model Vertical Soundings

Aside from classical RAOBs presented earlier, we generated grid point sounding profiles out of the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL datasets by parsing and interpolating both grids and isobaric levels. A compilation of NWP-based profiles that are pin-pointed in the coordinates of Manila is showcased in Figures 43 and 44 for the ERA5 Re. Meanwhile, Figures 45 and 46 are designated for the NCEP FNL model. Each frame is displayed in succeeding appendices.

First, the ERA5 Re profile at 00 UTC materializes a large thermodynamic and kinematic background environment hinting some *free* surface-based storms as SBCAPE reaches 2935 J kg^{-1} . Supersaturation seems to occur well above the surface in the first 2 km AGL before transitioning into a fairly dry layer allowing large instability. Potential TSTMs were efficient (81%) in tapping the undiluted buoyancy with ECAPE of 2384 J kg^{-1} due to the veering winds and moist troposphere.

Speaking of veering winds, along the hodograph, veering profile generated a curved hodograph that can support long-lived TSTMs sometime while having a modest shear magnitude at 16 kts in the lowest 1 km AGL and DLS of 25 kts. Notice that the wind profile does a 'small loop' between the 400- to 300-hPa due to the UL HPA centered in Northern Luzon with light northerly winds. As such, $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ were

also in a lesser degree of $85 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ while having a substantial helicity in the 3 km AGL of $145 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. With SCP_{eff} at initially 5 units, and both $\text{EHI}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ at 1.6 and 2.7 units respectively, potential TSTMs can attain supercell nature capable of producing tornadoes due to the favorable conditions mentioned.

3 hours later on 03 UTC, the undiluted SBCAPE slightly decreases by nearly 300 J kg^{-1} but remains potent otherwise with EHI in both layers are ≥ 2 units. This is likely due to the dry buldge spanning from the lower to upper levels that grew larger diluting the warm, moist air parcel upon crossing the LFC. This in turn takes a small toll on the updraft efficiency to withstand dilution by $\sim 3\%$ from its previous measurement, though is backed by the background winds in place.

The kinematic mechanism that are in place, particularly shear profile, are in a weakening trend as it rises with altitude. A LLS of 23 kts is recorded while DLS are at 19 kts in the 6 km AGL which can still support some rotating updrafts. Both $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ were in the $100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ range, specifically $121 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $149 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ with respect to their aforementioned heights. Despite the slightly worse shear profile which in turn contributes to the lack of storm inflow, the ample streamwise vorticity instead contributed to the large SRH which in turn can be ingested by the developing updraft.

By 06 UTC, the thermodynamics; particularly SBCAPE, have reached its peak at 3441 J kg^{-1} along an ECAPE of $\sim 2700 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$. By normalizing both values, the developing severe TSTM still realize 78% of the undiluted available buoyancy in place due to the moist and veering profile making updraft initiation remain stout to environmental-dilution. The theoretical maximum thermodynamic velocity within the

Figure 43

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile from 00 UTC to 12 UTC (from (a) to (m)) with hourly timesteps. Skew-T and Hodograph wind profiles are included. Red (T and T_V) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure 44

Connected to Figure 43 is the ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile from 00 UTC to 12 UTC (from (a) to (m)) with hourly timesteps. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

updraft column may also reach $\sim 83 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, though by using ECAPE instead will slightly reduce to 73.5 m s^{-1} .

The maximum undiluted thermodynamics grew larger and moist as it approached diurnal maximum convective heating that took place in the midnoon to afternoon. As we have seen in the meteogram at Figure 22, ground-relative observations revealed substantial warming with near-surface temperatures above ≥ 30 °C and T_v of ≥ 35 °C along a large difference between the ~ 25 °C surface T_D . This aids the already buoyant parcels of air to precipitously rise while making the storm base also close to the ground.

The dry intrusion area spanning from 800- to 400-hPa as depicted before have also thinned out likely due to the low-level moisture transport by the SWM and westerly winds aloft. When the moist atmosphere encounters dry air, moist air mixed with dry air can ascend and a supercell develops in these conditions. Meanwhile, the wind profile remains a major component for severe weather to develop, especially with an increasing trend with height. BWD in the low-levels were near the 20 kts range while MLS vector bumped up to 24 kts accompanied by a fairly large SRH_{0-3km} of $149 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. SCP_{eff} climbed up to 6 units and EHI parameters are well above 2 units further supporting and favoring supercell initiation with potential for tornadogenesis in Manila.

At 08 UTC, 30 mins before the tornadic initiation, the wind profile was more uniform as the UL HPA moved away from the landmass. SRH values in the 1 km and 3 km AGL have increased and spiked drastically to $104 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $174 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ due to the 20 kts and 26 kts VWS, respectively in each layers along an SWV-rich environment and modest RM storm inflow. Above, the 18 kts of DLS along an SRH in 6 km AGL of

$163 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ can favor and allow TSTMs' updraft column to rotate as mesocyclone or misocyclone.

Free convective storm mode seems to be the theme of the thermodynamic environment composed with $\sim 3100 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ with no capping layer. With SCP_{eff} at 7 units along an STP_{fix} of 1 unit and both EHI_{0-3km} and SWEAT maxing out to 3.4 units and 384 units, respectively, the atmosphere was well-primed and volatile for severe weather to occur with TSTMs attaining supercellular characteristics that have potential and risk for significant tornadoes to occur ($\geq(\text{E})\text{F2}$).

An hour after, the post-tornadic profile revealed a potent thermodynamics and kinematics comprised by a moist low- and upper-levels generating 3380 J kg^{-1} of CAPE based of parcel-profile lifted from the surface. Hints of supersaturation was depicted between 300- to 400-hPa levels within the model sounding as humid parcels contain more water vapor than it can hold at equilibrium. Due to its unstable nature and continuous uplift, the excess vapor can be quickly converted to liquid through cloud condensation by providing embryonic nuclei. Thus, it allowed convective clouds to further develop and intensify.

The simulated hodograph remained curved due to the veering winds imposed by the SWM and westerly jet streak aloft along a 20 kts, 26 kts, and 18 kts of LLS, MLS, and DLS, respectively. $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ containing sufficient SWV are also nearly the same an hour ago, with the 3 km AGL having $160 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ as ingested and tilted by the updraft inflow base for tornado development. Composite indices remained the same as in the previous hinting a volatile environment for severe TSTMs

with supercellular characteristics and risk for significant tornadoes to take place (\geq (E)F2) within the area of interest.

3 hours later as part of post-tornadic environment, the thermodynamics remained very potent along Manila City. Undiluted SBCAPE is still near 3000 J kg^{-1} threshold with a maximum updraft speed of $\sim 77.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and layer of supersaturation above 400-hPa present. This allowed generation of stout updrafts that can overcome tropospheric dilution.

The kinematic mechanism further improved towards the evening due to the curved hodograph profile. Bulk shear across all 3 layers is well above 20 kts, with LLS at 23 kts, 27 kts of shear magnitude in the mid-levels, and 23 kts of DLS allowing potential TSTMs to achieve rotation. Due to the healthy shear magnitude present, $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ containing ample horizontal vorticity have exceeded $133 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $196 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively. With SCP_{eff} at ~ 9 units along an STP_{fix} of ~ 2 unit and $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ of 3.7 units, the environment remained capable in producing for TSTMs that have potential for meso/misocyclone-induced significant tornadoes.

On the other hand, NCEP FNL diverges from the ERA5 Re profiles with a less aggressive thermo-kinematic indices. We note however, that the CAPE in the first 3 km AGL is not present in majority of the NCEP FNL cases due to a 'MetPy bug' on calculating CAPE for a layer.

Initially at 00 UTC, both SB and MUCAPE are at 2682 J kg^{-1} along a relatively moist profile, veering winds, and steep LR_s near ground level promoting an ECAPE of 1967 J kg^{-1} . This allows potential TSTMs to tap 73% of the available undiluted CAPE

Figure 45

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile from 00 UTC to 12 UTC (from (a) to (e)) with 3 hr timesteps. Skew-T and Hodograph wind profiles are included. Red (T and T_V) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure 46

Connected to Figure 44 is the NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile from 00 UTC to 12 UTC (from (a) to (e)) with hourly timesteps. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Initially at 00 UTC, both SB and MUCAPE are at 2682 J kg^{-1} along a relatively moist profile, veering winds, and steep LR_s near ground level promoting an ECAPE of 1967 J kg^{-1} . This allows potential TSTMs to tap 73% of the available undiluted

making it less susceptible to entrainment dilution. Composite EHI both in 1 km AGL and 3 km AGL are above ≥ 1 unit along a SWEAT value of 351 units can indicate for potential severe weather to materialize.

The kinematic profile at the same time revealed an ample vertical shear with LLS of 17 kts while 20 kts near the upper-levels which can support some meso/misocyclonic rotation. Within the slightly curved hodograph and a 20 kts of storm-relative inflow, this in turn aided to generate fairly modest helicity values than the previous solution with SRH0-1km and SRH0-3km reportedly are at $79 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $111 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively.

By 03 UTC, the thermodynamic environment remains same yet potent otherwise allowing potential TSTMs to realize $\sim 71\%$ of its undiluted SBCAPE. However, MLCAPE have decreased to 787 J kg^{-1} from the previous reading. VWS across all layers have also weakened with LLS of 14 kts, and both MLS and DLS of 16 kts making it difficult to achieve TSTM rotation, further exacerbated by the slow-moving RM component of 17 kts.

With wind shear lacking, it also took a toll on the storm helicity with SRH_{0-1km} and SRH_{0-3km} of $59 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $94 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$, respectively can hinder mesocyclonic rotation and tornadic initiation. Conventional indices also decreased with respect to the derived SRH as both EHI_{0-1km} and EHI_{0-3km} decreased to 1 unit and 1.6 units, respectively, making the chances of supercell tornadoes limited.

The undiluted thermodynamics reached its maximum at 06 UTC as SBCAPE (so as MUCAPE) reaches $\sim 3000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ with no capping layer, with MLCAPE slightly

increases up to 863 J kg^{-1} . However, potential TSTMs and their updrafts can be slightly less efficient in harnessing the full potential energy in place reducing to an ECAPE of 2001 J kg^{-1} and fractional entrainment (\tilde{E}) at 67% instead due to the impacts of less storm inflow and lack of wind shear.

And speaking of wind shear as seen along the hodograph, the shear magnitude remains dull with 0-6 km VWS of just 12 kts. So as the Bunkers RM component of just 13 kts which in turn gives off low values of SRH across two layers i.e. 1 km and 3 km layer at $44 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and $71 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. Composite indices i.e. EHI in the first 1 km and 3 km AGL also subsided to below ≤ 1 unit across the two layers barely hinting potential TSTMs that are tornadogenic.

3 hours later at 09 UTC, the small inverted-V profile with relatively moist layer in the upper levels shows that the undiluted CAPE have decreased by $\sim 1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ though remains substantial by all means due to the steep LRs in the low-levels allowing warm buoyant air parcels to rise precipitously. With an ECAPE of 1420 J kg^{-1} , any thriving convective storms can be efficient in realizing its thermodynamic potential energy at 71% making it less susceptible to dilution than the previous setting 3 hours ago.

The slight increase to fractional ECAPE is due to the small bump of storm-relative inflow where the low-level wind shear increased to 18 kts and RM component from Bunkers ID of 16 kts as calculated from the simulated hodograph. This also makes the potential TSTMs' thin updraft column resistant to tropospheric dilution as indicated. The increase of LLS and RM component also led to some increase within

the derived SRH parameters. The SRH_{0-1km} improved to $62 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ while SRH_{0-3km} is reported to be at $80 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. Regardless, EHI across the two layers remains well below, if not equal, to the 1 unit threshold (EHI_{0-1km} and EHI_{0-3km} of 0.8 unit and 1 unit, respectively) making it less possible for potential severe TSTMs to attain mesocyclonic features with risk of brief tornadoes.

At the evening, the undiluted CAPE relaxes to 1753 J kg^{-1} hinting a small CIN of -9 J kg^{-1} and an MLCAPE grew to 972 J kg^{-1} . Warm moist air parcels can still penetrate through the small inhibiting layer with the aid of synoptic lifting by the surface trough. Furthermore, potential TSTMs remained efficient in realizing the full thermodynamic profile of the environment at 71% resisting to tropospheric entrainment-dilution.

This is due to the increased vertical shear in the low- and mid-levels at 22 kts and 19 kts, respectively. However, the storm-relative inflow regressed to just 13 kts along the Bunkers RM. This is in turn affected the SRH values across two layers being calculated with SRH_{0-1km} at $41 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and SRH_{0-3km} of $89 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. With lesser degree of CAPE and SRH remains the same, if not inferior than the previous run, the EHI value in the first 1 km AGL further decreased to just 0.5 units, while still retaining the 1 unit within the 3 km AGL allowing the potential TSTMs to form. However, attaining supercell characteristics and tornadoes to form is unlikely in most cases.

Despite the meager SRH values and lack of storm inflow within the NCEP FNL point hodographs, it is possible that the vorticity component within the SRH parameter itself is large $\geq 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$ counteracting the inflow deficit. And this vorticity can be

ingested efficient TSTMs updrafts with 190 J kg^{-1} of undiluted CAPE present in the first 3 km AGL. Across all calculations of NCEP FNL soundings, both SCP_{eff} and STP_{fix} rendered indescribable at 0 unit, hence non-tornadic and supercell storm. Despite the large instability in place, the considerably lagging wind profile, especially with the generally weakening trend of the bulk shear in the 0-6 km AGL, have hindered the potential for developing and maturing TSTMs to attain supercell nature with risk for tornadoes.

3.4. Severe Weather Characteristics and Baseline Climatology

We further evaluated the HCW by comparing the Manila Tornado's environmental characteristics to the available baseline climatology of parameters commonly used in forecasting TSTM, HCW and specifically, to tornadoes. This includes the Tanay RAOB and the grid point profiles from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL. However, in the Philippines, no known baseline climatology exists yet that is adequate to support these quantifications for most of the thermo-kinematic parameters utilized.

To test out the environment, we rely heavily to the climatological benchmark studies and criteria for significant tornadoes (SigTor ; $\geq (\text{E})\text{F2}$) as conducted by Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998) and Thompson et al. (2003), and a more recent study by Thompson et al. (2012) from discrete RM supercells with risk for SigTor in the Great Plains of the U.S. (Tornado Alley). These are well-known and established methods along the location of an increasingly alarming rate of tornado occurrences $\geq \text{EF2}$ (Elsner et al., 2019). The comparison between the two was conducted and displayed on Figures 47 and 48 in order.

Figure 47

Comparison of the Parameter Ranges of the Manila Tornadoic Environment (Red/Blue Boxplots as Ranges and Red/Blue x for exact values) calculated with the Tanay RAOBs from 00 and 12 UTC in Figure 4.15 and 4.16 to the U.S. Baseline Climatology for a Supercellular Tornado Environment given by Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998), Thompson et al. (2003), and Thompson et al. (2012).

Figure 48

Additional Parameters for Comparison of the Manila Tornadoic Environment (Red/Blue x for exact values) calculated with the Tanay RAOBs from 00 and 12 UTC in Figure 4.15 and 4.16 to the U.S. Baseline Climatology for a Supercellular Tornado Environment given by Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998), Thompson et al. (2003) and Thompson et al. (2012).

With each CAPE distribution increasing monotonically and the 00 and 12 UTC RAOB together its derived convective potential ranges presented in Table 4 and 5, the undiluted buoyancy values from the SB-parcel hovered between the IQR at 64th and 89th percentile for the 00 UTC sounding, while 68th towards 94th percentile by 12 UTC. Meanwhile, the MUCAPE ranges (since SBCAPE ≈ MUCAPE) are located at the Inter-Quartile Range (IQR). Specifically, the 00 UTC buoyancy range is sitting between the 41th and 52nd percentile area, while the 12 UTC MUCAPE values are less constricted spanning from 44th to 60th percentile region.

In the SBCAPE and MUCAPE distributions, both 00 and 12 UTC buoyancies are overlapped in this case with 00 UTC values having a tighter range and differences at 172 J kg^{-1} , while 12 UTC sounding had more spread by as nearly as 300 J kg^{-1} . The overlapping is also visible with the CAPE using an ML-parcel. The MLCAPE values across the RAOBs are encompassed on the box distribution, with 00 UTC at the IQR from 39th to ~51st percentile, while the 12 UTC sounding spans from near minimum to the median, due to the large deviation on the derived CAPE using a ML-parcel profile.

Both the calculated $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ using Bunkers ID algorithm within those times are located within the IQR, with the 0–1 km and 0–3 km AGL above the median (57th and 55th percentiles) and below the median of the baseline norm (43rd and 49th percentiles), respectively. This could indicate that the SRH are within the majority of the supercells that can form significant tornadoes.

Additionally, the various EHI parameters, including the MLEHI devised by Thompson et al. (2003), are also utilized for point of comparison of the Manila Tornado's environment. In the 0–1 km method, both measurements from 00 and 12 UTC are well below the imposed median, on 48th and 39th percentiles, which can be used to identify between tornadic and non-tornadic storms. On the flipped side, the 0–3 km AGL are well above the median with the 12 UTC located at the upper-quartile range (65th and 95th percentiles), although the usage of the $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ can be fixated in diagnosing supercell TSTMs and ordinary convective modes. Meanwhile, using MLCAPE and $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ in combination, the $\text{MLEHI}_{0-1\text{km}}$ values from both RAOBs are

below the imposed median were the 00 UTC is within the IQR at 38th percentile, while the MLEHI_{0-1km} at 12 UTC lagged at 6th percentile.

Additional matching of the environment is conducted on other parameters involving vertical shear and composite indices. In particular, the shear magnitude at the 0–1 km LLS values are at 86th and 99th percentiles to each timestamp. However, ascending to the 0–6 km deep layer, the vertical shear is considerably weaker than most of the accounted soundings in the baseline. The DLS reading at 00 UTC is at 34th percentile while the 12 UTC 0–6 km shear had dropped down by ~28th ranks lagging behind the majority of high DLS environments.

Although a depreciated parameter already, the VGP signature up to 0–4 km AGL of both 00 and 12 UTC were above and below the 25th and 50th percentile, exactly at 38th and 41th percentiles to each time of launch. Both SCP and STP values in fixed-layer in the morning are within the bounds of the baseline climatology for severe environments at 37th and 10th percentile, respectively. By 12 UTC, the composite values are at 38th and near the lower quartile limit still describable for HCW i.e. SigTors.

In addition, we also benchmarked our sounding profiles derived from the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL as presented and discussed earlier. Each of the calculated parameters in the solutions were accumulated accordingly. In total, we have 13 samples for the ERA5 Re (from 00 UTC to 12 UTC with hourly timesteps) and only 5 samples for the NCEP FNL profiles (from 00 UTC to 12 UTC with 3-hr temporal resolution). The comparison of each utilized dataset is shown in Figures 49 and 50.

In ERA5 Re solution, our SBCAPE values are within the upper bounds of the baseline distribution. The two lower outliers within the ERA5 Re distribution fall along the 86th and 93rd percentile, while the lower 10th percentile limit are within the 95th percentile. The SB/MUCAPE values from ERA5 Re solution are very tight to each other with lower half of the IQR sitting at the upper limit of the baseline distribution while the rest; including the median, being an outlier instead. This can mean that SB/MUCAPE measurements from the ERA5 Re profiles linked to the tornadic event are in the same league as those of surface-based storms capable of producing tornadoes.

The situation changes when these derived CAPE values are in the MUCAPE climatological baseline. While the whole distribution is within the baseline's norms, the ERA5 Re's IQR falls between the 84th and 88th percentile. The ERA5 Re's minimum percentile sits within 62nd percentile, while the maximum percentile is at the 92nd percentile of the baseline. The outliers were also within the scope of the baseline distribution where the lower outliers; 02 and 07 UTC MUCAPE, sits below the median and 58th percentile of the baseline respectively, while the sole outlier beyond the maxima is at the 94th percentile.

When it comes to CAPE derived from mixed-layer parcel properties, the ERA5 Re vertical soundings lags considerably to the rest of the sounding baseline. Half of the MLCAPE's distribution, particularly the upper IQR, are confined within the first 25th to 38th percentile. Only a small portion of MLCAPE's IQR falls short of the 25th percentile limit, though separated only by 2 ranks below. Lastly, the minimum and ma-

Figure 49

Comparison of the Parameter Ranges of the Manila Tornadoic Environment to the U.S. Baseline Climatology for a Supercellular Tornado Environment given by Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998), Thompson et al. (2003), and Thompson et al. (2012). Sounding profiles are from ERA5 Re (Red Boxplot) and NCEP FNL (Blue Boxplot) cumulatively from 00 to 12 UTC shown in Figure 42 and 44.

Figure 50

Additional Parameters for Comparison of the Manila Tornadic Environment to the U.S. Baseline Climatology for a Supercellular Tornado Environment given by Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998), Thompson et al. (2003) and Thompson et al. (2012). Sounding profiles are from ERA5 Re (Red Boxplot) and NCEP FNL (Blue Boxplot) cumulatively from 00 to 12 UTC shown in Figure 42 and 44.

imum limits of the ERA5 Re MLCAPE distribution are bounded in the 13th and 41st percentile of the MLCAPE baseline. We also note that one of the soundings recorded an MLCAPE of 0 J kg⁻¹; thus, an outlier to the baseline norm.

In the SRH parameters, our distributions increase monotonically according to each layers and remains constricted to one another. The 0–1 km AGL shows that the median falls right within the 25th percentile, directly bisecting the lower and upper SRH_{0-1km} distribution. In particular, the upper IQR’s 75th limit was at the 37th percentile of the baseline, while the lower 25th limit was outside of the baseline’s IQR in 13th

percentile. On the other hand, nearly the tight bulk of SRH_{0-3km} derived from ERA5 Re point soundings fall short of the baseline's IQR. Specifically, the IQR of the ERA5 Re distribution sits between the 11th and 34th percentile ranges, with ERA5 Re median at 12th percentile. The upper and lower limits of ERA5 Re's SRH_{0-3km} boxplot are located on the 40th and ~10th percentile, respectively.

Our EHI parameters meanwhile exhibit a relatively similar trend to the ERA5 Re CAPE distributions presented, though removing the MLCAPE solution on the EHI shows also a monotonic increase in a similar fashion to the SRH. In the 0–1 km AGL, the composite distribution sits within the baseline EHI, where the IQR is between the 25th percentile and the baseline's median; more specifically the median of the ERA5 Re EHI_{0-1km} boxplot is located at the 34th percentile. Both the upper and lower bounds of the distribution are above the median and below the first quartile limit.

Along the conventional 0–3 km AGL relative to the set baseline, the ERA5 Re's IQR falls between the 65th and 91st percentile, with the distribution's median at the 84th percentile. The median nearly segments between a small and large portion of IQR of EHI_{0-3km} that falls below and above the upper quartile limit, respectively. The minimum of the ERA5 Re distribution is located at the 57th percentile, while the maxima is situated in the 97th percentile of baseline.

We also sought out to test the Mixed-layer EHI, initially conducted by Thompson et al. (2003). Combining the MLCAPE and SRH in the 0–1 km AGL, the $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ are compact and stands well below the baseline's IQR. This is also due to the relatively small value of MLCAPE with more than a half of the soundings have

$\leq 1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$. The 25th and 75th percentile (quartile limits) are confounded at the 1st and 3rd percentiles, while the minimum limit; including an outlier due to an MLCAPE of 0 J kg^{-1} , of the $\text{MLEHI}_{0-1\text{km}}$ from ERA5 Re falls as an outlier to the climatological distribution.

Further matching of the ERA5 Re simulated environment is conducted on other parameters involving vertical shear and composite indices. Specifically, the whole distribution of vertical shear at the 0–1 km values are at 1st and 13th percentiles. However, ascending to the 0–6 km deep layer, the bulk shear decreases monotonically and weaker than most of the accounted soundings in the baseline. The cumulative DLS readings are between the minimum and 25th percentile, specifically at the 7th and 12th percentile of the 0-6 km BWD baseline distribution lagging behind the majority of high DLS environments.

Both and cumulative SCP and STP values in effective- and fixed-layer are within the bounds of the baseline climatology for severe environments. The ERA5 Re solutions sports decent SCP_{eff} units as high as ~ 9 units as the upper limit of the distribution. The IQR of the SCP distribution from ERA5 Re manages to between the 13th and 39th percentiles. On the ERA5 Re's STP_{fix} , half of the soundings have STP values at 0 unit especially in the morning, making the IQR extend beyond the baseline's minimum limit. The upper quartile of ERA5 Re STP_{fix} is located at 33rd percentile and the upper limit is on the 36th percentile of the baseline.

With the NCEP FNL on other hand, nearly all of the listed parameters lagged considerably relative to the ERA5 Re solution and even to the baseline climatology

itself, with the exception of the SBCAPE, MUCAPE, and EHI_{0-3km} . However, throughout the testing, the entire NCEP FNL trails behind the previous solution.

Along this solution, our SBCAPE values are encompassed within the upper bounds of the baseline distribution. Extent of this distribution were quite large compared to those of ERA5 Re's compactness, but contributed by the lack of temporal steps i.e. cumulative samples in this case and varying solutions. The maximum bound of the SBCAPE distribution are nearly close to the baseline's maximum. The IQR meanwhile falls along the upper whisker spanning 87th and 97th percentiles.

On the MUCAPE, the bulk of the distribution sits along IQR of the baseline norm. In this case, the MUCAPE's IQR is encapsulated along the ~51st and 63rd percentile. The MUCAPE distribution from NCEP FNL solution had its minimum value located within 44th percentile, while the maximum percentile at the 86th percentile of the baseline.

With parcel profile using mixed-layer properties on the other hand, the NCEP FNL point soundings also suffers the same fate as the ERA5 Re lagging behind considerably to the rest of the sounding baseline. The IQR of the MLCAPE's distribution, including the minimum limit, are confined well below the initial quartile limit. The minimum and maximum limits of the NCEP FNL MLCAPE distribution are bounded in the 10th and 36th percentile of the MLCAPE baseline.

In the SRH parameters, our distributions also followed the monotonic behaviour according to each layer. However, across all layers, the distributions fall as an outlier. Only the upper limits of both distributions managed to be included on the SRH baseline

in this case. The maximum values of SRH_{0-1km} and SRH_{0-3km} are located at 3rd and 1st percentiles of each normal distribution, accordingly.

Going to one of our composite parameters, EHI, it also exhibited a relatively similar trend to the CAPE from NCEP FNL presented, though removing the MLCAPE solution on the EHI shows also a monotonic increase in a similar fashion to the SRH. In the 0–1 km AGL, the composite distribution is marked along the lower whisker outside the baseline's IQR. With limited samples, the IQR of the EHI_{0-1km} is between the 3rd percentile and 4th. Both the minimum and maximum values of EHI_{0-1km} derived from NCEP FNL were treated as outliers, but still follows the baseline being set at 1st and 6th percentiles.

Along the conventional 0–3 km AGL relative to the climatological baseline, the NCEP FNL's IQR falls between the 43rd and 52nd percentile, with the distribution's median at the 47th percentile. The minimum of the NCEP FNL distribution is also located at the 43rd percentile similar to the first quartile bound, while the maximum limit is situated in the 55th percentile of baseline climatology. The combination of MLCAPE and SRH_{0-1km} is also tested out yielding to the $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ parameter being utilized. In this regard however, the $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ values associated in this distribution were tightly narrow and small, which then falls below and outside the baseline from Thompson et al. (2003).

Additional comparison and matching of the NCEP FNL point soundings are conducted on other parameters involving vertical shear and composite indices. Specifically, nearly half distribution of vertical shear at the 0–1 km values are at 2nd

and 11th percentiles, while the lower half of the NCEP FNL distribution falls as an outlier. Meanwhile, as we ascend to the 0–6 km layer and similar to ERA5 Re, a decreasing trend is also depicted as the bulk shear decreases monotonically and weaker than most of the accounted soundings in the baseline. The cumulative DLS readings are also located between the minimum and 25th percentile, specifically at the 1st and 11th percentile of the 0-6 km BWD baseline distribution. This is also indicative that the severe weather's kinematics in play lagged behind the majority of high DLS environments.

On the other hand, the SCP and STP values in effective- and fixed-layer coming from the NCEP FNL profiles are also indiscernible with nearly all point soundings recording no unit/value to each parameter. Except for the 12 UTC NCEP FNL sounding recording an SCP_{eff} of 1.6 units, though an outlier as well relative to the baseline from Thompson et al. (2012).

Additionally, we further examined the environment by evaluating the CAPE-SRH space, both for 0-1 km and 0-3 km AGL. The scatter distribution of the two variables entailed in the EHI parameter is displayed and plotted in Figure 51. We also substituted the undiluted CAPE with ECAPE and implemented a new EHI parameter we called as "Entrained Energy-Helicity Index" ($E_{NT}EHI$) from the works of Hart and Korotky (1991). In this form, the influences of entrainment-driven dilution on the positive buoyancy was encapsulated together with the kinematic profile brought by storm inflow and vertical shear. Tweaking the conventional EHI with ECAPE results to;

$$E_{\text{NTEHI}} = \frac{(\text{ECAPE})(\text{SRH})}{1.6 \times 10^5}$$

Where ECAPE is the Entraining CAPE using the analytic formulation of Peters et al. (2023a) and SRH can be in the 0–1 km or 0–3 km AGL. Although, we also advise the use of the 0–1 km layer to match the SRW requirement of ECAPE and since its a better predictor among the tornadic and non-tornadic storm modes than is the quantity customarily computed.

An examination of Figures 51a and d reveals only 2 out of the 20 cumulative soundings (both Tanay RAOB and Model Profiles from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL starting at 00 to 12 UTC) are well below the 1.5 optimal line. This translates to 90% that have the potential for supercellular storms that can initiate tornadoes. Switching to the 0-1 km SRH solution, 90% of the cumulative soundings during that timeframe are also capable of supercell-induced tornadoes as it is well above the 1.0 optimal value (Brooks et al., 1994a; Brooks et al., 1994b). On the remaining 10%, the EHI values are encompassed instead by the 0.7 line of Rasmussen (2003) which can be treated as 'marginally' capable of producing tornadoes.

On Figures 51b and e, an MLCAPE instead is being used on scatter space. With the $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ combined, only the Tanay RAOBs are placed within the bounds, while rest are clumped outside the optimal line. Nearly half were able to reach $\geq 1000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$, while the rest were some were in the range of $800-900 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ accompanied by ample $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}} \geq 100-150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. The same fashion is also being exhibited by 0–1 km AGL as the Tanay RAOBs are placed well beyond the 1.5 optimal line. The model

Figure 51

Scatter Diagrams of composite EHI parameter with SRH in 0–1 km and 0–3 km AGL, and various forms of CAPE. Red circles indicate the observed RAOB from Tanay at 00 and 12 UTC while Blue circles indicate the extracted model profiles from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL.

Note: The dashed lines are the optimal values based of Rasmussen and Blanchard (1998) (1.5), Rasmussen (2003) (0.7), and both Brooks et al. (1994a) and Brooks et al. (1994b) (1.0) for Tornadic situations.

soundings still lagged substantially, but nearly ~11 out of 20 soundings managed to be located at the constraints placed by Rasmussen (2003). In this case of model soundings, both EHI_{0-3km} and EHI_{0-1km} values greater than 0.7 or 1.0 are most likely a combined result of the modest MLCAPE ($\geq 800-900 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$) and $SRH_{0-1km} > 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ situations.

Lastly at Figures 51c and f, we utilized the newly-revised EHI; $E_{ENT}EHI$, with the ECAPE parameter. In the 0–3 km AGL, 80% of the 20 available samples are encompassed by the 1.5 line. The Tanay RAOBs are closer to the optimal value than the conventional undiluted CAPE when entrainment is included. Furthermore, the

ERA5 Re vertical profiles remain inside the contour region with ample $E_{CAPE} \geq 1500 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and SRH_{0-3km} around $150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$.

By matching up with the 0-1 km SRW requirement of the E_{CAPE} parameter with SRH_{0-1km} as well, the shift of available sounding values is also present as in previous Figure 51c. Both 00 and 12 UTC Tanay RAOBs are also nearer in the 1.0 line than the undiluted $CAPE \times SRH_{0-1km}$ space. The samples of ERA5 Re soundings managed to be well-placed inside the fitted line, with 4 of them being able to tap the maximum thermodynamics. On the other hand, the rest of the NCEP FNL also falls outside of the 1.0 benchmarking line although two (2) of those managed to be within the marginal sector.

When distinguishing between last two parameter spaces, the $E_{NTEHI_{0-3km}}$ can yield a more rounded discriminatory skills between non-supercell and supercellular storms. Meanwhile, the E_{NTEHI} in the 0–1 km AGL (Figure 51f) can be used to further identify and zero-in between supercell environments capable of tornadoes and those that are not, especially with the 1-to-1 combination of the 0-1 km SRW and SRH being factored in the composite index. Generally, the EHI values greater than 1.0 are most likely result of the high undiluted CAPE environments. But in the case of the E_{NTEHI} , fractional entrainment in the updraft plume is also contributing to the shift. Although variation in the SRH still exists, small updrafts can be more efficient at utilizing the streamwise vorticity despite the weak SRW flow. Only 3 sounding profiles fall off the 1.0 line, with E_{CAPE} and SRH_{0-1km} values from ERA5 Re are within the imposed limits indicative of the environment's severity.

Figure 52

Scatter plot and Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) of Fractional Entrainments (%; ECAPE vs CAPE) computed in the soundings associated with Manila Tornado.

We further investigated and benchmarked the severe environment by using the fractional entrainment (\tilde{E}) via CAPE vs ECAPE distribution. This is depicted in Figure 52 with several contours constituting $\tilde{E} = 2, 1, 0.5,$ and 0.25 . Despite the lack of samples in this case wherein cumulative soundings are being used instead throughout the period, there's a tight connection between CAPE and ECAPE associated with the potential severe TSTM i.e. with supercellular nature that impacted Manila City, with an $R^2 \approx 0.93$ between the two or a cumulative fractional entrainment of $\sim 93\%$.

Peters et al. (2023a) suggest that $\tilde{E} \geq 0.5$ can be associated with soundings that are depicting supercell events, with their results showing closer to 1 in many supercell profiles at an $R^2 = 0.90$ (90%). Despite the relatively small cumulative samples, the result compliments the previous cited work and supports the notion of

Peters et al. (2019) that supercells realize a larger percentage of their undiluted positive buoyancy than ordinary storms due to the ample vertical shear magnitude and SRW. In this case, however, the Manila Tornado was associated from a TSTM with supercellular characteristics; more of a mini-supercell, and thin mesocyclonic updraft that can still withstand dilution and efficient in vortex ingestion, tilting, and stretching.

4. Dynamical Evolution

In this last section, we examined PV and to diagnose the dynamics entailed to the tornado occurrence along the area of interest. Provided in Figures 53 to 54 are the vertical cross sections (VCS) along the zonal axis from the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL products. Additionally, we looked at the potential 'ignition source' of the tornadic mini-supercell through the lens of emanated and ducted gravity waves within the environment.

The cross-sectional location is chosen because it is near the onset of tornado occurrence. Hence, along the zonal direction where the inverted trough is also in place moving along the east-west direction. Additionally, we define a PV tower/core as a vertically aligned high-PV (≥ 1 PVU) region above a surface cyclone as in Rossa et al. (2000) and Wang and Rogers (2001).

When there is a big difference in the water vapor amount or potential temperature between two levels, convection can easily occur due to the instability in place brought by the mesoscale and synoptic condition. In the lower levels, a downwelling segment in the θ gradient (or isentropes) signature grew as seen by 03 UTC.

Figure 53

ERA5 VCS Profile of the Baroclinic Potential Vorticity (PV; contour filled) and Potential Temperature (θ ; dashed contour lines) along the Zonal Direction from (a) 00 UTC, (b) 03 UTC, (c) 06 UTC, (d) 09 UTC 14 Aug 2016, respectively. The Dashed Straight Line represents the Coordinates of the Tornado Occurrence at 120.98 E. Pressure Profile is set up to 500-hPa.

The near-surface warm isentropes further expanded by $\sim 1^\circ$ in easterly zonal direction and greater as it clocked at 06 UTC.

That being said, by taking half of the VCS profile, a more PV- θ signature in the tornadic initiation vicinity was seen with clarity. Shown in Figures 53a and 53b in ERA5 Re solution, the lower troposphere was considerably unstable at both 00 UTC and 03 UTC as discussed above. Near-surface AGL, isentropes became steeper as an occurring warm surface anomaly, while the PV anomaly associated with PV tower in

the background is growing and allowing moist air parcels to ascend vertically. Thus, representative that convective instability is also building within the area of tornadic environment.

At 06 UTC (Figure 53c), the extended patch of warm isentrope anomaly accompanied by a low-level PV tower of ~ 1.3 PVU is evident in the tornadic initiation area. Beneath 800-hPa, convection is possible in the area due to increasing vertical motions causing instability further supported by the overall moist environment as discussed in previous sections, just before the tornado occurred. This is also being rectified by the PV anomaly that stretches and extends from 800-hPa down to the 1000-hPa standard pressure. Along the unstable isentropic layer, the PV tower injects cyclonic circulation and vorticity in the inverted trough, which in turn provided a favorable thermo-kinematic environment for tornado to occur.

With the similar PV formulation, the NCEP FNL also had a few points of similarities, but differ otherwise. Shown in Figure 54a on the morning of the same date, signs of destabilization within the thermal gradient was already seen implying convection may occur along the surface cyclone. By 03 UTC (Figure 54b), the environment is conditionally unstable due to the steepening of low-level isentropes on the atmospheric column allowing convection to materialize. Between near-surface AGL and 700-hPa, a PV core was seen in development stage with positive PV contour.

Continuing to 06 UTC (Figure 54c), the PV core along the *entrance* sector of the surface cyclone matures to ~ 1.1 PVU. However, the PV anomaly did not extend completely towards near ground but instead manifested as 'weak PV dampening' from

Figure 54

NCEP FNL VCS of the Baroclinic Potential Vorticity (PV; contour filled) and Potential Temperature (Theta E; dashed contour lines) along the Zonal Direction from (a) 00 UTC, (b) 03 UTC, (c) 06 UTC, (d) 09 UTC 14 Aug 2016, respectively. The Dashed Straight Line represents the Coordinates of the Tornado Occurrence at 120.98 E. Pressure Profile is set up to 500-hPa.

the lower-troposphere to near-surface AGL (≥ 100 m). The ample low-level PV were also carried towards the 09 UTC (Figure 54d); the post-tornadic environment. Furthermore, near-surface isentropes decrease with height along the vicinity of the tornado occurrence, a sign of warm surface anomaly further promoting initiation of deep convection. Although the PV anomaly is not quite as high as in ERA5 Re, it can still provide the suitable conditions for tornadogenesis.

Across all of the model data being analyzed, warm surface θ starting at 300 K is being shown with a similar feature evident. Towards the east direction; located at the EPAC, a semi-curve streak of PV column is seen. The center of this anomaly is located around the middle troposphere (or mid-levels). From both solutions, the midlevel PV column can be seen as high as $\sim 1.1-1.2$ PVU with the NCEP FNL having a well-defined boundary from the negative PV, though gradually weakened over time.

Overall, relatively-large PV in between 800-hPa and standard pressure layer corresponds to the lower-tropospheric part of PV tower/core as depicted. Čampa and Wernli (2012) attributed the large positive PV to adiabatic process. The classic PV dynamics predicts that diabatic heating in the middle atmosphere would result in a PV dipole with negative/lower PV anomalies aloft and positive/high PV anomalies below (Hoskins & James, 2014). Near-surface AGL, positive PV anomalies near the surface are associated with warm surface temperature anomalies (Hoskins et al., 1985). This clearly was observed in Figure 51 and 52 cases: namely, that near the surface large values of PV were associated with downwelling warm isentropes.

Furthermore, the potential ignition/energy source was also investigated using the same instruments leading to the generation of gravity waves that can influence and interact the mesocyclogenesis process and its ensuing tornadogenesis. With that, we analyzed the 850-hPa chart with the ducting function (DF) and geostrophic and non-geostrophic winds. In general, concentrated areas of positive DF values represent regions of strong ducting. Apparently, no minimum positive value of DF has been established as a lower threshold. Koch and Saleeby (2001) suggest that a DF of 10

to 15 is enough for strong ducting. However, gravity waves have been shown to occur in DF environments of 5 to 10 (e.g., Gaffin, 1999).

As a bit of refresher, gravity waves tend to form around strong convective systems disturbing the atmosphere. But synoptically and dynamically, even at the absence of convection, gravity waves also tend to form through the aid of highly diffluent non-geostrophic flow rounding the base of a trough i.e. midlatitude intense trough with a negatively-tilted axis (Koch and Saleeby, 2001). The formation of these mesoscale gravity waves initiates at the exit region of the jet streak (Uccellini and Koch, 1987). To keep these gravity waves and its associated energy to be in place, a low-level stable layer is required to keep its energy from dissipating upward and propagates further through ducting (Schaub, 2005) measured through the ducting factor of Koch and O'Handley (1997).

In the ERA5 Re solution shown Figure 55, at 00 UTC, strong ducting is mostly located at the Central Luzon measured at ~13 units while geostrophic winds at the PBL rounding the inverted pressure perturbation. At Metro Manila downstream the low-level inverted trough, the DF values are ~10 units indicative of strong ducting allowing potential gravity waves to form and propagate.

By 03 UTC through 06 UTC, the core of the ducting factor situated in western portion of Central Luzon advected towards the north and became muted across the landmass. DF in NCR reduced to ~8 units though still capable of low-level ducting for gravity wave propagation. Geostrophic winds ramped up to 20 to 30 kts as the height contours constricted and 70 kts further downstream of the inverted trough.

Figure 55

ERA5 Re Dynamic Maps involving 850-hPa Isohypsers (blue solid lines; dam), 850-hPa observed, geostrophic, and ageostrophic wind components (black, red, and green wind barbs respectively; kt), and Duct Factor (contour filled; dim) from (a) 00 UTC, (b) 03 UTC, (c) 06 UTC, (d) 09 UTC 14 Aug 2016, respectively.

By 09 UTC, another round of strong ducting is on its way entrenched at the same place as previous ducting core at Central Luzon. There is also an 850-hPa low that possibly formed and stacked atop of the small yet large values of duct factor in Luzon landmass as seen with the light geostrophic winds of ~5 to 15 kts encircling. As

Figure 56

NCEP FNL Dynamic Maps involving 850-hPa Isohypsers (blue solid lines; dam), 850-hPa observed, geostrophic, and ageostrophic wind components (black, red, and green wind barbs respectively; kt), and Duct Factor (contour filled; dim) from (a) 00 UTC, (b) 03 UTC, (c) 06 UTC, (d) 09 UTC 14 Aug 2016, respectively.

height falls in Metro Manila, the DF number increased to 10 units once more suggesting strong ducting for gravity waves to form and propagate for long distances.

Meanwhile, the NCEP FNL solution lags considerably to the previous model as depicted in Figure 56. Across the entire timeframe (from 00 UTC to 09 UTC even up to 12 UTC), the DF in the entire Luzon landmass remained weak with values <5 units;

the minimum threshold for gravity waves to occur as found out by Gaffin (1999). This suggests that despite the presence non-geostrophic flow around the inverted trough, these mesoscale waves can quickly dissipate due to non-existent stratification in the low-levels which is required to impede the vertical leakage of the wave energy.

To support the DF environments from ERA5 Re and before the tornadic supercell initiated, we simply computed for the DF accompanied in the Tanay RAOB starting at 00 UTC; the pre-convective environment. By that time, the DF is at 12 units supporting gravity wave ducting and propagation due to a low-level moist stable layer spanning to nearly 850-hPa with substantial instability aloft. The RAOB profile that time as discussed earlier in Section 3, also featured a mid-level warm temperature nose/inversion and another stable layer from ~6 to ~8 km of the column that can have a role on the limiting the leakage of the energy associated with the ducted wave, aside from convection-induced gravity waves.

These potential ducted gravity waves then contributed on the intensification of these TSTMs to attain meso/misocyclonic environment especially at the presence of large vertical shear within the low-levels caused by veering winds (Lalas and Einaudi, 1976, Ferretti et al. 1988). This wind shear produces horizontal vorticity which can be tilted into vertical associated with the base of the updraft column, and convergence that promotes positive stretching; hence a net increase in the mesocyclone vorticity. The strengthening of the severe TSTM's mesocyclone upon interaction with a gravity wave may lead to tornadogenesis in some situations as examined by Coleman and Knupp (2008) and speculated ahead of time (e.g. Miller & Sanders 1980).

CHAPTER V**SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS**

This chapter discusses the complete summary, conclusions, and recommendations of the researchers concerning the presented data.

Summary of Findings

In this section, we completely summarized the analyzed data and information regarding the HCW event that occurred in the afternoon of 14th of August 2016. Accordingly, we divided this section into four parts inline to the Chapter 4 discussion; (1) The case description of the tornadic event, (2) the synoptic and (3) mesoscale storm environment, (4) the dynamical evolution of the atmospheric setting and (5) lastly, summary of atmospheric conditions leading up to the Manila Tornado initiation.

1. Case Description of Tornadic Episode

Following PAGASA's HRW No. 19, TSTMs may form under favorable conditions due to the SWM affecting and bringing heavy rains across the capital. 15 mins to 20 mins past 08 UTC, satellite imagery; supplemented by radar images from the nearest station, shows a small TSTM with OTT along the anvil layer plowed over Metro Manila. Underneath, a possible hook echo is also depicted which is the staple of tornado formation.

The TSTM thrived under a moist environment as depicted from ground-relative observations from the nearest AWS at Bluementritt and Tayuman area. With diurnal maximum convective heating in place at the early afternoon, parcels of air can proliferate under high T and T_D , especially with ground T_v reaching a staggering ~ 36

°C. This is further supported with air parcels attaining more moisture and becoming more buoyant in the early afternoon as the RH% decreases on the other hand. It also shows a gradual deepening of the pressure profile causing perturbation all the way towards the DCI by 08 UTC.

As the TSTM intensified, the meteogram readings of T , T_D , T_v , and moisture profile dropped by 0830 UTC indicative of TSTM starting to affect the Metropolis, particularly Manila City. Along the area, rainfall within the aforementioned stations reveal a spike to 3 to 7 mm inline with the decreasing thermo-surface data. A short yet sharp pressure perturbation was also read out by one of the stations at around 0845 UTC, likely due to the tornadic wind field being close.

As indicated earlier, the TSTM started to affect Manila City by 0830 UTC with the convective storm forming a tornado under its base evident as a debris ball and its weak echo hole in the radar scan. The tornadic event initially started at the Baseco Beach then crossed along compound dealing structural damages for a minute. Shortly after, it then affected the Port Area, Manila where it struck Philippine Red Cross then coursed along the Fort Bonifacio lasting 6 mins. It then reached Carriedo-Quaipo Area 3 mins. after where it afflicted vendors and stores.

While moving due NE and crossing the LRT line 2, the tornadic circulation targeted Sampaloc Area, particularly near BPI Bustillos and in Brgy. 435 Zone 44 in succession, nearly 15 mins. after its initiation and 3 mins after it struck Quiapo, Manila City. It further inflicted damages within G. Tuazon St, Sampaloc, Manila City and

adgacencies by 0850 UTC wherein notably, the 7/11 convenience store took damages so as to other houses and establishments alike and nearby.

The tornadic event lasted for about 30 mins. which was last seen at its final 'rope stage' in New Manila, Quezon City as captured by one Netizen at Madison 101 Tower and the funnel cloud likely got cut off in Gilmore Ave a minute after. It tracked nearly 9 km. due NE at an average ground speed of 4.92 m/s. It impacted more than 10 Brgys. and 100 houses along the way while two people sustained minor injuries of finger laceration.

2. Synoptic Environment

The synoptic setting of the Manila Tornado and its associated TSTM developed under ideal conditions. Initially at 00 UTC, an UL HPA was depicted which moved away from the landmass by 06 UTC from model guidance. The anticyclone features light winds within Luzon 5 to 10 kts exhibiting divergent property. At the surface, MSLP contours along the Philippines highlighted a subtle surface troughing.

Parsed from the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL solutions, we further diagnosed the synoptic condition at several layers; 500-, 700-, and 850-hPa, as well as near-surface AGL. A strong westerly streak is depicted crossing the country in the mid-levels, while a deep-low is centered along the SCS. A swath of vorticity from the 500-hPa low was transported out by the westerly winds, especially along Northern Luzon, before re-intensifying along open WPAC

The 700-hPa pressure level or otherwise known as the 'steering level' from both models was indicative of monsoonal rains along the western section of Luzon,

including Metro Manila. This suggests that convective activity was also placed on the aforementioned area due to increased vertical ascent motion. This is further exacerbated with the NCEP FNL model even hinting a subtle signal of 700-hPa trough which can amplify DCI and convective parcel motion. The LPA in the SCS, as seen with the encircling contour lines, benefited from the moist and transitioning SW to westerly winds hinting some intensification along the way.

The 850-hPa level or also called as the PBL from both models are more inline to one another. Isohypes became more concentrated along the LPA in the SCS and so as more distinct at depicting the inverted trough in the Philippines. Additionally, moisture advection was also possible due to the briskly-moving and warm SW winds equatorial flow acting as the LLJ. The warm moist 850-hPa air responded to the perturbation perpendicular to the PBL isotherm contour within western coast of Luzon to PBL.

Near-surface AGL, the pressure perturbation became more distinct across the two platforms with the NCEP FNL depicting a highly curved surface trough overlaying a vertical gradient along the western section of Luzon landmass. This further supports that low-level WAA is possible with the aid of the enhanced SWM and westerly winds aloft. The wind profile then carries the moisture-relevant ingredients towards the landmass allowing DCI and latent heat to be released once convection starts.

Coupled unstable lower-atmosphere in place, an area of convergence zone is also depicted and stalled at the Luzon landmass inducing upward motion overlaying the surface trough and the negative ω signature in the steering layer. An upward

motion of air parcels promotes convection process especially with the simulated wind profile and surface trough in place. With a (South)West-to-Westerly wind profile, the trough sectors probably have also flipped over as the *entrance* sector is located at the western coast while exit gate along the Luzon landmass. An ascent *entrance* corridor in the western flank can exhibit DCI, so as a HCW such as a TSTM activity.

3. Mesoscale Environment

The observed mesoscale environment as depicted from the RAOB launched in Tanay Station. At 00 UTC, the sounding shows a large instability brewing near the area of interest. Despite the weak LR_s, this is due to the undiluted total CAPE of around 1600 to 2150 J kg⁻¹, with relatively no capping layer, while the ML-parcel managed to draw a modest 1200 to 1600 J kg⁻¹ along a small inhibition. With an ECAPE of 1500 J kg⁻¹, potential TSTMs may draw out nearly 70% of its environmental buoyancy making the TSTMs' convective updraft plume less susceptible to updraft entrainment caused by the moist and veering profile.

In conjunction to the veering profile, the kinematic background is also conducive for long-lived TSTMs as seen in the hodograph with sickle-shaped veering winds which can be indicative of WAA. At the low-levels, a 30 kts vertical shear is observed along a 26 kts of DLS allowing TSTMs to achieve mesocyclonic rotation and in succession, providing ample vorticity. With 17 to 20 kts of storm inflow, SRH across 2 layers; 1 km and 3 km AGL, to achieve large values around 170 to 190 m² s⁻² and 190 to 210 m² s⁻², respectively, making potential TSTMs with supercellular nature and tornadogenesis possible. Within the SRH parameter itself, the environment was also

rich in streamwise vorticity that can/will be ingested by a proliferating TSTM as ζ_{SWM} near-ground clocked at 0.03 s^{-1} and streamwiseness reaching as high as 85% in the first 500 m.

Standard composite indices were also inline to the potential severe TSTM with KI of $39.20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, SWI of -1.10 to $-3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and LI of -2 to -4 allowing warm moist air parcel to take advantage of the vertical environment due to the temperature differences. A SWEAT Index of 310 to 370 units can also mean a potential HCW to materialize due to the modest MLS of 25 kts, while having a multicellular storm mode. Both $EHI_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $EHI_{0-3\text{km}}$ also showed a strong possibility for a supercellular induced tornado due to the high CAPE and SRH environment with 2 to 2.5 units and 2 to 3 units, respectively, being recorded across the board. SCP and STP at that time clocked at 5 to 6 units and a tight range of 1.1 to 1.2 units supporting the notion for the chances of an HCW such as tornadoes to form.

By 12 UTC, the thermo-kinematic environment remains unstable. A Skew-T analysis depicts a relatively moist profile, accompanied by steep low-level LRs. The undiluted buoyancy reaches to around 1750 to 2550 J kg^{-1} , still with relatively no capping layer, while MLCAPE values having a larger spread between at 470 to 1750 J kg^{-1} along a small inhibition. With an ECAPE ranging from 1500 to 1800 J kg^{-1} , potential TSTMs may realize nearly 70% of its available CAPE making vigorous updrafts within TSTMs' still due to the moist and veering profile, making it less-susceptible to environmental-dilution from entrainment.

The kinematic background remains conducive for long-lived TSTMs as seen in the hodograph with sickle-shaped veering profile hinting low-level moisture advection. In the first 1 km AGL, large vertical shear of 27 kts is observed, however the DLS have dropped to 16 kts. With low-level shear available, ingestion of ample vorticity can be stretched via buoyancy perturbations and provide the mesocyclonic rotation. With 17 to 23 kts of SRW within the first 3 km AGL and convective storms propagating potentially towards the Bunkers LM, SRH across 2 layers; 1 km and 3 km AGL, attained large values around 150 to 200 $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$ and 220 to 230 $\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$, respectively, making potential TSTMs with supercellular nature and tornadogenesis possible. Within the SRH parameter itself, the environment remains very rich in streamwise vorticity that can/will be ingested by a potential TSTM as ζ_{SWM} near-ground clocked at 0.027 s^{-1} and streamwiseness reaching as high as 88% in the first 500 m.

Despite decreasing than the previous morning sounding, standard composite indices were also still inline for a possibility of severe TSTM with KI of 36.10 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, SWI of -1 to -2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and LI of -4.5 to -6 allowing warm moist air parcel to take advantage of the vertical environment due to the temperature differences. A SWEAT Index of 304 to 305 units was located at the lower-end of the spectrum but still indicative of a potential HCW to materialize due to the modest MLS of 25 kts, though having a more pulse type of convective storm due to high BRN values. Both $\text{EHI}_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $\text{EHI}_{0-3\text{km}}$ also showed a strong possibility for tornado development due to the high CAPE and SRH environment with 2 to 3 units and 3 to 4 units, respectively, being recorded. SCP

and STP at that time clocked at 7 and 1.5 units, respectively, further supporting the notion for the chances of an HCW, such as supercell-induced tornadoes.

Supplementing the RAOBs are with the mesoscale sectors/maps created and provided from the solutions utilized; ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL. In the ERA5 solution, low CAPE with high CIN was depicted while the NCEP FNL diverged by having 1000 J kg^{-1} with no CIN. Across the selections, the bulk of large buoyancy values are located at the open waters in WPS. For ERA5 Re, large CAPE contours overlay the Northern Luzon coinciding the exit sector of the inverted trough. On the flipped side, the NCEP FNL had a large CAPE hatched at the Central Luzon.

Looking at the BRN Shear as part of the BRN index, the ERA5 Re pulls ahead with a strong area of mean vertical shear near Manila City and the area of tornadic initiation. While CAPE remains meager across the Luzon landmass, vertical shear is quite ample across the board. Meanwhile, the NCEP FNL have a different take with CAPE contributing much than the mean vertical shear. This points that the ERA5 Re may have depicted a low CAPE, high shear setup, while the NCEP FNL having a High CAPE, low shear environment.

Temperature differences were also analyzed and visualized across the two solutions utilized. Both ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL were neck-to-neck to one another due to the 1 °C, with the ERA5 Re managed to have a KI of 38 °C while the NCEP FNL had 37 °C. On the TT index, ERA5 Re registered 44 °C, while the NCEP FNL also a degree lesser at 43 °C. Both models showcased a modest and potential instability especially in the low-levels, which can in turn fuel for a severe weather. This

is supported by the SWEAT parameter across the board were values in the target reaching ≥ 300 units suggesting sufficient low-level moisture, including transport, fueling the instability to build up.

The kinematic environment from both models were also inspected by computing various kinematics parameters. In this case, the SRH and SWH parameter, including the magnitude of streamwise vorticity is evaluated to determine whether the environment is tornadogenic. Starting of, both solutions depicted that storms can propagate along the Bunkers RM or along the environmental mean wind. Based of mean wind, the SRH values in Manila City were below $\geq 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ across the two layers. However, SWH in the area of interest were modest at $\sim 0.02 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ containing ample vorticity magnitude (ζ_{SWM}) of 0.01 s^{-1} . This provides the ingredients that allows potential convective storms to intake the sufficient vorticity making it long-lived and tornadogenic.

Since both solutions have different takes on the mesoscale environment associated with the Manila Tornado event, we further analyzed the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL analyzed by parsing the environmental data directly on the Manila coordinates. In this way, a point vertical sounding is generated to evaluate the thermo-kinematic environment of the case.

Within the ERA5 Re vertical profile, a very unstable environment is depicted across all 13 soundings with undiluted thermodynamics reaching ~ 2000 to 3000 J kg^{-1} sustained over the span of 12 hours. The moist low-level thermodynamic profile along the relatively small curved hodograph allowed potential convective storms to be

resistant to updraft entrainment with fractional entrainment in the high 70s as contributed by high ECAPE measurements. This also in turn allowed potential storms to tap and realize large available buoyancy in place making updraft base wide to capture storm inflow and vorticity.

Speaking of hodograph, the kinematic environment also supports the severe weather environment that materializes and eventually took place. Hodographs produced a curved wind profile suggestive of large SRH values in the first 1 km and 3 km AGL. Upon kinematic analysis, SRH while propagating along the RM component of Bunkers ID produced measurements that are nearly $\geq 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ in the 1 km AGL and $\geq 150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ in the 3 km AGL. This is due and contributed by the available ample vertical shear of 20 kts in the low- and mid-levels and storm-relative inflow to be ingested, while DLS cumulatively ranging between 15 to 25 kts to induce updraft column rotation.

Meanwhile, the NCEP FNL depicts a relatively different environment with a small inverted-V profile suggesting steep low-level LRs. The overall thermodynamic profile remains moist nonetheless with high undiluted CAPE of nearly 2000 to 3000 J kg^{-1} indicative of very unstable atmosphere in place, with the exception of 12 UTC NCEP FNL sounding. Potential TSTMs on this kind environment were still efficient, though lesser than the previous solution. In this case, storms can realize around 70% of the undiluted buoyancy due to the high ECAPE relative to total CAPE as backed by the moist and kinematic profile.

On the kinematic environment associated with the NCEP FNL soundings, hodographs still depicted a semi-curved veering profile, though in a lesser degree than the ERA5 Re solution. SRH values across the two layers being used; 1 km and 3 km layer, were shallow due to the storm inflow lacking at ≤ 20 kts in all times. Despite the ample low-level bulk shear, the deficient storm-relative winds took a toll to the SRH parameters with values $\leq 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$. The DLS within the soundings are also weak with recordings as low as 10 kts which was not enough to make the TSTM rotate as a mesocyclone. This makes the potential for TSTMs capable of producing a tornado slim at chance.

Lastly, we benchmarked the soundings cumulatively to determine how 'severe' the Manila Tornado's environment. This is was constructed using the available baseline designed in the Tornado Alley in the U.S. Great Plains based of supercell storms capable of producing tornadoes as initially conducted by several authors (Rasmussen & Blanchard, 1998; Rasmussen, 2003; Thompson et al., 2003; Thompson et al., 2012).

With the RAOBs from Tanay Station at 00 and 12 UTC, the sounding profiles were relatively comparable to the undiluted buoyancy with different parcel methods derived from the U.S. soundings. The computed SRH values were also in the distribution's bounds for soundings associated with tornadic supercells, with the $\text{SRH}_{0-1\text{km}}$ measurements above the median and the $\text{SRH}_{0-3\text{km}}$ below the baseline's median. Further testing was applied on the CAPE-SRH combination; EHI composite parameter. In this case, our EHI values, including with the MLCAPE, were located well

within the climatological baseline suitable for tornadic supercells and severe weather environs alike.

Additional matching of the sounding profiles coming from Tanay reveals a potent atmosphere as the bulk shear magnitude in the first 1 km and 6 km were also located in the Great Plains' normal baseline, as as the depreciated VGP values computed. Both in fixed layers, SCP and STP values at 00 UTC were comparable to the environment for tornadic storms. However, by 12 UTC, the mentioned composite indices were displaced and out of bounds of the distribution as the HCW wined down.

Since we derived and analyzed vertical profiles from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL, we also benchmarked the model solutions compared to the tornadic environment that was captured by the previously-cited proponents and studies that forms the baseline climatologies. In the case of ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL, the CAPE distributions based of the SB and MU-parcel profile were located close to the upper echelon area of baseline i.e. $\geq 50^{\text{th}}$ percentile, while the MLCAPes were lagging behind on most of the intense storms recorded in the Great Plains.

In terms of the kinematics however, increasingly monotonic behavior is depicted as we ascend from 0-1 km to 0-3 km AGL. Both $SRH_{0-1\text{km}}$ and $SRH_{0-3\text{km}}$ were offset against most of the tornadic supercell cases. In the ERA5 Re, half of the $SRH_{0-1\text{km}}$ distribution resides both in and out of the IQR, while the $SRH_{0-3\text{km}}$ distribution exhibits a positive skewed axis with the IQR located below the 25th percentile of the baseline being set. On the other hand, the NCEP FNL profiles lagged completely against nearly the entire baseline climatology.

With the composite index such as EHI, the distributions; particularly the 0-1 km and 0-3 km AGL across the two solutions were comparable to those of the U.S. tornadic baseline. In this case, the baseline climatology was overlaid by the EHI_{0-1km} derived from ERA5 Re, while the EHI_{0-3km} sports at the high end of the distribution due to the high CAPE and SRH situation. The situation drastically changed on the side of the $MLEHI_{0-1km}$ with a similar pattern to the MLCAPE distribution due to the small derived MLCAPE completely offsetting the large 0-1 km AGL SRH measurements and the NCEP FNL fall at the lower end and outlier.

Additional testing from kinematics and composite indices was performed. In particular, the LLS and DLS is further assessed in the ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL profiles alongside SCP_{eff} and STP_{fix} included. Results showed that the cumulative sounding distributions and the derived bulk shear from 0-1 km and 0-6 km AGL decreases monotonically according to height as both solutions lagged to other tornadic supercell profiles when compared. The SCP_{eff} and STP_{fix} computed from the ERA5 Re soundings were able to notch up within the baselines' normals but also at the lower end of the spectrum for soundings associated with supercells capable of producing tornadoes.

We also performed evaluation on the environment by looking at the composite EHI's individual components, specifically the CAPE SRH space. In relation, we constructed a new EHI parameter we called as "Entrained Energy-Helicity Index" ($E_{NT}EHI$) by substituting the standard CAPE with ECAPE to account for the entrainment effects. With the EHI_{0-3km} , most of the sounding profiles were located at

the optimal constraints which can be used to assess between ordinary vs supercell storms, in this case only 3 soundings are not fit to the distinction. On the other hand, the EHI_{0-1km} is more of a utility to discriminate between supercellular TSTMs capable of producing tornadoes or not with the scatter diagram revealed only 1 sounding were out of bounds while 3 profiles were designated in the marginal sector.

The landscape changes when the MLCAPE instead is used in the formulation across the two variants of SRH parameter. Both in the $MLEHI_{0-3km}$ and $MLEHI_{0-1km}$, all of the model profiles fall outside of the optimal line being set while the Tanay RAOBs are still located with $MLEHI \geq 2$ units. In the 0-1 km AGL, some of the vertical profiles extracted from ERA5 Re managed to be included at the 'marginal' 0.7 line due to relatively modest buoyancy $\geq 900 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and high $SRH_{0-1km} \geq 100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$.

We also checked the scatter space of the ENTEHI parameter across the cumulative sounding profiles. Distinctively, the EHI values computed from Tanay soundings were shifted as high as ~ 1 unit as the entrainment effects within the updraft were included. The 10 model profiles were split into half; for ERA5 Re vertical soundings managed to still be within the bounding 1.5 line in the 0-3 km and 0-1 km AGL which can be categorized as supercell profiles with potential for tornadic initiation. Meanwhile, the rest of the NCEP FNL soundings in this case fall short and more inline to the ordinary TSTM class due to the lack of SRW and SRH.

Finally, we analyzed the fractional entrainment space derived from both RAOB and model profiles to assess the environmental-dilution within the HCW, while continuing to compare the Manila Tornado's environment to other severe and intense

HCW. The cumulatively derived CAPE and ECAPE measurements results to an $R^2 \approx 0.93$ or $\tilde{E} \approx 93\%$. Supporting previous cited works (Peters et al., 2019; Peters et al., 2023a), this was indicative that potential TSTMs with supercellular storm modes along the area of interest can realize larger percentage of the undiluted CAPE at the presence of ample wind shear and storm inflow allowing vigorous updrafts.

4. Atmospheric Dynamics

Using ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL gridded data products, we generated cross section diagrams using dynamical tracers such as Baroclinic PV and in its isobaric form.

The large PV spanning the lower-tropospheric layer appears to be associated with growing warm surface temperature anomalies, consistent with the PV dynamics (Hoskins et al., 1985). The large PV region in the lower troposphere is diabatically produced by latent heat release. Our results indicate that the high PV in the lower troposphere is concentrated in the area with warm surface temperature anomalies and with abundant precipitable water (as synoptically depicted). This is strong evidence suggesting an association of large PV values in the lower troposphere with the latent heating process which is the fuel for DCI (Pang & Fu, 2017). The latent heat release typically occurs near the middle troposphere, where the upward vertical motion is the strongest. Recall that the diabatic heating in the middle atmosphere would result in a PV dipole with negative PV anomalies aloft and positive PV anomalies below (Hoskins & James, 2014).

This explains why the high-PV region in the lower troposphere tends to be distinctly separated from the high-PV region in the upper troposphere. Furthermore, the cyclonic circulation around the high-PV anomaly would also strengthen in response to the amplification of the potential temperature perturbation. This increase in winds with respect to height would increase the vertical shear below and near the anomaly and aid in developing an environment conducive for rotating updrafts. Juckes and Smith (2000) asserts that while directly under and near the positive PV tower, it also provides higher undiluted buoyancy increased by up to 83% and decreased CIN. As convective instability builds due to moistening and deforms isentropic surfaces, it causes the downwelling of the signature. Such as that it also causes the tilting of the vortex tubes that lie along the isentropic surface.

The ducting mechanism and generation of gravity wave(s) are also investigated alongside multiple-wind dynamics above PBL that can influence and interact the TSTM initiation, mesocyclogenesis, and its potential tornadogenesis, aside from the classical convergence line or OFB-driven TSTM. While the NCEP FNL lagged considerably in this case, the ERA5 Re solution in particular portrays strong ducting across the entire period with DF values between ~8 to 13 units as height contour falls in Metro Manila. This indicative that a low-level stratification is present with instability aloft. This is supported by the Tanay RAOB at 00 UTC with DF values at ~12 units due to existence of several stable layers in the vertical column preventing wave energy leakage.

This potential ducted-gravity wave then contributed on the explosive development of the deep convective storm associated with the Manila Tornado, especially with the additional help from a modestly wind-sheared environment. The gravity wave interaction can assist and providing boost by allowing the parent TSTM to attain and intensify its developing mesocyclone. This is done through efficiently tilting, ingesting, and stretching of streamwise vorticity, along the storm inflow, up to the mid-levels via significant convergence. Hence, which can lead to tornadogenesis.

5. Summary of Atmospheric Condition

This last section tackles and sums up the environmental condition leading to the initiation and dissipation of the Manila Tornado. 'Time stamps' involved are at 00, 03, 06, 08 to 09, and 12 UTC with 3-hr spacing. A summary table of conditions was depicted in Table 6.

The environment is already prime since the morning at 00 UTC when a quasi-stationary inverted trough; an area of low pressure, is placed in western Luzon coinciding with an UL high for efficient ventilation rendering a 'chimney effect', supported by negative N^2 reading in the nearest sounding area. Tanay RAOB at the same time reveal a moist-stable profile up to 1 km AGL with instability aloft to near EL with undiluted CAPE values between 1750 to 2150 J kg⁻¹. Background kinematics due to the SWM and westerly winds aloft were also supportive of long-lived/prolonged convective activity due to veering wind profiles and its continuous moisture return with SRH across 1 km and 3 km AGL > 150 m² s⁻² and approaching 200 m² s⁻² accompanied by ample and near-pure streamwise vorticity of 0.03 s⁻¹.

Table 6

Atmospheric Conditions in within the Area of Interest. Temporal resolution of 3-hr. Instruments utilized were included.

Time	Condition	Instrument / Method
00 UTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Upper-level High Pressure Area located in Northern Luzon. • Negative N^2 indicative of instability in place. • CAPE values between 1750 to 2150 $J\ kg^{-1}$, can be as high as 3000 $J\ kg^{-1}$ and high fractional entrainment > 70%. • SRH across 1 km and 3 km AGL > 150 $m^2\ s^{-2}$ and approaching 200 $m^2\ s^{-2}$, respectively. Accompanied by ample and near-pure streamwise vorticity magnitude of 0.03 s^{-1}. • Duct Factor (DF) of ~10 units suggestive of potential gravity waves that can magnify TSTM activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JMA Regional Weather Charts • Tanay RAOB at 00 UTC • ERA5 Duct Factor • Model Sounding Profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL • Vertical Cross Sections from ERA5 and NCEP FNL
03 UTC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undiluted CAPE reaching 2650 $J\ kg^{-1}$, fractional entrainment of ~76% allowing stout updraft, and ample low-level instability. • Vertical shear across the entire mid-levels > 20 kts and SRH indices > 100 $m^2\ s^{-2}$ along a highly and ample magnitude of streamwise vorticity at ~0.01 s^{-1}. • Surface cyclone with PV anomaly have reached near the surface layer indicative that it is intensifying and can magnify both the thermodynamics and kinematics in place. • DF in NCR started to become muted. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ERA5 Duct Factor • Model Sounding Profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL • Vertical Cross Sections from ERA5 and NCEP FNL

06 UTC

- DOST-PAGASA has issued a HRW No. 19 in Metro Manila and Greater Metro Manila Area (GMMA) due to continuous precipitation activity.
- UL high pressure had moved towards the West Philippine Sea (WPS) while still inducing divergence aloft.
- An easterly inverted trough centered in western Luzon alongside an active southwesterly wind flow promoting convergence.
- 20 kt westerly winds in the 500-hPa, an area of enhanced vertical velocity pressure and convergence in low-levels at western section of Luzon, continuous WAA i.e. moisture return. Synoptic wind shear is between 30 to 40 kts.
- 3400 J kg⁻¹ of undiluted CAPE and SRH indices approaching and above 100 m² s⁻² across the entire 3 km layer supportive of severe weather initiation due to convective heating and moisture return seen in Manila Observatory's AWS readings.
- Near-surface PV anomaly/tower in the area intensified to ~1.2 PVU increasing the local shear, thermodynamic, and kinematic support.

- DOST-PAGASA HRW No. 19
- JMA Regional Weather Charts
- ERA5 and NCEP FNL Synoptic Charts
- Vertical Cross Sections from ERA5 and NCEP FNL
- Model Sounding Profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL
- AWS Measurements from Manila Observatory

08 to 09 UTC

- Satellite imagery from HIMAWARI-8 at reveal a discrete TSTM with OTT in its anvil layer.
- Reflectivity C-band radar scans shows a *textbook* supercellular structures up to its tornadic initiation by 0830 UTC.

- PAGASA Damage Assessment
- HIMAWARI-8 AHI
- Tagaytay C-band Radar

- Pressure profile decreased to ~1004 hPa until 0830 UTC in the nearest AWS instruments in Manila City.
- Explosive profile consisted of > 3000 J kg⁻¹ of maximum CAPE, shear profile > 20 kts, and SRH indices > 100 and 150 m² s⁻² in the first 1 km and 3 km AGL, respectively.
- Modest and highly streamwise vorticity is also recorded at ~0.01 s⁻¹ at the 1 km layer suitable for tornadic setups.
- The surface cyclone within the inverted trough retained its PV anomaly at ~1.2 PVU and downwelling isentropes indicative of increasing parcel ascent and local instability.

- Model Sounding Profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL
- AWS Measurements from Manila Observatory
- Vertical Cross Sections from ERA5 and NCEP FNL

12 UTC

- CAPE values between 1750 to 2550 J kg⁻¹, curved wind profiles are also in view with LLS at 27 kts contributing to the large SRH indices approaching 200 m² s⁻².
- Ample storm inflow and highly streamwise vorticity magnitudes were also recorded at 0.027 s⁻¹ at the first 500 m.
- Model profiles, especially ERA5, projects ~3000 J kg⁻¹ of undiluted CAPE supporting wide updrafts, background shear profile ramped up to within 25 kts allowing SRH indices to approach 200 m² s⁻² at the 3 km AGL.

- Tanay RAOB at 00 UTC
- Model Sounding Profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL

Vertical profiles from ERA5 and NCEP FNL also support the instability in place, with ERA5 projecting near 3000 J kg⁻¹ and ample SRH in the first 1 km and 3 km AGL. At

the same time, the surface trough and its entailed PV anomaly started at a base 1 PVU with DF values > 10 units that can also support ducted waves which can enhance vorticity and modulate TSTM activity.

By 03 UTC, box soundings from reanalysis datasets, particularly ERA5, continued to portray a volatile environment with undiluted CAPE reaching 2650 J kg^{-1} , fractional entrainment of 76% allowing stout updraft, and ample low-level instability. Kinematics remain supportive of TSTM initiation and activity with vertical shear across the entire mid-levels > 20 kts and SRH indices greater than $100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ along a highly streamwise vorticity of 0.01 s^{-1} . except for the NCEP FNL soundings. This is attributed to the intensifying surface cyclone with PV anomaly have reached near the surface layer which can magnify both the thermodynamics and kinematics in place. The DF core however moved towards the north inhibiting potential gravity waves to propagate for distances and essentially, lose its piece of energy.

At 05 UTC, DOST-PAGASA issued a HRW No. 19 in Metro Manila and Greater Metro Manila Area (GMMA) due to continuous precipitation activity. By 06 UTC, an hour after, upper-level charts suggest that the UL high pressure had moved towards the West Philippine Sea (WPS) still inducing divergence aloft. At the surface, regional charts from JMA reveal an easterly trough centered in western Luzon alongside southwesterly wind flow. ERA5 and NCEP FNL synoptic charts have ramped up their depiction of the pre-severe weather environment with 20 kt westerly winds in the 500-hPa, an area of enhanced vertical velocity pressure and convergence in low-levels at western section of Luzon, continuous WAA i.e. moisture return. Due to diurnal surface

heating as recorded by the AWS' handled by Manila Observatory and moisture return as discussed and depicted due to SWM and westerly winds aloft, box sounding, from ERA5 primarily, reveal an excessive $\sim 3400 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ with SRH indices approaching and above $100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ across the entire 3 km layer due to the curved/hook-shaped hodographs (ample directional and speed shear) supportive of severe weather initiation. Although the DF values in Metro Manila have become muted, the near-surface PV anomaly/tower in the area intensified to $\sim 1.2 \text{ PVU}$ increasing the local shear, thermodynamics, and kinematics within the area of interest for such activity.

By 08 UTC towards 09 UTC, the state bureau has issued a TSTM warning in Manila due to the HCW initiation. Satellite imagery from HIMAWARI-8 at 0820 UTC reveal a discrete TSTM with OTT in its anvil layer, while reflectivity radar scans by the Tagaytay C-band Radar reveal *textbook* supercellular structures up to its tornadic initiation by 0830 UTC. AWS readings from the nearest stations in Manila reveal that air parcels have tapped on the primed environment for tornadic mini-supercell to initiate along the area of interest as pressure profile decreased to $\sim 1004 \text{ hPa}$ from its base state until 0830 UTC. As a tornado carves its $\sim 9 \text{ km}$ damage path in Manila City, box soundings, primarily from ERA5 at 08 and 09 UTC, reveal an explosive profile consisted of $> 3000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ of maximum CAPE, shear profile $> 20 \text{ kts}$, and SRH indices > 100 and $150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ in the first 1 km and 3 km AGL, respectively. Modest and highly streamwise vorticity is also recorded at $\sim 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the 1 km layer suitable for tornadic setups. The VCS of the dynamic environment showed that the surface cyclone

retained its PV anomaly at ~ 1.2 PVU and downwelling isentropes indicative of magnifying parcel ascent and instability.

Finally, by 12 UTC, the RAOB from Tanay station reveal that the post-tornadic situation remains very volatile with CAPE values between 1750 to 2550 J kg⁻¹, curved wind profiles are also in view with LLS at 27 kts contributing to the large SRH indices approaching 200 m² s⁻². Ample storm inflow and highly streamwise vorticity magnitudes were also recorded at 0.027 s⁻¹ at the first 500 m. Due to supportive kinematics still in place, proliferating TSTMs, especially at nocturnal/evening hours, can withstand entrainment effects causing dilution to the updraft core/column. Supporting the observed sounding, the model vertical profiles, especially ERA5, was indicative of explosive environment suitable for tornadic supercell activity to initiate and proliferate. Nearly ~ 3000 J kg⁻¹ worth of undiluted CAPE supporting wide updrafts, background shear profile ramped up to within 25 kts allowing SRH indices to approach 200 m² s⁻² at the 3 km layer, thus results to composite indices to point out another round of severe weather activity.

Therefore, the entire atmosphere from 00 to 12 UTC clearly supports severe weather setups to initiate. The mechanisms are a combination of surface PV anomaly over the Metropolis and overall vertical profile i.e. thermodynamics and kinematics, support provided the ingredients for a tornadic supercell in the afternoon to form. Figure 57 displays the combination of these mechanisms at a dynamical interplay.

Figure 57

Schematic Diagram of Manila Tornado formation. The Black Lines are Streamwise Vortex Lines, with the sense of rotation indicated by Brown Circular Arrows and Cyclonic (+) and Anticyclonic (-) signs. The Red Line represents 1.2 PVU associated with a Surface Cyclone, the orange and purple arrows represent buoyant flow underneath the Tornadic Mini-supercell. Idealized Veering Winds is presented.

Conclusion

This account presents a thorough case description, damage distribution, and storm environment of the tornado event that occurred in Manila City, NCR, Philippines, during 0830–0900 UTC (0430-0500 PM PhST) 14th of August 2016. An extensive investigation on the tornadic environment; both synoptic and mesoscale, including the atmospheric dynamics, was carried out to understand the cause of DCI and its HCW.

Causing damages to various establishments and minor injuries on its 9 km long wake, the tornadic event earned an EF1 rating across the board. The DCI occurred along Manila City as warm moist surface winds coming from the southwest benefited from the convective heating that took place in the peak noon as seen from the nearest *in situ* measurements.

Synoptically, the environment was composed of a quasi-stationary surface trough allowing increased ascent and convergence within the *entrance* region, while upper-level divergence providing ventilation. Satellite imagery at 0820 UTC revealed a discrete TSTM near the Manila Bay accompanied by presumably a small hook signature in the Radar imagery from PAGASA. The maturing phase of the updraft was accompanied by the increase of the lightning activity. In the mesoscale, the convective setup was already prime for DCI and subsequent severe event with undiluted CAPE reaching between 1600-2500 J kg⁻¹ making up the volatile atmosphere throughout the day. The parent storm was also efficient in utilizing the background buoyancy in place with fractional entrainment reaching 70-80% making it stout to entrainment due to the supporting moist and kinematic conditions. Background kinematics revealed that the monsoonal flow created a modest vertical shear with DLS of 26 kts and 16 kts as computed from the 00 and 12 UTC RAOBs, respectively, that can allow some meso/misocyclonic rotation. A clockwise-turning low-level shear provided a moisture transport in the area and substantial SRH reaching >180 m² s⁻² in the first 1 km and >200 m² s⁻² in the 3 km AGL. The low-level storm environment was also rich in streamwise vorticity with magnitudes reaching 0.03 s⁻¹ and streamwiseness of ≥80%

to be ingested by tornadic TSTM and stretched by the ample buoyancy worth $>200 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ of $\text{CAPE}_{0-3\text{km}}$ across the soundings, making the formation of a tornadic storm quite favorable.

Sounding profiles from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL also support the thermo-kinematic environment associated with the Manila Tornado with substantial buoyancy reaching as high as $\sim 3000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$ and sufficient SRH of $100 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ for 1 km AGL and $150 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}$ for the 3 km AGL. Most of the thermo-kinematic indices associated within the RAOBs from Tanay and the two solutions, especially ERA5 Re, for this case was within the baseline distribution of the U.S. climatology of tornadic supercell setups making it comparable to those of the aforementioned severe and unstable conditions. The substantial CAPE measurements ($\geq 2000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}$) and shear-related indices is brought by the surface trough and its associated dynamic atmospheric column. Specifically, a PV tower (1 PVU) spanning in the lower-tropospheric region was depicted situated along the gradient deficit near the tornadic initiation. The deepening process of the low-level PV tower and stretching of in this case contributed to the large instability in the region, enhancing both thermodynamic and kinematic conditions. Thus, setting the stage for HCW. Although we did not perform any substantial statistics and its more of an assumption at this point, we therefore reject the included hypothesis that the environment was stable inhibiting convective and its tornadic activity based of the environmental setup and derived measurements. More importantly, we concluded that the severe TSTM that affected Manila City starting at 08 UTC which led to tornadogenesis 30 mins. after and lasted for another 30 mins. ended in New Manila,

Quezon City, either have supercellular features or is a narrow/mini supercell TSTM due to overall favorable conditions for such DCI and HCW.

Recommendations

Although tornadoes are a rare weather phenomenon in the Philippines, they are nonetheless a significant threat to human life and property when they occur such as this Manila Tornado being studied, especially given the level of economic development and the recent increase in population in tornado-prone areas. In general, what we recommend to our readers, especially local ones, is to conduct more case studies regarding mesoscale events i.e. severe TSTM, tornadoes, hails etc.

Additionally, despite all of these analyses in this paper, our conclusion regarding this event i.e. characteristics of the storm remains loose. Photographic analysis of the tornadic event showed that:

1. Funnel cloud was connected to cumulus/cumulonimbus base as observed; and
2. The vortex tube probably developed at the southern edge of the cb tower.

Wakimoto and Wilson (1989) and Brady and Szoke (1989) proposed that convergence line can also explain non-mesocyclonic (non-supercell) tornadoes on the flipped side. The LLJ observed and the associated vertical shear and substantial streamwise vorticity, even at the absence of proper SRW, is a feature compatible both with non-supercell and mini-supercell characteristics of the storms. The intensities of the tornadoes, in case they were of non-supercell origin, would be perfectly in line with Dotzek et al. (2005) who determined that global distribution of tornado intensities is

bimodal, in which up to about F2 (or EF2) intensity, the non-mesocyclonic events are more likely.

We recommend additional work and analyses, particularly radar analysis, of this event to rectify the results we gathered, assuming that we can actually request to attain the radar data and which we did not performed. A number of features from the future radar analysis might suggest the mini-supercell character of some of the convective structures observed. Alberoni et al. (2000) performed a dual Doppler analysis to analyse the environment of supercell storms in the Po Valley. As meteorological tools improved, Magsig (2008) discussed techniques for diagnosing radar-based storm attributes and integrating environmental information into the warning decision-making process. More recently, Smith et al. (2015) conducted a thorough investigation by using WSR-88D radar from NEXRAD network to assess convective storm modes and near-storm environmental data that provided a baseline for conditional probability of tornado intensity.

We also made use of the newly-developed diagnostic ECAPE parameter and meld within the composite EHI of Hart and Korotky (1991) to get a better grasp of the severe weather environment we referred to as *Entrained Energy-Helicity Index* or $E_{NT}EHI$. We believed that by substituting the ECAPE on the composite equation may yield better storm diagnostic skill. This actually makes sense since the analytic equation for ECAPE involves by taking into account the storm inflow usually in the first 1 km AGL via Bunker's ID and potential buoyancy dilution, while SRH is the integral of storm-relative winds also from Bunker's ID and the magnitude of streamwise

vorticity, with better discriminating skills in the 1 km AGL than the frequently-used 3 km AGL. Nearly undiluted updraft cores may also be efficient in ingesting helical inflow along the ample SRW, especially under dynamic forcing. When using the effective inflow layer (EIL), the magnitude of SRW modulates the transition of convective storm mode from non-supercellular to supercellular. If the EIL SRW contains large vorticity then it results to a strong low-level net rotation supporting the current understanding of tornadogenesis and one of the leading theories involving streamwise vorticity.

Lastly, as an author's note, we indicate and motivate researchers and amateur meteorologists around the country to conduct convection, TSTM, HCW, and tornadic research regardless of its frequency, especially with the dawn of reanalysis datasets e.g. ERA5 Re. The need for a TSTM- and HCW-focused studies (hail, tornadic event, etc.) and most importantly, a proper baseline climatology for severe weather based of 'proximity' soundings or of model profiles, is to support certain aspects of operational TSTM forecasting. Although, proximity soundings are also not yet available due to the limited number of balloon launching sites; of 13 sites, only 8 are online via UWyo, which needs expansion across the country and rectification.

As an example, CAPE (or other measurements associated with HCW events) and even satellite images of some TSTMs are often cited as being "severe" or "significant" category etc. However, we do not even know how "severe" or "significant" it was without basing it to other baselines conducted outside our borders. Therefore, this certainly raises the need for assessing the interannual variability of these TSTM indices focused in the archipelago as a must, and needs investigation at all cost.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A – Data Archives

Over the course of this paper, I used several kinds of data coming from different archiving servers. This ranges from observations to NWP models all at which various time scales (mostly for a day-long) and resolution. If one is looking for such, I highlight and list down in this section all the data bases I utilized to source those.

1. CDS - Climate Data Store
2. DIAS - Data Integration and Analysis System
3. Digital Typhoon - hosted by National Institute of Informatics
4. Manila Observatory - hosts 16 AWS in Metro Manila.
5. RDA - Research Data Archive
6. OGIMET - provides weather information service

7. THREDDS Data Server - hosted by Unidata; alternative to RDA
8. WWLLN - World Wide Lightning Location Network
9. UWyo - University of Wyoming's Atmospheric Sounding Database.

Querying the datasets are straightforward as creating initially an account both in the CDS, DIAS, and RDA. Meanwhile, the THREDDS is an open-source web server as hosted by Unidata which does not require any sign up. Similar to above is the OGIMET as being an open server where you can query SYNOP and other reports, if one needs or depending the needs. For both Manila Observatory and WWLLN, one may need to create a request to the contact person that the site enunciated. One thing to note here is that the WWLLN is a subscription-based server either yearly or monthly depending on the timescale of the data (recent, yearly, decadal etc.). But for small or couple of days of lightning data, they have a policy of providing small amounts of WWLLN data for free as a public service.

Lastly, the NWP models, including the raw Himawari-8 bands that are downloaded from DIAS, are in NetCDF (either nc or nc4) with CF-compliance (Climate and Forecast) file format that provides description and properties of the data. One may need to select all the variables needed and identify the coordinates of the area of interest as a *bounding box* (as latitude and longitude).

Appendix B – Code Availability

The codes that are crafted and utilized in this study will be open source and available on my GitHub and its repositories for future and related meteorological use and studies. These are relatively simple notebooks for analysis and visualization (i.e. cartographic/contour maps) that can be implemented.

For further information regarding visualizing the gridded data aside from the one that I created, one may head and check into Unidata's Python Gallery. Of course, keep in mind, that you need to install MetPy and its needed packages, to make your own beautiful plots.

However, I would like to emphasize, that I cannot completely share the whole dataset that I used throughout the course right away, in accordance to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (known as Philippine Republic Act 10173). Either one may need

to source for those at the following archives I've listed in Appendix A or through contacting the corresponding author upon an acceptable and reasonable interest/request.

Appendix C – Model Sounding Profiles

Since I intuitively included a small sounding profile evolution of the Manila Tornado environment, one can/will also look for the individual profiles without the fancy design techniques. In this additional section, each individual model profiles extracted from ERA5 Re and NCEP FNL were given, starting with the ERA5 Re Skew-Ts and Hodographs moving to the NCEP FNL profiles.

Figure C1

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 00 UTC. Red (T and T_V) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C2

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 01 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C3

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 02 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C4

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 03 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C5

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 04 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C6

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 05 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C7

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 06 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C8

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 07 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C9

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 08 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C10

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 09 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C11

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 10 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C12

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 11 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C13

ERA5 Re Sounding Profile at 12 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C14

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 00 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C15

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 01 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C16

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 02 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C16

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 03 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C17

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 04 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C18

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 05 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C19

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 06 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C20

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 07 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C21

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 08 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C22

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 09 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C23

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 10 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C24

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 11 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C25

ERA5 Re Hodograph Profile at 12 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C26

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile at 00 UTC. Red (T and T_V) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C27

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile at 03 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C28

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile at 06 UTC. Red (T and T_V) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C29

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile at 09 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C30

NCEP FNL Sounding Profile at 12 UTC. Red (T and T_v) and Green (T_D) lines are depicted. Parcel profile lifted from the surface is shown as orange dashed lines while shaded by light red is the CAPE area under the curve.

Figure C31

NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile at 00 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C32

NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile at 03 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C33

NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile at 06 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C34

NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile at 09 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Figure C35

NCEP FNL Hodograph Profile at 12 UTC. The RM, MW, and LM components based of Bunkers ID are annotated while Deviant Tornado Motion (DTM) is included according to Nixon and Allen (2021).

Appendix D – Certificate of Grammarian

RIZAL TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY
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Department of Earth and Space Sciences
Center for Astronomy Research and Development

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the undersigned has reviewed and went through all the pages of the undergraduate thesis manuscript entitled: **“SEVERE WEATHER ANALYSIS OF TORNADO (SWAT): SYNOPTIC AND CONVECTIVE SETTING OF EF1 MANILA TORNADO (14 AUGUST 2016) OVER PHILIPPINES”**

The paper has been aligned with the set of structural rules that govern the composition of sentences, phrases, and words in the English language.

Signed:

Ms. Nicole A. Martinez / May 8, 2024
Grammarian

Appendix E – Certificate of Similarity Index

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 RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION OFFICE
 RESEARCH ETHICS REVIEW AND JOURNAL PUBLICATION UNIT

Control No. RERJPU-2024-006

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CAS CBEA CEng ICS IA CEd IHK GP LS

Title of Thesis:

Severe Weather Analysis of Tornado (SWAT): Synoptic and Convective Setting of EF1
 Manila Tornado (14 August 2016) over Philippines

Name of Author/s and Adviser/s:

Capuli, Generich H., Guido, Ryan Manuel D., Ordinario, Raymond C.

Paper ID number/s in Turnitin:

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Date of check:

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 DR. RUBY ANN B. DELA CRUZ
 Head, RERJPU

5-8-24
 Date

Note: Please print your completed form and sign it. Electronic record: print the form in PDF format.

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- Verbally skilled and willing to cooperate in different work field.

- Adaptive and flexible in the work field, can work with a great sense of responsibility.
- Organized and multi-tasker works under pressure simultaneously.
- Work devoted and willing to adapt new skills.

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